

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT AND COMMERCE

City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001

Karnataka State, India

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International Conference on

EMERGING TRENDS IN

MANAGEMENT, INFORMATION

TECHNOLOGY AND EDUCATION

Conference Date:
16/08/2019 and 17/08/2019

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PAPER 1

**CONSUMERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ONGOING
CRAZE OF WEB SHOPPING IN NAGPUR CITY**

¹Dr. Sohail Imran Khan, ²Mrs.Humera Khan

¹Assistant Professor ,Lebanese French University ,Erbil – Iraq

²Teacher, Erbil – Iraq

ABSTRACT

Evolution of technology has completely revolutionised day to day life of common man. Technology has penetrated in our life-like anything. These days everybody is using technology for their benefit's and marketers are not exception to it. They are using technology to reach to the customers. Days are far gone when people used to line up in stores to buy general product. These days, more and more people lean toward online shopping, which is presently a pattern of style and fashion. Nagpur, the center city of the country and world-famous for its oranges is advancing towards computerized explosion that makes high significance on the assessment of the present acknowledgment level of online shopping by the youngsters. In this way, understanding the by and large state of customer's attitude towards web-based shopping is significant for the Nagpurians. In this study 43 respondents took part in the survey. Respondents were selected through simple random technique. Data was analyzed using SPSS Version 22. This study found that online shopping is very common in this young generation of Nagpur. Major reason for Nagpurains to do online shopping is that it saves a lot of time. However, consumer those who do not shop online is only because of online fraud, lack of personal touch and no return policy. Nagpur consumers do prescribe online shopping as an elective path for shopping.

Keywords: Online Shopping, Shopping Attitude

PAPER 2

**AN INTERACTIVE EFFECT OF FINANCIAL
PERFORMANCE AND FIRM BEHAVIOUR ON
EMPLOYEE GENDER DIVERSITY OF THE LISTED
FIRM IN INDIA**

Kofi Mintah Oware*, Dr T. Mallikarjunappa**

*Research Scholar, Department of Business Administration, Mangalore University
Mangalagangothri-574199, Karnataka, Country of Affiliation: Ghana
, Mob. 09606316911, Email. owaremintah@gmail.com

**Professor, Department of Business Administration, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-
574199, Karnataka, Email. tmmallik@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

The industry recognises the disparity between women and men in employment and reasons accounting for the gap needs investigation. Therefore the motivation of this study is to answer the question that is lingering towards increasing women employment and contribution towards Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Using Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE) as a testing ground, and we use panel regression to analyse 28 sustainability-reporting firms between 2010 and 2017. Our findings show that interactive variable (SPR x culture) has a positive effect on gender diversity. The results support the argument that a firm with excellent stock market performance and increase family management presents will lead to an increase in employee gender diversity. Our second findings show that the interactive variable ((ROA, ROE) x culture) has a negative effect on women employment, but, positive interaction between SPR x culture and women in employment. It means stock market prices react positively to the presence of increasing attention by firms on gender diversity issues, but ROA and ROE and culture negatively respond to gender diversity issues. The third results show no association between interactive variable ((ROA, ROE, Tobin q, SPR) x CEO conservatism) and employee gender diversity because conservative CEOs are not abreast with issues relevant to millennial which includes gender diversity in the workplace. Further, there is a negative association between culture and employee gender diversity (gender diversity, women employment), an indication that without strong stock performance, an increase in family management alone leads to low employee gender diversity as evidenced in India. Lastly, there is no association between CEO conservatism (age) and employee gender diversity (gender diversity, women employment) and is because there are older CEO managing listed firms than millennial CEOs, hence the outcome from the study.

Keywords: Employee Gender Diversity, CEO Conservatism (Age), Culture (family management), Firm Behaviour, Financial Performance.

PAPER 3

**AN APPRAISAL OF EFFICIENCY AND
EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SUPREME COURT OF
BANGLADESH**

Mohammad Saiful Islam

Doctoral fellow, School of Law

Beijing Institute of Technology, Beijing, China

&

Assistant Professor, Department of Law

International Islamic University Chittagong (IIUC), Bangladesh

E-mail: saiful@law.iiuc.ac.bd

ABSTRACT

The Supreme Court is the apex institution of the adjudication system and constitutional body in Bangladesh. The Constitution mandates its functions and jurisdictions. It performs functions and duties not as a servant of the government but performs constitutional functions as a guardian to uphold the Constitutionalism, secure the Constitutional guarantee of the citizens'. It has unique and extraordinary inherent jurisdictions like writ, taking action for doing complete justice, review of its own decision, punish to contemnor, settle issues arise under the Constitutional interpretation, providing perfect direction of unambiguous law, provide advice. This paper analyzes the momentous issue of jurisdiction and functions of the Supreme Court from the legal and economic aspects with highlighting the efficiency of the apex court. It also examines with particular consideration of contempt of court matter.

Keywords: Supreme Court, Economic efficiency, Contempt of court, Constitutional law.

PAPER 4

PREPARING PUBLIC AGENCIES TO MANAGE MULTICULTURAL WORKPLACE EFFECTIVELY: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

Dr. Najwa Mordhah

Management Science Department, Yanbu University College, Yanbua, Saudi Arabia
Najwa_murdhah@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Since there is a scarcity of research relating to the cruise industry in general and its workplace in particular, this study aims to explore the factors creating a successful cultural competent workplace in the US industry cruise. In completing this study and presenting the results, lessons and a framework are provided that are intended to assist the public administration sector to develop an effective workplace. According to what this paper found, the cruise industry gives lessons to be learned. Public administration has to take advantage of others experiences dealing with diversity. Adopting the concept of cultural competency does not benefit only the public administrators at the workplace but it goes beyond that to enhance responsiveness. It is not only the work place that has diversity but also the entire community; therefore, public administrators have to be culturally competent to be able to interact with citizens and co-workers successfully. This exploratory study ends up with five factors generating a successful multicultural workplace in cruise industry. Many lessons have been extracted to develop a framework for public administration as an initiation to overcome the challenges of inevitable diversity either in the workplace or community.

Keywords: Diversity, Multicultural workplace, Cruise Industry, Public Agencies, Cultural Competency.

PAPER 5

THE IMPACT OF HOSPITAL ACCREDITATION ON THE PATIENTS SATISFACTION OF RADIOLOGY DEPARTMENT SERVICES

Dr. Zuber Mujeeb Shaikh, FISQua (Ireland), PhD, MPhil, MHM,
Director, Corporate Quality Improvement,
Dr. Sulaiman Al-Habib Medical Group,
Riyadh-11643, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Email-drzuber5@yahoo.co.in
Contact Number: +966-564629290

ABSTRACT

The quality of hospital radiology department service is one of the most relevant parameter of health care quality perceived by patients and by their families. Patient satisfaction is considered a way of measuring the quality of services provided. **Objectives:** To study the impact of National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH) Accreditation, India on Patients Satisfaction of Radiology Department Service. **Methods:** It is a quantitative, descriptive and inferential research based case study in which sample of a population was studied by structured satisfaction survey questionnaires (before and after the accreditation) in a private tertiary care hospital at Secunderabad, Telangana State, India to determine its characteristics, and it is then inferred that the population has the same or different characteristics. **Significance of Research:** It was observed initially before the accreditation that there was a lower patient satisfaction rate of the hospital Radiology Department Services, which was affecting the study hospitals' business. **Hypothesis:** Null Hypothesis (Ho) and Alternative Hypothesis (H1) were used and tested to compare the before and after impact of accreditation by applying to each question in the questionnaire. **Study Design:** The closed ended questionnaire was developed considering the Radiology Department Services by incorporating the six dimensions of quality Safe, Timely, Effective, Efficient, Equitable, and Patient-centred (STEEP) and tested prior to implementing. Questionnaires were given to the patients' families for completion upon using the Radiology Department Services two months before and two months after the accreditation. The data were collected in order to cover all three shifts of the Out-Patient Department Services. **Study Population:** Simple random sampling method was selected; the researcher had involved all conscious patients (clinical conditions) from all age groups. **Data Collections:** Primary data were collected from the survey questionnaires. Secondary data were collected from relevant published journals, articles, research papers, academic literature and web portals. **Conclusion:** At the 5 % level of significance, the t-test results indicate that there is a significant difference in the responses between before (M=37.32, SD=15.75) and after accreditation (M=47.02, SD=9.54) with p-value <0.001. The mean satisfaction score has improved from before accreditation compared to after accreditation.

Keywords: Patient Satisfaction, National Accreditation Board for Hospitals & Healthcare Providers (NABH) Accreditation, Radiology Department Services

PAPER 6

**MANAGING TIME AS A RESOURCE IN
ORGANIZATIONS & INDIVIDUALS – SOME
INSIGHTS & PROPOSALS**

Dr. Mike Dillon¹ & Dr. P. S. Aithal²

¹Chief Executive Officer, Institute of Productivity, 3rd Floor, Telegraph House, Chethorpe Road, Grimsby, United Kingdom
E-Mail: mike@instituteofproductivity.com

²College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA
E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

It is known that time and technology are two factors which can turn any substance into a resource. But the present study argues that time is the most valuable resource for both organizations and individuals. Doing right things at right time leads to organizational success for firms and career success for individuals. Unlike other resources, time is cannot be earned, stored, regenerated, and hence should be used efficiently and effectively by means of proper planning and utilising. Time is always a forgotten dimension of organizational & individual progress. Though there is many time related research there is little research on time as a resource in organizations and individuals. *Time* is a limited *resource* that expires every day. Good time management allows the executives in organizations and individuals in life to accomplish more in a shorter period of time, which leads to more free time to focus on more opportunities, lowers the stress, and leads to organizational success and career success for individuals respectively. In this paper, the efficient and effective use of time in the organizational lifecycle, and human lifespan are discussed. How proper planning in a matured way and doing multi-tasking in systematic way with time helps to manage the time resource in an optimum way. It is also argued that for organizations along with time, effective leader who can think from the top is important. For individuals, along with time, another resource identified as health is also important. The paper analyses how and why the effective management of time in organizations by its leaders for organizational success and effective management of time by individuals for career success.

Keywords : Time as a resource, Effective and efficient management of time, Time management for organizations, Time management for individuals.

PAPER 7

IMPROVING SECTOR -BASED PERFORMANCE AND COMPETITIVENESS USING “PROJECT BASED LEARNING” BUILDING WORLD CLASS SKILLS IN INDIAN MASTERS STUDENTS USING MODERN EDUCATION APPROACHES

MANOJ NAGARAJA

Business Development Officer, Institute of Productivity (IoP), U.K. Grimsby. Email:

manoj@instituteofproductivity.com

Prof .Mike Dillon, Prof. John Heap, Dr. Aithal, Hanna Bradshaw and Vivek Krishnamurthy.

ABSTRACT

The UK academic team from the Institute of Productivity have been appointed visiting professors at Srinivas University for over 10 years. Professor Dillon and Professor Heap have worked closely with the Vice Chancellor to provide support to students in the UK and are now working on the new programme link between WSB University in Poland, Srinivas University and the Institute of Productivity. The Srinivas / IOP overseas programme titled “Improving sector -based performance and competitiveness” will be delivered at WSB supported by IOP – through workshops, lectures, case studies and company diagnostic visits. The “PROJECT BASED LEARNING “ case studies will include a review of how companies can build productive capacity to compete and supply national and international markets. The need to drive innovation as a basis of ensuring long term sustainability of the business is studied using complex problem solving as a key area of work. The project management module will focus on strategic planning skills in creating clear theory of change, associated log frames and risk assumptions which need to be managed and tracked. The six-month study programme is designed to develop practical skills and know how to tackle these issues within a business in the sector of study being undertaken in the main programme at Srinivas. The material is based on over 30 years of project work undertaken by the IOP team especially with United Nations agencies such as UNIDO (Industrial development organisation) and FAO (Food and Agricultural Organisation). The meeting standards /winning markets module will be built specifically on the approach used by key UN agencies to ensure both regulatory infrastructure and market standards are used to build competitive businesses. We believe this “improved education “will improve the “company productivity” which the graduates support and will improve their own “skills”.THE approach is based on the previous work 30 years of project work and academic approaches led by IOP within “Humberside Polytechnic – now Lincoln University, Leeds Polytechnic – now Leeds Metropolitan University , and Grimsby Institute”

Keyword: Project Based Learning, Skills Development and Modern Educational Approaches.

PAPER 8

A CASE STUDY: TESLA MOTORS

Sunil Edward Mendes

Research Scholar, Department of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangalore
sunil.mendes@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Tesla Motors was founded in 2003 by Elon Musk and others. First American company to go public since Ford in 1956. Raised \$226 million in 2010 through IPO. They design and sell high performance, highly efficient electric cars. Presently the company manufactures and sells five models of cars; Model 3, Model S, Model X, Model Y, and Roadster. Located in the USA and expanded into Canada, Europe, Australia, and Asia. Tesla also manufactures solar panels and roof panels to produce electricity from solar energy and store energy in Powerwall, a home battery designed to store energy. There are many advantages of electric powertrains over internal combustion engines. They are highly energy-efficient, less noisy, very responsive and use sustainable energy. Navigate on Autopilot is an active guidance feature for Enhanced Autopilot that, with driver supervision, guides a car finding and following the most efficient path to the destination. Model 3 earned 5-stars in – evaluate a car's ability to protect adults, children, vulnerable road users like cyclists and pedestrians, as well as its safety assistance features. Through innovation, Tesla disrupted the global automotive industry. It outdid the competitors in the electric vehicle segment by implementing standardized production lines with world-class technology. Its innovative strategy in design, development process and marketing made it a leader with a difference in the automotive industry. Among the unique product features, its product innovation strategy focussed on the power system while its product development process centered on the maximization of speed. In this paper, we study the products and services of Tesla Motors, its environment and competitors and technology adaptation strategies.

Keywords: Tesla Motors, Electric cars, Powerwall, Autopilot, technology adaptation strategy, sustainable energy

PAPER 9

**A CASE STUDY ON CHALLENGES IN HIGHER
EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ITS INFLUENCE ON
STUDENTS**

Sangeetha Kulala K*

*Assistant Professor, Department of Management, SVR College of Commerce and
Management Studies, Bangalore – 560102, Karnataka, India

Email ID: sangeethakulalak17@gmail.com; Mobile No: +919741825182

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Education is a very important factor for the overall development of a country. Education provides an opportunity to reflect upon the social, economic, political, cultural, and moral or ethical issues facing by a human being. The main purpose of this research is to identify the current issues and challenges of higher education system and its direct and indirect effect on students. **Research methodology:** This research study is undertaken to understand the influences of higher education system on students and also to develop a cause - effect relationship. The sample sizes of 250 students pursuing higher education in various courses were collected. The sample was selected on the basis of questionnaire. **Findings –** The results of the present study indicate that there is a statistically significant impact of education system on students. It provides the platform to the students that help to build their personality and overall career growth. **Implication:** Here some implications are put forward for the improvement of quality of higher education in the country. Job-oriented courses should be provided in colleges and universities that would fulfil the skill based educational needs of the today's society. The government's scheme providing subsidized education to the students for economically backward families helps in a great extent. Special grants to universities and colleges in rural areas should be provided to improve their basic facilities, infrastructure and facilitate research or innovations, thereby converting the best into great institutions.

Keywords: Higher education, student career.

PAPER 10

A CASE STUDY ON CSR ACTIVITIES OF MRPL

Pratheeksha

Lecturer in Govinda Dasa College, Surathkal and Research scholar, Srinivas Institute of management studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore - India

Email: pratheeksha.anchan@yahoo.com or pratheeksha@gdc.edu.in

ABSTRACT

Corporate social responsibility is the concept of the day. Modification of Companies' Act 1956 to 2013 has emerged the importance of corporate social responsibility. Companies Act 2013 made it compulsory for the companies to spend 2% of their turnover or profit (with certain categories) on societal well being. CSR is the responsibility of the organisation to work for the development of the nation through contributing their percentage of profit for the improvement of society and the environment. CSR is not the donation it is one way of doing business and improving organisations image through contributing to education, poverty, Swachh Bharath, women empowerment, health and many more. CSR represents the company's norms, values, and principles to society. Because of compulsion by the Government, all the organisations are seriously involved in CSR activities. For the case study of CSR, I have chosen MRPL. Because MRPL is a central public sector organisation, earning huge profits and turnover over a decade. MRPL contributing much to the societal well being. The study is to examine the CSR activity of MRPL and the impact of CSR on the society as well as to the organisation and also to identify the progress of CSR activity. The case study is based on secondary data collected from journals, websites, newspaper and informal conversation with the CSR committee head of MRPL.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, societal well being, MRPL, progress.

PAPER 11

A CASE STUDY ON REINVENTION AND CHALLENGES OF IBM

K. M. Kiran Raj¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail: kiranraj224@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

International Business Machine Corporation (IBM) is one of the first multinational conglomerates to emerge in the US-headquartered in Armonk, New York. IBM was established in 1911 in Endicott, New York, as Computing, Tabulating, Recording Company (CTR). In 1924, CTR was renamed IBM. Big Blue has been IBM's nickname since 1980. IBM started with the production of scales, punch cards, data processors and time clock now produce and sells computer hardware and software, middleware, provides hosting and consulting services. It has a worldwide presence, operating in over 175 nations with 3,50,600 staff with \$79.6 billion in annual income (Dec 2018). It is currently competing with Microsoft, Google, Apple, and Amazon. 2012 to 2017 was tough time for IBM, although it invests in the field of research where it faced challenges while trying to stay relevant in rapidly changing Tech-Market. While 2018 has been relatively better and attempting to regain its place in the IT industry. With 3,000 scientists, it invests 7% of its total revenue to R&D in 12 laboratories across 6 continents. This led to IBM's 26th consecutive year of U.S. patent leadership. Of the 9,100 patents granted to IBM in 2018, more than 1,600 were related to AI and 1,400 to cyber security. It also helps in training people across the globe in new technologies. IBM Research scientists are pioneering work in field of artificial intelligence, block chain, security, cloud, quantum computing, nanotechnology, silicon, post-silicon computing architectures, Healthcare & Life Science. In this paper, we will the company's annual report to discuss Global Market, Strategies, Services, Contribution to Research, Social Responsibility, and Financial State. And also addresses how to use Garage technique in IBM Cloud, various cloud services, and how to manage them.

Keywords: IBM, Computing-Tabulating-Recording, Reinvention & Challenges, Garage Technique, IBM Cloud.

PAPER 12

A CASE STUDY ON TOKENIZATION OF REAL ESTATE USING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Jennifer Arun Mendes¹

¹Research Scholar, Department of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore. Email: jenniferarun@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In our world of continued technological revolution, most new technology aims to improve business and profitability. Blockchain technology is no exception. The Blockchain is an immutable, decentralized, distributed, public ledger technology in which transaction data is recorded. It is a business exchange network characterized by transparency, cost-effectiveness, enhanced security, immutability, traceability and accessibility. Over the past few years, Blockchain technology has emerged as new funding mechanisms for firms looking to raise money for ventures and projects. This paper is an exploratory study of the impact of Blockchain technology on investments in real estate using Tokenization. Real estate is property made up of land as well as anything on it, including buildings, flora and fauna, and natural resources. This could be categorized as residential, commercial and industrial. The global real estate market is estimated at \$217 trillion with a 25% contribution from commercial real estate. Real estate investment could be direct by buying land or property or indirect through buying shares in publicly traded real estate investment trusts (REITs) or mortgage-backed securities (MBS). As an investment, real estate offers income and capital appreciation. Due to the high cost of investment and complexity involved with these transactions, the ability to diversify and invest in real estate has historically been limited to institutions and high net worth individuals. However, the utilization of Blockchain technology can potentially revolutionize the dealings in real estate. Tokenization is the process of representing the ownership of real-world assets digitally on a Blockchain. It offers products and services for the creation, distribution, and transfer of digital securities. Tokenizing makes crowd ownership and fragmented sales of a single real estate possible.

Keywords: Blockchain technology, tokenization in real estate, investments in real estate

A CRITICAL CASE STUDY ON QUALCOMM AS PIONEERS OF WIRELESS REVOLUTION

Sangeetha Prabhu¹, & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail: sangeethaprabhu96@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The company Qualcomm established in July 1985 by Irwin Jacobs and Seven at San Diego, California, the United States. Qualcomm is an American multinational company, it aims to design, develop semiconductors and market wireless telecommunications equipment's and services. Qualcomm derives most of its revenue from chip making and patent licensing businesses. Qualcomm has offices at almost 33 countries with a global workforce of approximately 35,400 employees. For the fiscal year 2018, Qualcomm reported annual revenue of US\$21.301 billion, an increase of 2% over the previous fiscal cycle. Its shares traded between \$51 and \$75 per share, and its market capitalization at the end of fiscal 2018 was valued at US\$105 billion. The company is ranked 133rd on the Fortune 500 list of the largest United States corporations by revenue. The company is focused on various industries like automotive, education, healthcare, networking, Internet of Everything, mobile computing, smart homes, smart cities, smart homes, and wearables. Qualcomm's products include Gobi, Hy-Fi, IPQ, IZat, Powerline, Snapdragon, Small Cells, VIVE, Wi-Fi platforms, Mirasol, Pixtronix, AllPlay, 2net, Brew, HealthyCircles, QChat, QLearn, RaptorQ, Vuforia, Halo, and WiPower. In this paper, we are analysing business strategies of qualcomm by studying various things like the corporate history, financial strategy, legal issues, strategies to boost revenue, various technologies, STEEP and SWOT analysis, target markets and key company challenges of qualcomm.

Keywords: Qualcomm, Wireless Technology, Electronics Industry, Case Study, IT Company, Telecommunications Industry

PAPER 14

A CRITICAL STUDY ON ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION SECURITY -A CASE STUDY FROM COGNIZANT TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS

Anvar Shathik J¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University College of Engineering & Technology, Mukka,
Mangalore, 574146, Karnataka, India

²Associate Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru-575001, Karnataka, India
Email: anvarshathik@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Security was not a major concern of past in Information Technology Organizations. But presently, due to vast growth in fraud and hacking techniques, security of Organizations is a great concern. The Organizations usually spend millions every year just to protect their environment and to maintain security. As the hackers are becoming hard and tricky, the major IT Organizations are willing to pay large sum of money for providers offering services of enterprise security schemes. The hackers are always ready to intrude into company's valuable information sources. As per the recent survey by 'Security Week', nearly seventy percentages of respondents have faced a security threat which ended up in loss of valuable information or collapse of functioning in last year. It is true that an employer of the company can be a major attacker than an outside intruder. An employee of the company is already having all privileges to use resources of the company while various other ways are needed for an outer intruder for accessing the same company's network or data. Cisco, the networking giant has major focus on Enterprise Security Policies. This company has seen a valuable improvement in the last few decades, which shows the importance of security. Cisco had recently released a data that showed lack of security policies in about 23 percentages of companies worldwide. More than 70% of Information Technology persons say that their organizations lack behind in areas of security policy. They function as road maps which each employee of the company use in various ways. Developing a well-defined policy requires an artistic skill. The chief Information Security Officer is mainly responsible for implementing these policies and definitely the CEO of the Company as well. The best security policies consider vision and mission of companies, the important assets that need security and security threats imposed against certain factors. All these come under risk management which needs defect identification by business impact policies. The weakness of a company has to be identified as to find the vulnerability ratio of that company. Designing a security policy is not a nightmare once major scope of policy design is identified. The major challenge lies in identifying the scope and threat areas for security policy. Policy is nothing but a collection of guidelines and procedures on what and how it can be implemented. In this paper we are analysing that how CTS maintaining its standards, policies, technologies and management policies which are defined for securing data of an organization.

Keywords: Security, Information Security, Cyber security, InfoSec, Security Analysis, Cyber threats, Vulnerability, Security policy, Cloud Security, Cyber Maturity.

PAPER 15

**A CRITICAL STUDY ON STATISTICAL ANALYSIS
SYSTEM AS ONE OF THE PROMINENT DATA
ANALYTICS SOFTWARE SUITE**

Krishna Prasad K

College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India
Email: krishnaprsadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

ABSTRACT

Statistical Analysis System (SAS) is software suites comprising of nearly two hundred software packages, initially developed by SAS institute for the purpose of various analytics which includes multivariate analysis, data management, and predictive analytics by making use of descriptive analytics. SAS is initially developed for the purpose of analysing agriculture data which began as a project sponsored by National Institute of Health (NIH) by the efforts of North California (NC) State University and Seven other universities in 1966. From 1976 to till today SAS has undergone dramatic and drastic changes and today has become one of the pioneer or prominent data analytics tool which stands front compare to other analytics package like Bio Medical Data Package (BMDP), Minitab, R, R-Plus, Revolution R, S-Plus, Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS), Statistica, Python, Stata, and Systat. Today in all over the globe SAS is considered to be one of the most favourable and rich procedure supported software suite. Data analytics helps in various angles for an organisation like efficiently reduce the cost by managing resources, better decisions at right time, better customer support by addressing the challenges of needy customer, and helps in generating advanced or new generation products. In literature there are various tools to analyze data under two major categories as paid tools and open source tools. The common paid tools are excel, spunk, tableau, Qlik, Splunk, and SAS. The common open source packages are storm, R, Spark, Hive, and Python. This paper critically studies SAS various data analytics capability in various perspective. This paper throws light on various SAS components or packages like BASE SAS, SAS/STAT, SAS/GRAPH, SAS/OR, SAS/ETS, SAS/IML, SAS/AF and many more which help to know the capability of SAS as a one of the prominent data analytics software. This paper also compares and analyzes SAS with various open source and paid data analytics package. This paper analyzes the various challenges of the data analytics and how these challenges can be overcome to some extent using SAS software suite. This paper could play an active and supportive role in the real research of SAS.

Keywords: SAS, Open Source, Data Analytics, SAS procedures, SPSS.

PAPER 16

A CRITICAL STUDY ON THE MEASURES TAKEN BY COGNIZANT TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACHIEVING THE SUSTAINABLE GROWTH IN DIGITAL MARKET

K. Geetha Poornima¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹ Research Scholar College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas
University, Mangalore, India

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India
Email: poornima.sanjay@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cognizant Technologies is a multinational company whose headquarters is in Teaneck, New Jersey, United States. Founded in the year 1994 by Kumar Mahadevan, it provides services in Information Technology, Information Security, ITO and BPO. The major services provided vary from Business and Technology, Consulting, Application Development and Maintenance, IT Infrastructure, Business Intelligence, Data Warehouse, Health Care, Mobile Computing Customer Relationship Management, Supply Chain Management, R&D Outsourcing and Testing Solutions. It has more than 286000 employees round the globe and in India 150000. There are 166 centres which are spread across the world in UK, Hungary, China, Canada, Brazil of which several Regional Development Centres in Manila, Philippines, Mexico. In India, there are 10 centres with Chennai being the largest in terms of head count. The annual turnover of Cognizant Technologies is \$16.12 billion with 3-4% sustainable growth. It is ranked as 193 on Fortune 500 Companies in 2019 and 16 in Barrons 100 Most Sustainable Companies in the year 2018. 90% of its annual revenue is generated from customer retention. It has around 200 acquisitions of which Zenith Soft Vision being the prominent one in the current year. The strategy of this company is to grow organically by reducing the use of natural resources and to grow inorganically through the acquisitions. In our paper we have tried to study the business model of Cognizant Technologies, business strategies, measures taken by the company in terms of skill development of its employees, role-based career structure followed, marketing strategy, and Customer retention as steps towards sustainable growth. We also focus on company's contribution towards green initiative and Corporate Social Responsibilities. Finally, we have analysed Cognizant company's best practices and innovations towards latest digital business such as Internet of things, Data Science, Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Cloud Computing etc. to consider it as global leader in digital business.

Keywords: Cognizant, Business Model, Customer Retention, Digital Market, Critical Study.

PAPER 17

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON COMPARISONS OF
STOCK PRICES PREVAILING IN THE CASH
MARKET AND FUTURES MARKET.**

Wilma Carol Martis, Priyanna Noeline Dcunha,

Students of 2ndMCom, St Agnes Centre for Post-Graduate Studies and Research, Bendoor,
Mangaluru – 575002.

ABSTRACT

In this current era of the 21st century, the economic scenario of our nation has taken altogether a 360 degree turn. Many companies such as Infosys, ITC, TATA, Reliance, etc have established themselves in the national as well as international market. Most of the Indians have come up with various start-ups. This has altogether contributed in the improvement of the economic conditions of our country. Through the growth of various industries and sectors, many people have started to invest their earnings in various companies of different industries, namely, the banking industry, the pharmaceutical industry, the textile industry, the steel industry, the automobile industry and many more, with an expectation to earn a high rate of return. The investors evaluate the best companies in which they can invest through NSE NIFTY and BSE SENSEX. Sensex is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE). Nifty is a figure which indicates the relative prices of shares and stocks of the companies listed under the National Stock Exchange (NSE). Derivatives are the products that derive their value on the basis of an underlying asset. The underlying asset can be a commodity, a currency or a security. Among the various types of derivatives, we are going to consider futures as the main highlight in our study. The main aim of our study will be to compare the share prices of various companies of different industries in the cash market and the futures market. The data that will be collected by us for our study will be secondary data and we will understand the changes in prices of the cash market and futures market through trends.

Keywords: Companies, prices, derivatives, market, industry, stock, shares.

PAPER 18

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON MIGRATION OF
HUMAN RESOURCE IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANGALORE
AREA**

Miss.Navya Kini H¹, Miss. Ambritha²

^{1&2}M.com Final, St. Agnes Centre for Post Graduate Studies and Research
Mangalore, Karnataka, India, Email:navyabantwal@gmail.com,
Email:ambruuvinu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Migration is a number or body of persons or animals migrating together. In layman's language it is termed as shifting, transferring or moving of people or animals or anything from one to another for the purpose of employment, education, or any other purpose. This paper focuses on migration of labours of construction industry. The migrants are from Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh and other states of India. The main source of data for this paper is collected by Personal interview method of primary data collection method. In this paper the data are collected for analysing reasons, effects, life conditions and other aspects which led the labours to migrate themselves.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Labor migration, remittances, working conditions, wages construction, poverty, well being.

PAPER 19

**A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE IMPORTANCE OF
EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM FOR THE SOCIAL
CHANGE**

Ms. Maithri¹, Ms. S.M Riha Parvin²

^{1&2} M.com St. Agnes Centre for Post Graduate Studies and Research Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: maithri98@gmail.com, riharafiq123@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present article studies the importance of education in the personal, social and economic development of the nation. Education empowers our mind that will be able to conceive good thoughts and ideas. It also enables the students to do the analysis while making life decision. Unfortunately, schools and college teachers is only behind completing the syllabus for the year and the results of the examination. Today the result is excessively focused on memorization. Let's understand the essence and the purpose of education as articulated by the National Policy of Education, 1986. The initiatives should be brought up by the teachers which helps in instilling the values and a greater sense for the purpose to prepare the future generations for the effective social makers. The education provided in schools and colleges and the efficient need for the society's growth should go hand in hand. Education must promote knowledge and integration among the people by broadening the visions of students and nationalism in the students. If we accept that, the education should influence on shaping society, then it is clear that we must focus on the real goals of education.

Keywords: Teaching, Educational system, Transformative learning, Development of personnel, Economic growth

PAPER 20

A HYBRID DESIGN TO TRAIN SVM USING RANDOM FOREST AND LDA

Sujina S¹, Remya R²

¹Faculty, College of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore

²Asst. Professor, Amrita School of Engineering, Amritapuri, Kollam, Kerala

Email: sujina.pdma@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Zero-day cyber-attacks such as worms and spyware are becoming increasingly widespread and dangerous. The existing signature-based intrusion detection mechanism is often not sufficient in detecting these types of attacks. As a result, anomaly intrusion detection methods have been developed to cope with such attacks. In this scenario, an effective network security strategy which detects the threats in the network has its importance. Among the variety of anomaly detection approaches, the Support vector machine (SVM) is known to be one of the best machine learning algorithms to classify abnormal behaviors. We address the following two problems of the NIDS system; the volume of data that has to be processed for identifying threats and the selection of relevant features which are contributing towards the abnormality of the dataset. Generally, threats are identified based on a set of features in the attack signatures but proper discrimination is possible only with the most relevant subset of it. Also, training a machine learning system with a large number of the training dataset is a tedious task and hence a better approach would be to select the training dataset by using cross-validation test which may not provide full details of the training dataset. We propose an anomaly detection method which uses machine learning approaches SVM, Random forest and LDA. Here Random forest and Linear Discriminant algorithm is used to choose the predominant the features and information extraction from a huge dataset NSL-KDD. Random forest gives the most important features contributing to the anomalous behavior of a connection. Reduction of huge data is done by LDA and the features obtained are used to train SVM thus making SVM quick and prevalent learner. The proposed system has a remarkable increase in accuracy and precision.

Keyword : LDA, NSL-KDD, SVM, Random forest, NIDS system

PAPER 21

A STUDY ON BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON FINANCIAL SERVICES IN MANAGEMENT

Bhuvana R. * & Krithi. **

*Research Scholars, College of Management and Commerce Srinivas University, Mangalore
-575001, India. E-mail: bhuvanareddy08@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Blockchain is changing the way the world lives and works. In the case of financial services, the use of blockchain is highly witnessed these days. Financial service firms and new entities are undergoing rapid expansion. The sector comprises of commercial banks, insurance companies, non-banking financial companies, co-operatives, pension funds, mutual funds, and other small financial entities. Blockchain technology, as well as distributed ledgers, is unique in many aspects they can revolutionize many industries, particularly in the finance world. Blockchain investors in financial services aren't small start-ups or fin techs many are medium-sized banks and large institutions. This paper contains companies who adopted blockchain for the financial service, use of blockchain in financial services, the difference between blockchain and distributed ledger technology and its impact of blockchain on financial services.

KEYWORDS: Blockchain, financial services, distributed ledger technology, and its impact

PAPER 22

A STUDY ON BUYING BEHAVIOR OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL FEMALE STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE TO BELTHANGADY TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT.

Samjoel Dias *& Jovita Priya Gonsalves**

*Lecturer in commerce ,Sacred heart college madanthyar Mobile - +917353959799
Samdias401@gmail.com

**Lecturer in commerce, Sacred heart college madanthyar,Mobile - +919148217564
itsjovi.priya@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

From the ancient literature to present all poets, writers have been symbolizing beauty to women. Beauty has been matter of concern and is the main subject to market any product for the marketer, in any advertisements, whether related or not marketers cast women as a symbol of beauty Majority of the women are beauty conscious when comparing to men they have got highly sensitive and soft skin, all females tend to purchase and use cosmetics either to safeguard their sensitive skin or to look beautiful. When we compare cities with rural areas cities are much smarter with all infrastructure facilities but rural areas are lagging behind so the people are. Buying behavior changes from one person to another because of difference in personal stimuli, perception and other factors. In cities people can get goods of their choice with ease but this is not so in the case of rural areas especially when they are lacking in transportation facility and network connectivity. Majority of the rural females are daily wage workers who work in either in the paddy fields or Areca estates. This paper is an outcome of an attempt made to know about the buying behavior of the undergraduate level rural female students of belthangady taluk while purchasing the cosmetic products, paper also highlights opportunities for the marketers to serve better and scope for entrepreneurship.

Key words: - rural female students, opportunities for the marketers, entrepreneurship

PAPER 23

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER'S OPINION ON BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECTED BRANCHES OF KASARAGODU DISTRICT COOPERATIVE BANK

Mr. P V Joseph¹, Dr. P N Raghunathan²

¹PhD Scholar, Bharathiar University- Coimbatore, Email: josephpv97@gmail.com

²Research Guide, HOD- Management Studies, Govt. Arts College, Coimbatore

ABSTRACT

Banking sector is the service industry which has shown a dramatic growth and development consistently for the last several decades. Banking industry of any country is highly instrumental in determining the magnitude of the developments of the industry and citizens of that country. India's banking sector has been characterized by the strong presence of public sector, private sector, cooperative and foreign banks. Cooperative banks that include the primary cooperatives, district cooperative banks and the state cooperative banks cater to the needs of the common man especially of the people working in the primary sector to a great extent. The district cooperative banks in Kerala are grown-up to a higher level that now they offer the services and facilities that are as competent as the one offered by any other well established commercial bank. This study has made an attempt to evaluate the opinion of the customers towards the products, services and facilities offered by the selected six branches of the Kasaragodu district cooperative bank. Twenty respondents were chosen randomly from each of these banks taking the sample size of the study to 120. The information was collected on factors such as Service capabilities, Customer services, ATM services, Employees, Paperless banking, Service quality and Product features. Statistical tools such as Factor analysis, ANOVA and T- tests were used to analyze the data collected. The study revealed that the customers have a favorable opinion on some of the factors, while they are not happy with some other factors.

Key words: Service industry, banking sector, district cooperative banks, customer services

PAPER 24

**A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL MEDIA
MARKETING TACTICS ON THE BUYING
BEHAVIOR OF GEN Z CUSTOMERS**

¹Swathi P K, ² Dr. Pavan K A

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Assistant Professor,
Kristu Jayanti College, Bangalore, Phone number: 9483354003, Mail ID:
swathipk92@gmail.com

²Dr. Pavan K A
Assistant Professor, KristuJayanti College, Bangalore

ABSTRACT:

In the era of digital marketing, the marketers have realized that the most valuable asset is getting the customer's attention repeatedly. The marketers are digging out innovative ways to reach their customer who are hooked on to various platforms on internet. Social media marketing is the latest trend which focuses as an innovative marketing tool. Social media marketing (SMM) is a form of Internet marketing that utilizes networking websites as a marketing tool. The goal of social Media marketing is to produce content that users will share with their social network to help a company increase brand exposure and broaden customer reach. As there are not much studies carried out on this trend, this paper attempts to analyze the impact of social media marketing on the buying behavior of Gen Z customers. Basically, Gen Z are people born between the year 1995 and 2010. They are also known as iGen. The survey tries to study the positive or negative impact of social media tactics such as online surveys conduction, blogging, Offers and online campaigns on the buying behavior of 120 Gen Z customers. The analysis of the results has been done using Anova and multiple regression tests. Most of the customers of social media marketing are influenced by the tactic of offers in Social media marketing and buy more products based on the same. We believe that the study will offer useful insights for both advertising scholars and personnel to understand this trend better and contribute towards introduction of better approaches to advertising.

Key words: Online surveys/polls/contests, Blogging, Offers, Online campaigns.

PAPER 25

A STUDY ON EMERGING TRENDS IN DIGITAL MARKETING IN INDIA

Kavitha J

Lecturer, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru,
Karnataka, India

Email: iamkavithaj@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Marketing is the main core of all business activities. Without marketing, organisations cannot sell the goods or services and without sales there is no revenue or income and without revenue or income people cannot run business. Just like how money is the lifeblood of business, marketing is also like a heart of any business organisation. Digital trends in marketing have come a long way in a short span of time. As digital trends is improving every year, marketers should always be aware and be ready for the changing trends in order to easily adapt with emerging technologies and stay ahead in the market. The digital marketing trend in India has been mounting for years now. It has led to present era to become sophisticated by becoming more responsive. It enhances the frequency and depth of its users. Digital marketing is in a booming stage, today in India. With striking features like cost-effectiveness, instant response, flexibility, convenience, effectiveness, digital marketing is making a strong impact in the world of marketing and advertisement. The digital marketing trends to be watched are artificial intelligence, voice search, voice shopping, technical skills. With these new trends emerging in the market, digital marketing can attract more customers to the business and satisfy them. However there is lot of work involved to stay ahead in marketing curve in 2019. This paper explains mainly about the emerging trends in digital marketing in India and it also highlights the opportunities available in digital marketing platform. This paper also speaks about why consumer prefers online marketing rather offline marketing because of which the digital marketing is booming every year and also the satisfaction level of customers.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Marketing, Marketing tool, trends and technology.

PAPER 26

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE WELFARE MEASURES

Prof.Yashashwi. A. Ail

Faculty, Department of Commerce and Management
Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore.
Email: Yashu.sgc@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Employees are the valuable human resource who influence organisational effectiveness by stabilizing the business environment. Every organisation has an important role to play in providing welfare facilities to the every employee not just monetary but also non-monetary, which go beyond money . A satisfied employee is the key ingredient for progress of every organisation and the concept of employee welfare was and will be always a part of organisational efficiency. These facilities may either be voluntarily provided by the progressive and enlightened employers at their will as a social responsibility towards employee, or laws may compel them to make provision for these facilities by the government and the trade unions. Employees have always been an integral part of an organisation and in this study an effort is put to realize the measures implemented to seek employee welfare in service sector by the way of making their work life contented. This paper also studies general employee welfare measures which are to be given to a employee which in turn may lead to employee development.

Keywords: Welfare, social responsibility, Employee Development.

PAPER 27

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF USING SMART CLASS ON STUDENT'S LEARNING IN SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF MANGALORE

Tanya D'Souza (Student), Rishel D'Souza (Student)

M.Com (1st Year), St Agnes Centre for Postgraduate Studies and Research, Bendore
Mangalore 575 002, Email: dsouza.tan1703@gmail.com, dsouzarishel@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

“Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world”-Nelson Mandela .Every country whether it is in developing phase or developed phase needs good education system for development of students. Quality education systems and proper dissemination of education values to students helps in the framing of intellectual minds for the growth of the country. It is immensely important for an educational institution to use best digital education techniques so that the youth of the country are instilled with knowledge required to contribute in the country's development. Digital education is a type of learning accompanied by technology. Studies have shown that the use of technology in schools have developed new and advanced way of teaching and learning. Smart class is a solution designed to solve the problem of teachers in meeting with new challenges and developing students' abilities and performance. A well designed module allows a student to visualize the concept and creates interest in the minds of students' hence helps the students' in understanding the concept. The study has been carried out in several schools of Mangalore to understand the level of effectiveness by the use of smart class compared to traditional way of teaching. This study focuses on the impact of use of technology (smart class) over students over traditional teaching method.

Key words: Digital education, Educational institution, Smart class.

A STUDY ON MACHINE LEARNING AND ITS APPLICATION ON EMAIL SPAM AND MALWARE FILTERING

Sachin Kumar¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Hierank Business School, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Machine learning is an artificial intelligence application that offers systems with the capacity to learn and enhance automatically from experience without explicit programming. Machine learning focuses on computer programs that can access information and use it to learn on their own. Some examples of machine learning are Database Mining for automation development: typical apps include Web-click information for improved UX (User experience), medical records for better healthcare automation, biological data, email spam, and much more malware filtering. Machine learning (ML) is the science, deals with statistical models and algorithms used by computer systems to efficiently perform a particular job without using explicit directions, relying instead on patterns and inferences. It is viewed as an artificial intelligence subgroup. Machine learning algorithms create a sample data-based mathematical model, known as "training data," to create projections or choices without the job being explicitly programmed. Machine automated learning algorithms are used in a wide variety of applications, such as email Filtering and computer vision, where specific instructions or algorithms are used to perform some impossible task. Machine learning is closely associated with computational statistics that focus on computer-based predictions. Mathematical optimization research provides the field of machine learning with methods, theory and application domains. In this paper, we present extensive apps of the most effective content-based spam filtering methods such as Word Obfuscation, Bayesian Poisoning Attacks, Backscatter Spam, Image Spam, Botnet Spam, and Social Engineering Phishing, etc. We concentrate mainly on spam filters and their variants based on machine learning and report on a wide review ranging from surveying appropriate thoughts, attempts, efficiency, and present advancement. The original background exposure examines the basics of filtering e-mail spam, the changing nature of spam, spammers playing cat-and-mouse with e-mail service suppliers (ESPs). We conclude with applications & their effect of filters based on Machine Learning and explores the promising offshoots of the recent innovations. However, there are still some exceptional email spam filtering issues as mentioned above. The anti-spam study will stay in an active study area until further improvements in spam filtering occur.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Spam, Filtering, Phishing.

PAPER 29

**A STUDY ON PROSPECTS AND PROBLEMS OF
HERITAGE TOURISM IN COASTAL KARNATAKA**

Lakshminarayan Karanth¹, Mallika A Shetty²,

¹Assistant Professor, Head department of Economics, MGM College - Udupi

²Department of Commerce, MGM College - Udupi

ABSTRACT

India is a vast country of great beauty and diversity and her tourist potential is equally vast. With her rich cultural heritage as superbly manifest in many of the architectural wonders (palaces, temples, mosques, forts, etc), caves and prehistoric wall paintings, her widely varied topography ranging from the monotonous plains to the loftiest mountains of the world, her large climatic variations ranging from some of the wettest and the driest as well as from the hottest and the coldest parts of the world, beautiful long beaches on the sea coast, vast stretches of sands, gregarious tropical forests and above all, the great variety of the life-style, India offers an unending choice for the tourist. In developing countries like India tourism has become one of the major sectors of the economy, contributing to a large proportion of the National income and generating huge employment opportunities. It has become the fastest growing service industry in the country with great potentials for its further expansion and diversification. Tourism industry is capable to generate employment to both skilled and unskilled workers, directly and indirectly. This paper studied the problem faced by tourism industry in coastal Karnataka.

Keywords: Tourism, Development, Problems, Opportunities, Coastal Karnataka

PAPER 30

A STUDY ON RECENT TRENDS IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Swathi, Sudheesha Poojary

Assistant Professor, Shree Devi College, Ballalbagh
Principal, Shree Devi College, Ballalbagh

ABSTRACT

Human beings are the most important resource in an organization. A firm's success depends on the capabilities of its members. Continuous changes in technology, economic, social and psychological understandings and structures have influence on both Human Resources and their management. Current models of HRM suggest that expectations about HR roles are changing as organizations are striving to make the HR function leaner and more 'strategic'. The aim of this article is to understand recent trends in human resource management and to review existing research with regard to these recent trends. As a result, the following trends are identified: Labour market communication and employee branding, employee experience, artificial intelligence, autonomy to employees, investing in talent, remote staff, employee engagement relevant existing research is reviewed and avenues for future research are discussed.

Keywords: Human resource management, opportunities, trend, management.

PAPER 31

**A STUDY ON SMART, INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE
TEACHING METHODS**

Ch. Asha Jyothi¹ and Dr. D. Nagaraja Kumari²

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Education

² Assistant Professor in IASE, Department of Education

A.U College of Arts and Commerce,

Andhra University, Visakhapatnam – 530 003, AP, India

chashajyo@gmail.com, dnagarajakumari255@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Advanced pedagogy is the way to enhance teaching and learning performance creatively. Different innovative creative teaching methods are now in use across the globe. Innovative teaching includes e-learning in addition to face to face teaching. The present study involves student innovative characteristics, the teachers and administrators' perceptions, conceptions and teaching strategies about creativity and innovative creative teaching. Innovative teaching methodologies such as short lecture, simulation, role play and problem-based learning are very useful in addressing the technological advances that will be required in the foreseeable future. We also studied the empirical research on the instructional practices promoting the students creativity, innovation and innovative thinking and the current trends in teaching and learning.

Keywords: Teaching methods, innovative teaching, instructional practices, student creativity.

PAPER 32

A STUDY ON TASTE AND PREFERENCE OF RURAL POPULATION TOWARDS USED PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MOODABIDRI, D.K

Mr. Elson Dsouza¹

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration,
St Agnes College(Autonomous) Bendur, Mangaluru - 575002.

E-mail: elson@stagnescollege.edu.in

ABSTRACT

A second-hand or used good is one that is being purchased by or otherwise transferred to second or later end user. Second hand items may be transfer between friends or family for free, or they can be sold at lower price at garage sales. Many people prefer to buy new goods, since new goods can make them feel safer. A warranty is provided for new goods they can fix for free or simply change a new one, buy new goods also can avoid buying stolen goods. But second-hand goods has significant benefits such as prevent them becoming waste and saves costly production of equivalent new goods. It can conserving natural resources and protecting the environment, and may from part of a simple living plan. The second-hand market is exciting developing now. Since global financial crisis hit, people turn to shopping in an economy way, so the second hand trading market benefit from this struggling economy. Therefore marketing of used products is a good marketing opportunity. This study gives some suggestions to improve the used products marketing strategy in rural selling and market promotion strategies framed by analysing rural buying behaviour.

Keywords: New goods, second-hand goods, Market, Opportunity.

PAPER 33

A STUDY ON THE ACTIVE PARTICIPATION OF STAKEHOLDERS IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

Anupama.R

Research scholar in Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Education is a process of facilitating learning that includes acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. A well-rounded development should be made in pupil. Students are taught to become well balanced personalities emotionally and intelligently. A better society can only be created through educating the whole society. School is a miniature of society. All areas of students are together studying in schools. Especially EFA (Education For All) made a lot of opportunities to all students school education. So quality education is a main cause of concern. Stakeholders especially School Management Committee and Parent Teachers Association can contribute a lot in quality education in elementary level. In Kerala public schools include government schools and schools working with government aid. Parent Teachers Associations in aided schools and School Management Committee in government schools take a major role in empowering academic quality. It is through development of structure and surroundings of schools. They can contribute in infrastructure development, development of library, laboratory, playground, smart classrooms, etc. Besides, Parents involving in academic matters like workshops in teaching learning materials. In many of schools PTA helped to buy vehicles to reduce journey problems, organizes community living camps, collects food items for breakfast, noon meal items etc. The parents are very much cared about basic skill development. But if the PTA or SMC is weak, we can see the quality of education is lesser. So a study on the role of SMC and PTA to developing academic quality is needed.

Keywords: elementary education, Smart Class, Stakeholders in Education

PAPER 34

**A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN LEADING
AN EFFECTIVE LIFE AT PRESENT ERA**

Dayana K*, D'Mello Laveena**

*II MSW Student, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: dsouzadayana898@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education in the present era is the most important and powerful instrument to shape and mould the individual and the society in a desirable manner. Any modification brought about in the behavior of an individual as a result of his interaction with inner self and outer world constitutes learning. Today life is education and education is life. Hence no differentiation can be made between life and education and the Right to Education, therefore is looked upon as Right to Life. The Right to education which is characterized as a fundamental right can also be considered as a Right of Higher Order that it determines whether other rights can actually exercised or not. Right to Education can be realized on a national level only through compulsory education or free and compulsory education. Modern Education is aided with a variety of technology, computers, projectors, Internet and many more. Diverse Knowledge is being spread among the people. Everything that can be simplified has been made simpler. Internet provides unlimited information on different subjects of education. In this paper the researcher wants to highlight how the present education will help to lead an effective life in the society because education in present era is mainly based on online education and increases day by day. Then there are challenges to choose which is good, effective and helpful to lead a happy life and to differentiate what is right and wrong. Impact and measures have been suggested at the end of the paper.

Keywords: Education, Modern era, Internet, Value based education, Behavior and Effective life.

PAPER 35

A STUDY ON THE WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES – WITH REFERENCE TO TEACHING FACULTIES

Sr.Clera Rodrigues¹ and Mrs Dsouza Prima Fredrick²

^{1&2}Assistant Professor, St Agnes College (Autonomous), Mangaluru, Karnataka, India
Email: ¹srclera@stagnescollege.edu.in; ²prima@stagnescollege.edu.in

ABSTRACT

A study on Work – life Balance with reference to women employees has gained an importance since the time has changed from men earning the family living in today's world where both men and women equally share the responsibility of earning for the betterment of their family life. Therefore, it is very necessary to know how the women balance their professional and domestic life. In the initial stages, women had to struggle a lot to establish their identity in this competitive world, both in the society as well as in the professional life. But with the advancement in educational and training institutions, things have improved to a great extent. Women in India have broken barriers and built bridges in the professional flat forms. Work-Life Balance focuses on two main aspects called Achievement and enjoyment. After the Industrial Revolution in the second half of the 18th century, there was a tremendous change in the pattern and concept of professionalism. This has given a new dimension to work-life balance. But there is no one perfect shape to work-life balance. A woman faces a great challenge with changes in priorities and in status, like when one is spinster, after marriage, after childbirth, when a new career begins and this keeps on changing till one's retirement. It is to be noted that educational field currently has not only created plentiful job opportunities but has also resulted in new types of challenging careers. As this field gives more emphasis to knowledge alone it is non-discriminating in nature. It provides opportunities for the educated, middle class women to impart knowledge, build their own dreams and excel in fields. Though they are not the majority, Indian women teaching faculties are definitely on the rise and are paving the way for future generations. Indian women are becoming increasingly visible and successful in the professional and public sphere. The present study explores aspects like to measure the level of satisfaction as perceived by the women-respondent employees on the varied determinants of work life balance, to identify the major factors that influence the work life balance among various categories of women teaching faculties and to measure the overall work life balance of women teaching faculties irrespective of cadres. The conclusion has been given.

KEYWORDS: Women Employees, Education Field, Performance, Women Teaching Faculties Careers Opportunity.

PAPER 36

**A STUDY ON WORKING CONDITIONS OF
EMPLOYEES IN PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS AND
THEIR IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION WITH
REFERENCE TOKENGRI-BANGALORE CITY**

Namreen Asif Va

Asst. Professor, Department Of Commerce, Benedictine Academy, Ashirvanam,
Anchepalaya, Bengaluru- 560074

ABSTRACT

In this highly competitive world, success of any organization depends on its human resource. Banks are no exception to this. A satisfied, happy and hardworking employee is the biggest asset of any organization, including banks. Workforce of any bank is responsible to a large extent for its productivity and profitability. Efficient human resource management and maintaining higher job satisfaction level in banks determine not only the performance of the bank but also affect the growth and performance of the entire economy. So, for the success of banking, it is very important to manage human resource effectively and to find whether its employees are satisfied or not. Only if they are satisfied, they will work with commitment and project a positive image of the organisation.

Key words: Working conditions, private sector banks, job satisfaction

PAPER 37

**A STUDY TO IDENTIFY CONSUMERS IN-STORE
PURCHASING BEHAVIOUR IN AN INDIAN SINGLE
BRAND RETAIL STORE**

Anil Kumar¹

¹Registrar, Srinivas University, Mangalore
& Prof. Srinivas University, College of Management and Commerce, Mangalore.
Email: akgnairs@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

In-store purchasing behavior is an important element for any retailer as it helps to better plan the last-minute conversion of the customer. A large body of research has examined consumer response to a retail stimulus. An area of growing interest seeks to understand the role of in store merchandising and offers in stimulating purchase behavior. This paper attempts to identify the various factors that impact the in-store behavior of a retail customer. The study was conducted in a single brand store located inside a mall in Mangalore. The choice of a single-brand store was aimed at understanding the effect of the brand on customer loyalty. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and ANOVA. In general, the study showed a positive relationship between store location, In store display, In-store deals. The study found that there is a greater correlation between customer loyalty and discounts when compared to the relationship between customer loyalty and brand name. This study will help the retailers to understand the customer response to various stimuli inside the store as also give a better understanding of enhancing the store competitiveness.

Keywords: In-store promotion, customer, loyalty, brand name, retail trade,

PAPER 38

**AN APPROACH TO STRENGTHEN THE SOCIAL
ECONOMIC CHANGE AMONG THE RURAL
WOMEN: A CASE STUDY ON ANVAYA**

Dr Suja John¹, Dr Parashurama Kamath²

¹Associate Professor School of Business Studies and Social Sciences,
Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore.

²Assistant Professor, School of Business Studies and Social Sciences,
Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore.

ABSTRACT

Social change is the change in social structure. It is the result of various social causes. Society can never remain static; it undergoes constant variations. Social change is used to describe variations or modifications of any aspect of social process, social pattern, social interactions, or social organisations (Jones, 2007). In contemporary era educational institutions, industries, organizations and NGOs are taking various initiatives and programmes to get the changes in the society which they would like to see. To bring positive socio-economic change among the rural women the Christ Deemed to be University, initiated Anvaya under the leadership of Department of Management Studies in the year 2015. Presently Anvaya is been taken care of by the Center for Social Action(CSA) wing of the institution. The very objective of the initiative was of giving back to the society and to help those in need as well as raising awareness within the college. The present study is a case study method wherein the researchers are trying to understand the benefits of the particular project to the society and their socio- economic development over a period of time. This study is to understand the acceptability among the community towards the various initiatives introduced under the banner of Anvaya- CSA. Also making an attempt to know the entrepreneurship skills they had acquired in the process and the barriers to accept the social change.

Keywords: Anvaya, Social Change, Rural Women

PAPER 39

AN INTERACTION EFFECT OF GIRLS MENTAL HEALTH, SCHOOL ADJUSTMENT AND HOME ENVIRONMENT ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN GEOGRAPHY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Prakash. Sannakkanavar

Assistant Professor, Department of Studies in Education, Karnataka State Akkamahadevi Women's University, Jnanashakti Campus, Torvi, Vijayapura-586105, Karnataka
Email:-Prakashanu88@Gmail.Com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to analyze independent and combined effects of variables viz., mental health (high and low), School adjustment (high and low) and Home environment (favorable and unfavorable) on Academic achievement in geography. The sample of the present study includes 260 girls studying in IX standard were drawn using stratified random sampling technique. Among the other things, the study revealed that, i) The girls with high Mental health have more influence on Academic achievement in geography than the girls with low Mental health in geography; ii) The girls with high Mental health and high School adjustment have more influence on Academic achievement in geography than the girls with high Mental health and low School adjustment; iii) The girls with high Mental health, high School adjustment and favorable home environment have more influence on Academic achievement in geography than the girls with high Mental health, low School adjustment and unfavorable Home environment.

Keywords: Girls Mental Health, academic achievement, home environment

PAPER 40

**APPLICATION OF HYBRID MODEL FOR
FORECASTING PRICES OF JASMINE FLOWER IN
BANGALORE, INDIA**

***¹Sunil, ²Satyanarayana, ³Sachin Acharya, ⁴Arun Kumar Jogi**

Department of Statistics Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Karnataka (India)

*Corresponding Author Email: sunildevadiga073@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The medicinal uses of Jasmin are well documented. It is used to enhance the immunity of the body, treatment of anxiety, stress, and sunstroke. The leaves are used in the treatment of mouth disease, treatment of cuts and wounds. The Jasmine plants is also the source of exotic fragrance. It is an important scent noted in perfumes and has herbal properties and hence today, Jasmine flowers are of much economic importance. Farmer's decision making on production of Jasmine depends on future price to be realised during the period of cultivation. Hence forecasting accuracy plays a vital role in Jasmine production. A hybrid model has been considered an effective way to improve the forecast accuracy. In this paper, hybrid model of SARIMA-ANN is proposed for forecasting the prices of Jasmine flower. We also compared the performance of hybrid model with traditional SARIMA model, ELM, MLP and NNETAR (ANN). The study concluded that the hybrid model of SARIMA-ANN is more appropriate model for forecasting the prices of Jasmine flower. The best model is used to forecast prices for next 12 months.

Keywords: SARIMA, ANN , Extreme Learning Machine, Multi-Layer Perce

PAPER 41

**CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH RUNNING A
GREEN BUSINESS IN INDIA AND OTHER
DEVELOPING COUNTRIES**

Sujaya. H¹, Meghana Salins¹ & P.S. Aithal²

¹Research Scholar, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore,

²College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Email: sujayaloknath@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Running a green business in India and other developing economies is indeed a challenging job for the producers involved in this business. In a green business environment, the company may re-design the product attributes since the usage of the harmful chemical may be prevented and scarce resources may not be exploited. The main objective of this case study is to assess the factors that are associated with running a green business in India and other developing economies. This case study also highlights the issues related to the green business. This case study is developed by using secondary data to assess the factors that influence green business. The secondary data was obtained from another exhaustive literature review of journals and internet sources. The developing economies strive hard to achieve green business since it has been a necessity for these countries to depend on natural resources. In addition, many developing economies face challenges basically related to power, water, ecological problems, social and economic problems and also problems related to weather and climate change. The developed economies need to import modern technology and technical knowledge from other countries because of the lack of their own technology and technical skills. The government has to take certain measures such as the provision of subsidies which may support the challenges of green growth and development. The short-term subsidies may not benefit more since it may hamper the production and demand by raising the price and cost. But as for the long term is considered these reforms may provide more effectiveness in productivity and thereby lead to changes in technologies.

Keywords: Green business environment, Challenging jobs, Developing economies.

PAPER 42

CHALLENGES IN MINIMISING THE ENERGY WASTE IN THE CABLE CONNECTING THE SOLAR PANEL AND CHARGE CONTROLLER

P. Sridhar Acharya * P. S. Aithal **

School of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru-575001,
E-mail: sridharaacharya@gmail.com* psaital@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

Solar energy system is one of the major renewable energy system used in the market as an alternative energy production system. This energy system being eco-friendly causes absolutely no harm to the environment. This energy system may be adopted for either commercially or independent domestic or industry use. The major challenge here is the efficiency of the system. Presently the efficiency is found to be somewhere around 20%. There are different reasons for such a low efficiency of the system. One of the major reasons is the cable loss. This presents the different reasons for the energy loss and concentrates on the cable loss. The paper also contains the reason for the selection of a thick and heavy cable which contributes to the energy loss. The paper also contains the need for selection of a long thick cable for the energy transfer from the solar panel to the charge controller. This paper introduces an alternate model to the existing system of transfer of energy from solar panel to the charge controller which minimises the energy loss. By using this model the cable need not be thick which contributes to the energy loss. The working of the model is explained in this paper. The advantages of and challenges in using this model is also analysed.

Key words: solar, energy, efficiency, cable, conversion.

PAPER 43

CHALLENGES OF DIGITAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

Vinil KumarSalanti ¹, Dr.T.Sharon Raju ²

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Education

² Assistant Professor in IASE

A.U College of Arts and Commerce, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam – 530 003, AP,
India, morisvini07@gmail.com, sharonrajut@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education globally is one of the important sectors to witness revolutionary changes in recent times. This happens primarily because of digital revolution taken place all across the globe. Digital education focused on all aspects of pedagogy and learning that involve computing Technology. New theories on teaching and learning that can be supported by computing Technologies. The modern society wants to you know the information as it happens and when it happens, and the world is moving from and information. Education reached most parts of the world and ICT has become an integral part of human life. This paper describes how technology is used to access and apply search knowledge. Digital b education is fun learning for all cadres and particularly effective for child learning as an innovative audio video feature boost the cognitive elements in a child brain. Learning is progressively affecting the both classroom and campus-based teaching however more import is prompting new models or structures for instructing and learning.

Keywords: Digital education, computing technology, innovative, modern society.

PAPER 44

CHOICE-BASED CREDIT SYSTEM IN INDIA: PROS AND CONS

**Johns Babu* , ThulasiP.S* ,Shashikala*
& Abdul Rasheed K.M****

*1st year MSW,

**Assistant Professor & HOD, Nehru Memorial College Sullia

ABSTRACT

Education system of India is full of intricacies of different nature. Every ladder of education has its own problems and prospects. However, attempts have been taken to lessen complexities. From ages, time to time commissions have been constituted to improve and remove the anomalies of Indian education system especially, ensuring quality and uniformity in India education system. Idea of Quality assurance cell has not only been mooted out but also implemented across the national level. Ensuring uniformity in Education System, especially at Under-Graduate level, Choice-Based Credit System has been confirmed mandatory. But the nature of Indian education system is much diverse and encompasses inherent problems of diversity in implementing the uniform system of evaluation. Present education system of India has got spread across the country in the form of Primary Education, Secondary Education and Tertiary Education. The last one of education sector has much importance in the process of developing nation. Major inventions and innovations have direct bearing on the quality of higher education. So, quality is the major concern of the present higher education which could be judged and assessed only by the universally acclaimed system of evaluation and this could be possible through the CBCS. Thus, the present article aims to highlight the merit and demerit of Choice-Based Credit System.

Keywords: Choice-Based Credit System, MHRD, UGC

PAPER 45

CONTENT DELIVERY NETWORK'S PIONEERING LEADER - A CASE STUDY ON AKAMAI TECHNOLOGIES INC

Yogish Pai U¹, Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

Email: yogish77pai@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Akamai Technologies, Inc., incorporated on August 20, 1998, is a content delivery network (CDN) and cloud service provider company headquartered in Cambridge, Massachusetts, in the United States. Its services include the delivery of content, applications and software over the Internet, as well as mobile and security solutions, and enterprise professional services. The Company's solutions include Performance and Security Solutions, Media Delivery Solutions, and Service and Support Solutions. Akamai was born from academia and research that spawned the algorithms needed to intelligently route and reproduce content across a large network of distributed servers. Dr. Leighton former head of the Algorithms Group at MIT's Laboratory for Computer Science and Mr. Lewin incorporated Akamai, with Jonathan Seelig and Randall Kaplan joining the founding team. The content delivery network of Akamai is one of the biggest distributed computing platforms in the world, responsible for serving 15-30% of all Internet traffic. The business runs a worldwide network of servers and rents resources on these servers to clients who want their websites to function quicker by distributing content from nearby places. Akamai has a worldwide presence with around 7,500+ staff with an annual revenue of \$2.7 billion. As of July 31, 2019, the Company has deployed globally-distributed content delivery network (CDN) with approximately 2,39,000 servers in 139 countries and nearly 1,600 networks around the world. For the second year in a row, Akamai ranked number 1 in the Boston Business Journal's 2019 as Largest Cyber security Companies in Massachusetts list. The goal of Akamai is to mitigate their worldwide operations environmental effect, infusing measurable sustainability practices into the organization. In this paper, we analyze Akamai Technologies operational and business level strategies along with products/services strategy, new technology adoption strategy, CSR strategy, marketing strategy, security strategy and new product development strategies. The paper also involves the company's innovation in sustainability through green strategy and corporate social responsibility strategy. Some recommendations are also provided based on the SWOC analysis to accelerate sustainable development.

Keywords: Akamai, Case study, CDN, Content Delivery Network, Performance and Security Solutions.

PAPER 46

CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT MATRIX AND BUYER-SELLER RELATIONSHIPS THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA

Dr K R Kumar¹, Sivaram M², Sathish V³

¹Associate Professor in MBA, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering (Autonomous), Hosur

²Third Semester MBA Students, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering, (Autonomous), Hosur

ABSTRACT

The opportunities presented by social media to help build close relationships with customers seem to have excited practitioners in a wide variety of industries worldwide. Academic scholarship on customer engagement, however, has lagged practice and its theoretical foundation is relatively underdeveloped and a better understanding of the concept is essential to develop strategies for customer engagement. This paper seeks to address some of these issues. The paper attempts to enhance understanding of customer engagement by examining practitioner views of customer engagement, linking it to the marketing concept, market orientation, and relationship marketing, modeling the customer engagement cycle, and developing a customer engagement matrix. The paper develops a model of the customer engagement cycle with connection, interaction, satisfaction, retention, loyalty, advocacy, and engagement as stages in the cycle. It arrays customers in a customer engagement matrix according to the degree of relational exchange and emotional bonds that characterize their relationship with sellers. Four types of relationships emerge: transactional customers, delighted customers, loyal customers, and fans. The paper is an initial attempt to develop a theoretical framework for customer engagement and further research is required to better understand several aspects of the framework.

Keywords: customer engagement, social media, marketing concept, relationship marketing

PAPER 47

**DETERMINANTS OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT
AND THEIR IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE
ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS**

Dr. Shiva Shankar K C¹, RoopaShettigar²

¹Dr. Shiva Shankar K C, Assistant Professor, Tumkur University, Tumkur

²RoopaShettigar, Research Scholar, Tumkur University, Tumkur

ABSTRACT

Employee engagement has emerged as a popular organizational concept in recent years. It is the level of commitment and involvement of an employee towards the organization and its values. In order to achieve and sustain organizational effectiveness, through employees' increased contributions, organizations, apart from task proficiency, becoming increasingly reliant on employees' discretionary efforts at workplace. The purpose of this paper is to identify the key determinants of employee engagement and their predictability of the concept. It also studies the impact of employee engagement on employee effectiveness. Convenience sampling technique is used to obtain the data for analysis. A structured questionnaire is made to obtain the data and the sample is 100 employees of few selected Nationalised Bank. The results of this study describe that if the training & development, compensation & benefits, leadership and organizational perceived support are at higher level then it will lead to the higher level of employee engagement.

Keywords: Employee engagement, organizational effectiveness, discretionary efforts, organizational perceived support

EDGING QUALITY OF WORK LIFE WITH INDUSTRIAL RELATIONS

Vallabhadas Kalpana¹, Sk.Razia Begam²

Associate Professor, Usharama College Of Engineering & Technology,
Telaprolu, Ganavaramu, Andhra Pradesh, India

E Mail: Vkalpanasudha@gmail.com

Assistant Professor, Usharama College Of Engineering & Technology, Telaprolu,
Ganavaramu, Andhra Pradesh, India,

E Mail: Razia.Bashirunnisa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the present era, employees are considered knowledgeable and what they bring to the world of work in terms of the knowledge and competency matters for the organizations in their desire to be accurate and effective. Industrial Relations, Job satisfaction and quality of work life needs to be addressed viably to keep them motivated. Organizations are looking for innovative ways of doing business in order to meet the dynamic challenges of today's business environment. Most of the Industries are interested in enhancing employee's quality of working life' (QWL) for good industrial relations and finally, try to instill the feeling of security, equality, pride and prestige among its employees. For this purpose, policies and procedures are framed in such a way as to make less work and more rewarding for the employees. These policies and procedures provide autonomy, recognition, good working environment, work culture and achieving awards in appreciation of work done etc. Therefore, organizations are required to adopt a strategy to improve the employees QWL for good industrial relations to accomplish both the organizational objectives and employee needs. In general parlance, Industrial Relations deals with the worker employee relation in any industry Government has attempted to make Industrial Relations more health the by enacting Industrial Disputes. Industrial relations in different countries have been influenced by a variety of circumstances and key players like political philosophies, government, owners. IR binds the function of rendering employees with a integrated voice, and unions with the means to establish formalized terms and conditions of employment not only within an enterprise but also across an industry, and sometimes across an economy. This was accomplished through the freedom of association, collective bargaining. Quality Work is an integral part of everyday life, as it is our livelihood or career or business. Research on quality of work life is considered to be more important at the individual and Industry level. Quality of work life is considered for both the employees and organization and it is involved with job satisfaction, productivity, job involvement, job enrichment etc.. This study is made to analyses the "Quality of work life in relation to industries". It emphasizes on quality of work life, and group effort, mutual benefits to both employees and employers. This article reviews the Origin and meaning of QWL, factors affecting Industrial Relations, QWL as a Philosophy, Key Players and Proposals for the improvement of QWL with Industrial Relations.

Keywords: Quality of Work Life, Industrial Relations, Impact, Edging, Proposals.

EFFECTIVE APPLICATION OF ICT IN THE FACILITATION OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN TAMIL NADU: A CASE STUDY

K. G. Nandha Kumar

School of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, India

Email: professorsorkn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Evolution of computer and internet has reduced the various complications in all the domains. Higher education has no exception in this. Distance education is one of the modes of higher education in India. Initially, it was introduced to provide the opportunity of higher education to the people who were unable to afford higher education in regular full-time mode. But later it is found as an efficient method for those who are interested in improving their knowledge & qualification while they are working. Greater developments in the field of computer science have made every industry be upgraded with computers and the internet. In this decade, the advancements in the internet have made tremendous changes in getting things done through computers and mobile devices. In that way, information and communication technology (ICT) is inevitable in the field of higher education too. Tamil Nadu is one of the states in the Republic of India and it is contributing a major part for the development of the country through its distance education institutes. A detailed study is conducted on the institutes of distance education in Tamil Nadu in terms of applications of information and communication technologies. This study has investigated various types of ICT applications in distance education institutes. In Tamil Nadu, both government and private universities are offering distance education under different faculties such as arts, commerce, management, and science. They have converted most of their functions from conventional mode into online mode. The advantages and limitations of applications of ICT in such institutes are studied and the outcome of the study is presented in this paper.

Keywords: ICT, E-Governance, Distance education, Teaching, Learning.

PAPER 50

E-HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

Girisha M C¹Dr. K Nagendrababu²

¹Research Scholar, DOS In Commerce, University of Mysore, Mysuru¹

²Associate Professor, Department of Studies In Commerce, University of Mysore, Mysuru²

ABSTRACT

Due to rapid growth of management activities there is no little chance for argument of the nation that people are one of the key assets focuses on the success or failure of an organization and hence the importance of the knowledge skill, attitude and behavior of those people for the betterment of the organization. People are the key assets that are capable of growth and development. The people are nothing but human resource, during the past 3 decades organizations have begun to embrace a “human asset approach” one that consider the money spent on integration with innovation in the workforce as an investment. As with any asset, by nurturing, protecting, and growing this investment, organizations that align workforce strategies with business goals and objectives will benefit from capturing and focusing the attention of workforce. After analyzing several theoretical perspective from different discipline such as organizational psychology, strategic management, strategic human resource management, organizational behaviour, industrial psychology, global human resource management this research developed a perception based approach to examine the challenges and possibilities that employees’ perceptions will be associated with the organizational changes. Specifically this research examined the perceptions of employees on e-HRM practices in an automotive industries in Mysore. This research address two major research questions relevant to organizational change management. What perceptions influence employees to resist to change and support to change?

Keywords: e-HRM, automotive, human asset approach

PAPER 51

**EMERGING TRENDS IN MANAGEMENT,
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND EDUCATION
INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE TEACHING**

Chandrakala B

Chikkamudnur village; Puttur D.K 574203; M:9591948739;

Email:chandrakalabptr@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The combination of education and technology has been considered the main key to human progress. Creativity and innovation can play an important role in the knowledge society creativity has been defined as a product or process that shows a balance of originality and value. It is a skill, an ability to make unforeseen connection and to generate new and appropriate ideas. Innovation is the application of such a process or product in order to benefit a domain or field-in this case of teaching therefore innovative teaching is the process leading to creative learning the implementation of new methods, tools and contents which could benefit learners and their creative potential. New and emerging technologies challenge the traditional process of teaching and learning and the way education is managed. Information technology while an important area of study in its own right is having a major impact across all curriculum areas. Easy worldwide communication provides instant access to a vast array of data, rapid communication, plus increased to access to IT in the home, at work, and in educational establishments, could mean that learning becomes a truly lifelong activity, an activity in which the pace of technological change forces constant evaluation of the learning process itself. Creativity and Innovation in education are not just an opportunity but a necessity. Innovative Teaching and learning technologies have also been useful an improving student activity and motivating them.

Keywords: IT, Communication

PAPER 52

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT SUSTAINABILITY

Dr. Sudha Tiwari¹, Dr. Rashmi Bansal²

¹Assistant Professor, Army Institute of Hotel Management and Catering Technology,
Kothanur Post, Bangalore- 560 077, India

²School of Management Studies, Indira Gandhi National Open University, Maidan Garhi,
New Delhi-110 068, India

ABSTRACT

Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability to identify and manage one's own emotion as well as the emotions of others. It is the combination of Interpersonal and Intrapersonal intelligence. It consists of a set of conceptually related mental processes of Self awareness, Social Awareness and Self Management. Employability on the other hand provides inner sense of stability and security which is related to sustainable employment. The objective of this research paper is to determine the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Employment Sustainability. Emotional Intelligence is positively related to career thinking, greater career decision making and high level of willingness to explore. It is also associated with important employment experience and its emotional attachment to the current job. People differ from each other while displaying their Emotional Intelligence. It is found that individuals who are able to manage their emotions at workplace have greater confidence in their skills and ability to conquer the business world. A quantitative survey design using primary data was used to fulfil the research objective. Primary data was collected through convenience sample with sample size of 50. The sample predominantly represents respondents from the Hotel Management background who are currently in employment with 7-8 years of experience in the service sector. The analysis of the Emotional Intelligence and Employment sustainability helps the organisation to optimize performance and job satisfaction of the employee.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Employment sustainability, Self awareness, Social Awareness and Self Management.

PAPER 53

ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN IT BASED EDUCATION

Mr.Rajesh.K, Dr.Udaykumar M.A

Email: rajeshkappanayil@gmail.com

Mobile: 9447374660

ABSTRACT

In the modern world of education information technology plays a significant role in alleviating the burden of teachers as it helps them to present their ideas attractively. It also helps them to evaluate their pupil, to take corrective actions, if any, and in decision making. IT based teaching enables the teachers to access the students who are anywhere in the world and at any time of their convenience. Entrepreneurs provide respective hardware and software to them as these are essential for IT based teacher-student communication. Websites are made available by such entrepreneurs to which teachers and students can register and they collect fees from students and pay remunerations to teachers. Mobile Apps and pre-loaded tabs are also available to students which help them in enhancing their knowledge. This study aims to address the opportunities and challenges of Entrepreneurship in IT based Education.

Key words: Teachers, Stuent, Entrepreneurs, Hardware, Software.

PAPER 54

EVALUATING THE COMPETITIVE EDGE OF COMPANIES IN GLOBAL ARENA – A STUDY

Meghashree¹, Sujaya H²

¹Lecturer, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru,
Karnataka, India

Email: meghashreekulal@gmail.com

²Research scholar, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru,
Karnataka, India

Email: sujayalokanath@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In a world is full of global competition, nations have become more or not less important. As the basis of competition has shifted more and more to the design and conceive of knowledge, the role of the nation has grown. Competitive advantage is created and sustained through a limited process. In International markets, innovations that yield competitive advantage predict both domestic and foreign needs. The internal environment operates like a moral principle to isolate or evict “hostile” individuals who challenge current directions or established thinking. If Innovation ceases the company becomes stagnant; it is only a matter of time before aggressive competitors overtake it. The data collected is based on secondary sources such as internet, exhaustive literature, websites etc. The objective of the study is to identify the competitive edge of companies and to investigate the world markets along with identifying the countries involved in global trade and to analyse the different strategy adopted by companies in global market. The scope of the study is based on the study of world markets and evaluating the competitive edge of the companies in global arena. For nearly more than two decades, emerging markets have generated a more successful investment opportunities across the world. Economies such as Asia, Eastern Europe, and Latin America started growing at a faster pace to the extent that it surpassed most developed countries.

Key Words: Global Competition, Competitive advantage, Global Arena, International Markets

PAPER 55

**EVALUATION OF MARKETING STRATEGIES &
CONSUMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS LAKME
COSMETIC PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO CHALLAKERE**

Prof. Leelavathi.K.

Asst. Prof. Dept. of Commerce & HOD, HPPC GFGC, Challakere-577522, Cell No.
9880054727, E-mail: leelavathikanur@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Marketing is perhaps the most complex and challenging function performed by every business firm. Marketing is the process of exchange involving two distinct aspects namely, 'Mental' and 'Physical'. Cosmetics have become an integral product of our day to day life. It is difficult to imagine given a single day without the use of cosmetics. Each and every member of the society irrespective of age, sex, status, income etc uses this product called 'cosmetics' it has become more of a 'necessity' than a 'comfort' or 'luxury'. Cosmetics are mainly used by the female section in the society. The main purpose of using cosmetics is to enhance the beauty. Its other purpose is also to maintain good texture of the skin. With growing environmental pollution it is very necessary to look after health specially the skin which is most exposed and the best method is the use of cosmetics. Cosmetics have the solution for each and every problem right from pimples and blackheads to wrinkles. Not only the consumers are benefited but also the wholesalers, retailers and dealers earn the profit margin in high sales of cosmetics. The study of Lakme cosmetic products has a wide scope in the market of cosmetics. The scope of marketing of these products involves high efficiency and high quality products. The price of these products also matters in this case. Cosmetics have a great feature in the field of marketing, because cosmetics has become part of human being. With the increase in literacy, the impact of western culture, the television and the emergence of discriminating youth have increased. Whether cosmetics results in permanent or temporary looks, every one prefer cosmetics to feel fairer, beautiful etc. hence the firms in the industry also have a great feature if managed properly. The study will analyze the market potential includes these market share, selling and purchasing of the share, analysis of the brand awareness, consumer preference their satisfaction level and the present status at the cosmetics company in Challakere.

Keywords: Marketing strategies, Consumer Satisfaction and Lakme Cosmetics Products.

PAPER 56

FIN TECH AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION TOWARDS INCLUSIVE GROWTH

Dr.B.Nagarjuna¹, Dr.k.Rajendra Prasad²

¹Associate Professor, Sree Vidyanikethan Institute of Management, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh.

²Associate Professor, Sanskriti School of Business, Puttaparthi, Andhra Pradesh

ABSTRACT

Inclusive growth in Banking and Financial Services is the result of Fin Tech and Financial Inclusion, the buzzwords in Digital India. In the light of the recent governments focus on relying more on technology and electronic modes of rendering govt services to public, Fintech and Financial Inclusion are beyond doubt, the key enablers. Financial Institutions, Information Technology and telecommunication developments are in the forefront in contributing to the sustainable development of the country by providing fair, transparent, affordable financial services to the largest unreached rural population. FinTech is the conglomeration of Information Technology with Banking & Financial Services that enables the improvements in efficiency, cost reduction and customer satisfaction. Financial Inclusion, promoted as a National objective by the Govt of India and Reserve Bank of India to attain the inclusive growth is a process of ensuring availability, access and usage of formal financial system and financial services by all members of the economy. The prominent drivers of the growth in India which is one of the fastest growing economies in the world include telecommunications, infrastructure, literacy & financial services. Digitalization in Financial Inclusion & Paradigm shifts in FinTech industry opened new avenues of expansion for existing financial service providers and also allowed new players to enter into financial services sector, yet the results towards inclusive growth of Indian Economy are dissatisfactory. This paper attempts to focus on the evolution & growth of the concepts of Fin Tech & Financial Inclusion and also examines the impact, challenges and future perspectives towards inclusive growth of Indian Economy.

Keywords: Fin Tech, Financial Inclusion, Digitalization, Inclusive growth.

PAPER 57

GREEN BANKING AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM INDIAN BANKING INDUSTRY

Vanessa Monteiro¹, Akanksha Shenoy²

First Year B.Com, St Aloysius College (Autonomous), Mangaluru-575003

ABSTRACT

Banks are the financing agents for the economic development of any nation. Sustainable development is taking care of the need of present generation without compromising the needs of future generation. The concept of sustainable development has given rise to green consciousness in business management. Today sustainable development is possible through the adoption of green initiatives. The biggest challenge faced by the Indian industry is controlling the environmental impact of the business. The development process equally creates side effects to enormous loss of biodiversity, climate change and environmental damage. As the Society is becoming more and more concerned about the natural environment, banks have to modify their operations in an attempt to increase greenery to the maximum possible. Green banking refers to promoting environmental friendly practices through combining operational improvements, technology and changing client habits in banking transactions. Using online banking instead of branch banking; or paying bills online instead of mailing them are the examples of green banking. Green banking gives more weight to environmental factors with an aim to provide good environmental and social business. Green banking is different from conventional banking which is solely based on the principal of security and profitability. Green banking is a new concept that considers environmental and socially responsible investing. Green banking is a banking that benefits the environment. Banks following green initiatives check all the factors for environment friendly operations of a business before lending a loan. Green banking benefits the environment by reducing the carbon footprint of consumers or banks. The present paper emphasizes the scope of green banking in India so as to make the banking business environment friendly for sustainable development. The study is based on the secondary data. The paper provides empirical evidence of the developments made by sample Indian banks in adopting green banking.

Key words: Banking, Sustainable development, Green Banking, Indian Banking, Socially responsible environment

PAPER 58

GREEN GOLD ANIMATIONS - A CASE STUDY ON LEADING INDIAN ANIMATION PRODUCTIONS

Jeetha¹, Krishna Prasad K², Srinivasa Pejathaya³

^{1 & 2} College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575001, Karnataka, India

³Department of PG studies in Journalism & Mass Communication, Alvas College, Moodubidire– 574227, Karnataka, India

E-mail: jeethasaakshi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Green Gold Animation could be a pioneer in making original Indian animation content and has been amusive towards the young generation for over a decade. The shows made by Green Gold Animations are massively well-liked across all leading children TV channel slike Cartoon Network, Pogo, Discovery Kids, Hungama & Disney, drawing an active viewership of over 60 million kids. Green gold animations are currently being telecast in 12 countries including the Middle East, Southeast Asia and North America. Green Gold Animation was incorporated in 2001. Green Gold Animation Private Limited is an Indian based private company. The company provides licensing & merchandising, movie production & distribution, digital business, retail stores and events. The Production house has two directors, Rajiv Chilaka and Samir Jain. The company registered office is at Office Hyderabad, Telangana and with offices set up in Mumbai and Kolkata. They have their offices set at Singapore, Philippines and USA too. Company's authorized capital stands at Rs 500.0 lakhs and has 84.0% paid-up capital which is Rs 420.0 lakhs. The last Annual General Meeting of the company was held on 29 September, 2018. As a company, it focuses on content- creating new animation shows to help expand the animation industry. Secondly it concentrates on developing the licensing of brands with all the licensors to make the industry powerful and strengthen its dynamics. Green Gold Animation is the solely Indian company to diversify itself in to multiple domains and it's a pioneer in exploring new revenue streams with the exception of ancient sources like L&M activity, Branded Stores and Digital Media. what is more, it's the primary Indian company reaching bent on international audience with original Indian animated content. The company aims at releasing more feature films and enter new markets through content across the globe; create exciting products and merchandise; plan more exciting events and activations. This paper concentrates on how green gold animations has been a leading player in Licensing & Merchandising, Movie Production & Distribution, Digital Business, Retail Stores and Events.

Keywords: Green Gold, Animation, Production, Chhota Bheem, Rajiv Chilaka.

PAPER 59

HEALTH INSURANCE – AN OVERVIEW WITH RESPECT TO INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

Madhusudan H N

Assistant Professor, Department Of Commerce, Government First Grade College, Udayapura
,Channarayapatna Taluk, Hassan District- 573225 , Mobile: 7019916330

E-Mail: Madhuhngowda@Gmail.Com

ABSTRACT

For every individual in india, health insurance has become a necessity. It provides risk coverage against expenditure which is caused by unforeseen medical emergencies. Today, when the medical inflation rates are so high, failing to hold an adequate health cover can prove costly financially. However, the awareness about health insurance is on the rise in urban india. A study jointly conducted by max bupa and nielsen in 2014-15 which covered 1500 consumers revealed that 70% of the respondents felt that health insurance was more important than life insurance. 60% of the consumers were aware that health cover provided by the employer may prove to be inadequate. Health insurance in india is a growing segment of india's economy. The Indian health system is one of the largest in the world, with the number of people it concerns: nearly 1.3 billion potential beneficiaries. The health industry in India has rapidly become one of the most important sectors in the country. India's health sector faces immense challenges. It continues to be characterized by high out-of-pocket expenditure, low financial protection, low health insurance coverage amongst both rural and urban population. It is a matter of grave concern that we incur a high out-of-pocket expenditure on account of health and medical costs. 62.58% of our population has to pay for their own health and hospitalization expenses and are not covered through any form of health protection. Besides using their income and savings, people borrow money or sell their assets to meet their healthcare needs, thereby pushing 4.6% of the population below the poverty line. The Government of India is committed to ensuring that its population

Keywords: Max Bupa, Health Insurance, Urban India, health sector

PAPER 60

HUMAN RESOURCE CONCERN FOR UPCOMING WORKFORCE - MODERN AGE SOFT SKILL GAP IN UPCOMING WORKFORCE

Babli Kalita, Harshini.S, Soundaryaa.C

M.com-International Business(Post Graduate Students)

Fatima Block, 58, Palace Rd, Abshot Layout, Vasanth Nagar, Bengaluru, 560052

Email: bablikalita67@gmail.com, harshinimay1997@gmail.com,

soundaryaachandrasekar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Surviving in a corporate world is a difficult. Many people are quitting their heavily paid jobs every day. Meanwhile, some are failing to get hired and others are getting laid off before even before completing a stable amount of time in the company. Top business companies are waiting to hire new age employees, but are unable to do so because of the lack of soft skills in them. It is a problem that is global in nature and the gap is wide and increasing unemployment. There are many reasons for the increasing skill gap but education plays a major reason as it has been constant since many years. Most individuals are highly qualified with prestigious degrees but are lacking in soft-skills that are needed to do the job well. Hence, it's important to bridge the soft-skill gap among the upcoming employees (students). To provide soft-skill training among the students the education system has many methods but the student's perspective differ from each individual about the methods opted to enhance the soft-skills. soundaryaachandrasekar@gmail.com is another aspect as employees tend to lose interest in what they do and therefore they blunt out their skills. To resolve this gap, the employer needs to understand what they want from the employees and what they can offer. Training is an effective way to keep the organisation's man power updated with their skills and keep the task going. Many companies invest a lump sum on the training of their new age employees who are fresher's in the industry. One permanent solution to this problem is to communicate the challenges of both the parties: employers and employees. New age workers are passionate about their creative contributions in a work space and senior management should encourage uniqueness. Imposing work pressure on fresh minds restricts them to develop interest in the job, thereby fixating their soft skills with no room for improvement. Knowledge beyond Classroom College can equip the new work force group to cope up with the culture. Internship is an important part of today's curriculum as it gives the students the taste of the corporate world and what is it like to work in the real-world scenario with different personalities around you.

Keywords: soft skills, job satisfaction, unemployment, soft skills gap

PAPER 61

**IMPACT OF DIGITALIZED EDUCATION ON
STUDENTS – A STUDY IN MANGALORE**

¹Ms Deshel Levines Fernandes, ²Mr. Gavin Abner Pinto

¹Research Scholar Srinivas University, Mangalore, Email: deshel31@gmail.com

¹Lecturer, St.Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangalore, Email: gavinabner0@gmail.com

²Student, St.Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Education plays a prominent role in the present. Over a period of time numerous changes have taken place in all the sectors including the Education sector. Eventhough the evolution of Education primarily had an open space teaching with a relationship of ‘guru-shishya’, technology has changed the Education sector and has given a different shape to this sector in terms of accessibility, convenience and affordability. Conventionally there was only a uniform method of teaching that was chalk and talk but today education is provided through various teaching aids like projector and power point presentations, video learning, online classes, social networks, other online visual platforms, etc. Most of the students have benefited from the digitalization of education, but in reality is this form of education helpful for the better prospects of students? The study relating to impact of digitalized education on students is aimed at analyzing the modern processes of education and its impact on the present day students. Education in its true sense is systematic learning and the application of knowledge and skills. In the process of the evolution of education there is an observation of a dramatic shift in the conceptualization of interpreting the true sense of education where the principle of learn and retain has turned into read and forget. Also the experience of learning through the conventional methods resulted in involving the use of digitized technology which in fact has integrated well in the education sector but still suffers from certain drawbacks. While detailed studies have been done abroad there are no prominent studies at the grassroot levels in India. This paper thus, seeks to bridge the deficiencies of lack of information with regard to this topic and also provide updated information with regard to the recent developments in the impact and integration of digital platforms among the students in Mangalore.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Education, Integration, Learning

IMPACT OF INDIAN GENERAL ELECTION RESULTS ON STOCK MARKET

Dr. Kushalappa. S¹, Vijendra Shenoy H²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Govt. First Grade College, Belthangady

Email: kushalkayarthadka@gmail.com, Mob: 9686324188

²Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Govt. First Grade College, Hebri
Email: vijendrashenoyh@gmail.com, Mob: 9663093700

ABSTRACT

The 2019 Indian general election has held in seven phases from 11th April to 19th May 2019 to constitute the 17th Lok Sabha. The counting of votes was conducted on 23rd May, and on the same day the results were declared. Various organizations had conducted opinion polls and majority of such opinion polls were in favour of NDA Government. Interestingly, majority of the opinion polls have become true and NDA alliance have obtained 350 seats and Prime Minister Narendra Modi elected back with a bigger majority than before. In the present paper, the researchers have made an attempt to study the impact of Lok Sabha election results on the price behavior of Indian stock market. The sample size is *NIFTY* stocks. CNX NIFTY, is the benchmark index of the National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India. *Nifty* comprises 30 of the largest and most actively-traded stocks on the NSE, providing an accurate gauge of India's economy. It is an event study and the event window is 61 days. 23rd May is the date of election results and hence considered as the event date. The estimation window consists of 250 working days prior to the event window.

Key Words: Abnormal returns, expected returns, sensx, stock.

PAPER 63

IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIAL MEDIA ON BEHAVIOURAL PATTERN- A STUDY ON GENERATION Z

Harinakshi¹, Madhushree L. M¹, Pradeep M. D²

¹Faculty, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – India. E-mail: madhushreemraju@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Advancement of information technology made the whole world a global village. Present 21st Century is regarded as an era of technology which made the whole world at the fingertips of everyone. Technology plays a very important role in each and everyone's life. Use of technology gained so much importance that it takes away the role of the human being. All individuals are dependent on technology to perform all the activities from learning to entertainment. As technology becomes increasingly democratized and accessible. Generation Z is those who born in the middle of 1990s till 2000s as many of these generations grow up with technology. Generation Z is even more accustomed to the digital world hence they are called 'I Generation'. This generation grew up during the most accelerated and game-changing periods of technological advancements in human history thereby spend a lot of time using technology, especially on social media. The accessibility to the internet through smartphones made everyone's life easier, in turn, it affected their thinking skills and social behavior. Spending too much time on the internet is bound to create a few issues dominating an individual's lifestyle. While technology makes life easier for people and in the meantime, it also creates problems by declining public behavior in society. There are increasing concerns in the speed at which modern technology is spreading with its uses and drawbacks. Thus, this study is undertaken to identify the positive and negative impact of technology on Z Generation's behavioral pattern and thereby contribute to raising awareness among people towards the appropriate ways of using modern tech.

Keywords: Information Technology, Z Generation, modern era, Social Media, and Behavioural Pattern.

PAPER 64

**IMPACT OF JOB SATISFACTION & JOB
COMMITMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL
PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO
PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR
ORGANIZATIONS-A PROFOUND STUDY**

Dr.B.Swathi,

Professor & Principal, Global Education Centre[MBA],Moinabad.
mail:baisswathi4576@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Employees are the most valuable resources for the successful running of any organization. In the present scenario, Job Satisfaction & Job Commitment is the most essential aspect of organizational strategy. Keeping in view the criticality of the situation, the research paper focuses on the various human resource strategies and its direct influence on performance index. Six (6) organizations were selected three (3) public sector and three (3) private sector organizations. A total of 120 respondents were chosen. Primary data collection was done through Questionnaires and face-to-face interview. SPSS was used to analyze the data. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the analysis. The study proved organizational performance is highly influenced by the Job Satisfaction & Job Commitment. It is therefore recommended that employee retention strategies should be allowed to function properly in an organization which persuaded workers to stay in an organization and render their valuable and enriched services to bring success .

Keywords: Job Satisfaction & Job Commitment, Employees' Retention, Workers Performance, Management, organizational strategy.

PAPER 65

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND VIDEO GAMES – A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

Meghashree¹ & Pradeep M.D²

¹Lecturer, School of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India
Email: meghashreekulal@gmail.com

² Assistant Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India
Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the information era all the people without any differentiation of rich and poor, educated and uneducated, kids and adults are addicted to the electronic gadgets such as mobile phones, tab or laptop. Especially our youths are more attracted towards social media and video gaming rather than concentrating on their education. The youths are spending more time in Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube and ruining their life in playing video games. The social media is having both positive and negative impact but playing video games have negative impact rather than positive impact. The games like blue whale, Halo 3, Fire Fairy and many more video games considered as suicide games because it has taken lives of many youths. Social media helps in creating network all around the globe but it is killing the creativity of people by providing all the things readymade. In higher education due to social media students are losing their individual capacity and innovative thoughts. The reason behind their addiction to social media and video games is it by friends or other. This papers highlights both the positive and negative impact of social media and video games on youth, impact on their education and also suggest measures to control excessive dependency of video games by the youths.

Keywords: social media, Video Games, Higher Education, Youths

IMPLEMENTING PRODUCT DIVERSIFICATION STRATEGIES FOR THE SUSTAINABILITY OF A TECHNOLOGY COMPANY - A CASE STUDY OF MICROSOFT CORP

Vinayachandra¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India¹ e-mail : veeciashu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Started in the year 1975, with a BASIC interpreter, Microsoft Inc. today develop, manufacture, license, support and sells computer software, consumer electronics, personal computer, and related services in the global market. The Company is world-famous today because of its best software products Windows operating systems, Office suits, Internet Explorer and Edge Web browsers. Its major hardware produces are Xbox Video game consoles and Microsoft Surface line-up touch screen personal computers. The company is listed as the Top 1 software company by Forbes Global. From its inception to till date, the company is maintaining top ranking technology-wise, product-wise, service-wise, revenue-wise, and growth-wise. It is possible for the company to sustain growth because of the implementation of product diversification strategy. In the early 1980s the company dominated personal computer market with its MS-DOS operating system. The company also released the Xbox at the later part of the year, moving towards the video game console market. Through Azure Services Platform, the company entered into cloud computing market. In recent years Microsoft also diversified its interest to the field of IoT and Cyber Security. This paper analyses the challenges faced by the Microsoft time to time and strategies it incorporated in diversifying product and services line-up to sustain growth and maintain market stability. It also analyses relevance and influence of different Microsoft products, its customer base, and software market share and near future strategies. Moreover, a critical comparative study of contemporary products was also made in this paper.

Keywords: Microsoft, Windows, Office, Azure, Cloud Computing, IoT, Cyber Security, WWW, Networking.

PAPER 67

IMPLICATIONS OF COUNSELING AND MENTORING SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION- PEDAGOGY TO COMBAT RISK & ENRICH STUDENT PERFORMANCE

Pradeep M.D.¹

¹Assistant Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India. Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Indian demography comprises 34.33 per cent of youth population by the end of 2020. Youngsters are known for creative ideas, passion, strength, compassion, energy, enthusiasm, curiosity and vibrancy. College students always challenge stereo types with 'Out of the box' approach. Youngsters are haunted by the problems of relationship crisis, love failures, premarital sex, career decision, financial problems, loneliness, anxiety, maladjustment, personality disorders, drug and substance abuse, stress, depression in their life. The psychological problems will hinder the performance of students. Higher educational institutions have started playing key role in mitigating these risks with professional responses. Institutions depend on professional services to detect existing risks and attain unprecedented nourishments of student life. It is eventually essential to control negative social behavior through planned student engagement initiatives. Researchers have proved that youth mind possess immense ability to bring meaningful changes in academics and social behavior. Counseling guides the students to reduce their weaknesses by constructively working on their strength. Mentoring incorporates valuable lessons through sharing experiences by the mentor for nurturing the personality of the students to strive for best performances in their life. Counseling and mentoring services channelizes life of students with moral strength, good character, confidence, enriched abilities and attributes. Higher education Institutions have imbibed Counseling & Mentoring Services as core aspect of higher education delivered through professional experts. The accreditation body NAAC gives due consideration for institutional Counseling and Mentoring Services by allocating marks during accreditation process. This nurturing process will enhance the learning environment to provide empowered and responsible citizens to our Country. This paper analyses on the implications of professional counseling and mentoring services in the light inputs, focus, nature, duration, general profile, family background, institutional support, academic performance, misconduct, personality, feedback and suggestions to combat the problems faced by students.

Keywords: Youth, Mitigating Risk, Building Strength, Counseling, Mentoring, Performance.

PAPER 68

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Veena Santhosh Rai,

Asst Professor, Department of MBA, Srinivas Institute of Technology
Valachil.

[e-mail-veenasanthsohrai@gmail.com](mailto:veenasanthsohrai@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

With increasing knowledge and technological progress of society; our country requires learning skills that could help it keep pace with the development of science and technology. Educational systems in a community and consequently education will not be able to separate from other social institutions, national and international interactions widely known in the global village. Education in the twenty-first century is the center from which all changes and developments arise. Information technology in education needs a culture. This culture needs to be learned along with the use of hardware resources. The system needs to be educated to use information technology; otherwise, purchase and transfer of technology and investment will be nothing but wasting resources. Although these technologies are not impartial in any sense they should be used as means for communicating information, in the existing social structures. However since the process of change and transformation is in the nature of human social institutions, the educational system is also prone to some alterations. But the fundamental problem is that what strategies should be adopted so that education systems in developing countries do not only follow developed countries but grow and progress base on their own needs in the path of progress. In this paper, after explanation about the role of information technology and its place in education in underdeveloped countries and Iran, a discussion is presented on how to enter the field of information society and how to use information technologies.

Keywords: Information Technology, Education, Global village, Hardware Resources, Information Society

PAPER 69

**INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE TEACHING TO
STIMULATE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENTS AT
HIGHER EDUCATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE**

Aditi Jha

Associate Professor, Rachana Sansad College of Applied Art and Craft.

ABSTRACT

College life is not only about academics, games, friends and fun. It is about learning to interact with other people, being aware of the social issues, taking responsibilities and learning to amend the deformities present in our societies. Change is an inevitable law of life. Change should by all means happen for good. Social change refers to any kind of significant alteration over time in behavior patterns and culture values and norms. How do we bring change in the society for betterment of life? The philosopher John Dewey wrote, "Education is not a preparation for life but is life itself". He believed classrooms aren't just places to study social change but a place to spark social change. Teachers as we believe are the key actors and agents of social change. It's a long-drawn debate that whether teachers should be tasked to preparing students to confirm or to actively push for progress and improvement where there is necessary. Youth of today are the torch bearers of tomorrow's society. Socrates himself said, "Education is a kindling of a flame, not a filling of a vessel." It follows, then, that using Socrates' method of discourse as a teaching tool will line up well with Dewey's goals for the classroom. It is therefore a challenge to inculcate awareness, social responsibility, and leadership well in the young minds since the very formative years by sensitizing them about social issues through global learning and critical thinking and channelize their learning processes through innovative techniques. Global learning and its related concepts of global education, global citizenship and education for sustainable development, are all built on the assumption that learning is closely linked to personal and social change. The paper aims to address through case-studies, how students at higher education can participate to bring about inevitable change in society through the understanding and exploration, and provide insight into the student's involvement in social issues through research and survey and finding innovative solutions for them. It will discuss the implication of 'learn, think and act'. Thus, future of our society is the youth, i.e., our students and building an engaged society will ensure that our future progeny will lead our nation into a "Heaven of Freedom" as stated by Rabindranath Tagore.

Key words: social change, global learning, sensitization, innovative teaching, sustainable development.

PAPER 70

INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODOLOGIES IN MODERN ERA FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Movina Kumara N P

Assistant Professor, Department Of Commerce, Government First Grade College, Udayapura
,Channarayapatna Taluk ,Hassan District- 573225
E-Mail: [Movin.Malnad@Gmail.Com](mailto: Movin.Malnad@Gmail.Com)

ABSTRACT

Education is an engine for the growth and progress of any society. It not only imparts knowledge, skills and inculcates values, but is also responsible for building human capital which breeds, drives and sets technological innovation and economic growth. Education is a light that shows the mankind the right direction to surge. The purpose of education is not just making a student literate but adds rationale thinking, knowledgeable and self sufficiency. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower people, strengthen governance and galvanize the effort to achieve the human development goal for the country. This paper aims to give information about importance of education, limitations of traditional teaching methods and innovative teaching methods for modern education system in higher education.

Keywords: Higher education, teaching methodologies, modern education system

PAPER 71

INTELLIGENCE ENHANCEMENT THROUGH I-THREE LEARNING -A CASE STUDY

Gururaj Itagi 1*, Laveena D'Mello 2**

1*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Email: gururajitgi@gmail.com

2**Assistant Professor, Social Work Department, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

All students in the classrooms are unique in terms of mental maturity or learning intelligence and every one of them receives information through sensory pathways from the external world. Assessment of these student's ability in receiving, processing and reacting on the information been taught, they perform even more unique. Learning intelligence is an ability to acquire, process, retain or retrieve information received through teaching approach. This process happens with different learning modalities such as auditory inputs, visual inputs, kinesthetic inputs and tactile inputs. Intelligence enhancement is the most essential part of the teaching and learning process in the classroom which will improve the student's attention in having a better comprehension of knowledge taught in the classroom. But the Indian classrooms having heterogeneity among students population representing different parental background, psycho-social condition, religious and geographical influences lack the teaching strategies in its methodology focussing enhancement of learning intelligence. The results of the case study showed that experiences through I-Three learning in three different modalities such as (1) information inputs, (2) information processing and (3) information output preparing students for exploring self-learning, maximizing comprehension and logical reasoning of knowledge taught in the classroom. The case study is also describing challenges in effective classroom teaching with the needs and benefits of intelligence enhancement through I-three learning.

Keywords: Intelligence, Learning, Learner, Teaching and Education.

IS EDUCATION DISRUPTED BY DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

Ms.Shreeprajna¹ , Akshith Kumar K²

¹Asst Professor ,E-mail: shreeprajna2015@gmail.com, Mobile Number: 8217410366
SDM College of Business Management, Mangaluru

²E- mail:Akshithkumar10@gmail.com Mobile Number: 9611319982

ABSTRACT

What started off as enlightenment under a tree, today means having Cerelac whilst watching cartoons on the I Pad. Over the past couple of decades, the magnitude of changes experienced by us gives a sneak peek into the future disruption that will only accelerate with time. What shape the future of education will take it still not fully clear, but most educators and observers agree that the future learning will be beyond the boundaries of ‘classrooms’ . Modern technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, Virtual Reality and Block chain aren’t just changing the learning spaces for students: instead, they are also shaking up the role of educators and remodelling modern classrooms. In light of the digital revolution, disruption heralds a change that may seem particularly unwelcome to those forced uproot their traditional ways of doing things. But it doesn’t emerge from nowhere. Disruption is driven by a convergence of forces: from the capabilities of new technologies, to the changing demands of customers, or rapidly evolving practices of competitors. Blackboard, chalks, textbooks and ink pens are slowly becoming a thing of a past. It is time to embrace technology where digital facilities coupled with tech-savvy teachers are enriching students’ learning experiences. A little glimpse into the dynamic digital world is indicative of how technology has given a whole new meaning to education. Education with the help of technology has crossed borders and has opened up a world of opportunities for students. From easy sharing of information to collaboration with the help of email and cloud applications to instant access to learning programs anytime, anywhere. Classrooms today don’t resemble the classrooms of our childhood. Gone is the chalkboard as the main communication tool. Now students have technology at their fingertips instead of one or two computers in the back of the classroom. Whole tablets, laptops and the like can certainly benefit and support education; they can also serve as a distraction and deterrent. So how do educators navigate this ever –evolving tech world? From ‘Smart Teachers’ we are now moving to ‘Smart Classrooms’. We firmly believe that the Indian Education system has already been disrupted by the digital revolution and further growth requires capabilities to reach to the remotest location through technology. In this article, a brief perspective has been about the shift in the delivery of education, from face to face mode to virtual space, through the use of digital technology, which provides a better reach in the remotest areas that internet, has reached. The biggest change is that innovative methods of teaching are taking over class rooms, lectures and textbooks.

Keywords: Enlightenment, Digital facilities, Smart Classrooms, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, Virtual Reality, Block chain.

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES TO HANDLE BIG DATA

Panchajanyeswari M Achar

Faculty, College of Information Science and Computer Science
City Campus, Pandeshwar, Srinivas University; Mangalore – 575 001
E-mail: jahnavi.murali2005@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present generation is an era where huge volumes of data is being generated from modern information systems and digital technologies like cloud computing, Internet of Things and social networking. This has resulted in enormous data in the hands of decision makers. Traditional data management technologies have limited capabilities to handle such data. In this information era, the data is a fundamental resource and the main focus is to efficiently manage and utilize big data. The speed at which data is gathered is growing exponentially. Due to the rapid growth and constant change in data, the processing of such data becomes a challenge. Decision makers need to gain value from the data that ranges from daily customer transactions to feeds from social networking sites. There are many challenges in Big data like difficulties in data capture, data storage, data analysis and data visualization. All these challenges require sophisticated tools to handle them. This paper aims at focusing on the issues and challenges associated with big data. This paper highlights the concepts of big data, evolution, applications, big data tools and the new challenges to handle big data are summarized.

Keywords: Big Data, data storage, data visualization, data management

PAPER 74

JOB FAIR – SOCIAL OR COMMERCIAL

Varun Shenoy & P. S. Aithal

¹Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India
E-mail :varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Socially organizing, participation and supporting Job Fairs is a mandatory obligation of all stakeholders involved towards employment generation in the economy. However, Job Fairs are also viewed with commercial intention by stakeholders for benefits or profits. A commercial approach in such a situation over runs the social patriotic agenda of societal development, economy and manpower development of a country. Though CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) mandates organizations to conduct social activities, holding job fairs or atleast freewill participation in such career fairs as a social responsibility has always remained a distance for corporations or employers. Further presence of third-party business-oriented consultants in the market with lobbying tactics has also made government agencies responsible for holding employment fairs centred towards favouritism. Therefore, this research investigates the differences involved in holding a social job fair as compared with a commercial one. The paper also propagates national support towards employment generation by listing out stakeholders' duties in social job fair collaborations and its importance.

Keywords: Job Fair, Social Job Fair, Social Employment Fair, Social Career Fair

PAPER 75

**LEVEL OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS
SERVICE PROVIDED BY SBI: A STUDY OF
DHARWAD CITY**

Bhuvaneshwari R Gojanur

Research Scholar ,PG Department of Studies in Commerce,Karnatak University Dharwad
Email:bhu.brg@gmail.com,Ph:+91-9731676531

ABSTRACT:

E-banking is related to the carrying out bank related business with the help of the computers or tele banking. A considerable growth of E-Banking services has been observed in the last few years. Managing service quality while using internet as distribution channel is a challenge for a service provider. This study aims at evaluating service quality of E-Banking services of SBI in Dharwad city from customer's perspective. Customer satisfaction plays an important role in banking business. Not only is it the leading indicator to measure customer loyalty, identify unhappy customers, reduce churn and increase revenue, it is also a key point of differentiation that helps to attract new customers in competitive banking environment. The main objective of this paper is to study the level of customer satisfaction towards E-banking services of SBI. For this study purposive sampling technique was used. The tool for sample collection was a structured questionnaire comprising open ended and Likerts type of questions. Firstly the Likerts type of questions have five point scale (1 strongly disagree to strongly agree), Secondly it includes primary details and e-banking preferences of customers in Dharwad city. The questionnaire was administered for 100 respondents. The statistical tool used for the study was percentage analysis and chi square test. The research corroborated the conceptual framework stating that if skills can be upgraded, there will be greater will to use online banking by the customers

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, E-Banking services, chi-square analysis

PAPER 76

**LGBTQ (LESBIAN, GAY, BISEXUAL,
TRANSGENDER, QUEER) AWARENESS THROUGH
MUSIC VIDEOS: A CASE STUDY ON TAYLOR
SWIFT'S MUSIC VIDEO 'CALM DOWN**

¹Clifford Chetan Ambler, ²Dr. Shubha. H. S,
³Dr. LaveenaD'Mello,

¹Assistant Professor, Senior Faculty-Film making, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Email: cliffordchetanambler@gmail.com,

²Associate Professor & Head - Dept. of Media Studies, School of Communication, Manipal
Academy of Higher Education Email: shubha.hs@manipal.edu

³Associate Professor & Dean, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas
University, Mangalore
Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ever since the inception of MTV, music videos have been a popular source of entertainment for masses all over the world. For over two decades, Music videos have transitioned from the mode of performance to mode of storytelling. Many artists have been using Music as a form of expression and to bring social change. Several governments have used music videos as aid to support the awareness campaigns of various government related development schemes. Over the years, it has been observed that music videos have been touching upon gender related themes. Various artists like Christina Aguilera, Green Day, Pink Floyd, David Bowie, Lady Gaga have attempted to make music videos on themes addressing gender identity. A wide range of Korean pop musicians have also turned into allies by addressing complex issues of queer and trans persons through their music videos. A new wave of spotlighting gay themed narratives has become a rising trend in the music industry. Narratives of both tragic and happy gay stories in music videos have been challenging societal stereotyping of gender in a big way. Many popular artists have produced ground breaking LGBTQ themed music videos that has raised questions. The current paper looks into one such currently trending music video by Taylor Swift which goes by the name 'Calm Down'. This qualitative study will discuss the lyrics, portrayal of LGBTQ, narrative and the hidden metaphors of visuals in the music video and look at how gender stereotyping has been addressed in this video as a major issue in the society.

Key Words: Music Videos, Gender Stereotyping, LGBTQ, Homophobia.

PAPER 77

MAKE MONEY THROUGH STOCKS WITH THE SUPPORT OF MACD: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY FROM INDIAN STOCK MARKET

Girisha Nayak S¹, Dr. Gaurav Lodha²

3030¹Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Manipal University Jaipur 303007
²Research Supervisor Department of Commerce, Manipal University Jaipur 303007

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the technical analysis of how it plays an essential role in the secondary market, inventory analysis and their usefulness in trade. Technical analysis is the art or science of stock market information, such as price movements, trading volume and the market scenario in the form of charts, to forecast future price trends. It can help investors predict what can happen with prices in the short term, and also help understand the intrinsic value of the stock and know whether the scripts are undervalued or overvalued by analysing the turning points of the market. This research study attempts to apply technical analysis tools & techniques on selective scripts to assist correct investment decision in the Indian equity market. This analytical research based on secondary data collected from the National Stock Exchange website to analyse the Moving Average Convergence Divergence is used to identify technically robust scripts. The makes it easier for investors to determine the current trend and threats related to scripting on a par with the market. This document aims to provide technical analysis of the securities of selected companies and help in making investment decisions on the Indian stock market, and technical analysis presents an impartial solution in the world of bias.

Keywords: Moving Average Convergence Divergence, Indian stock market, Technical analysis.

PAPER 78

MICROFINANCE IN INDIA: CURRENT TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT

Yashodhara. K

Research Scholar , Department of Business Administration, Mangalore University

ABSTRACT

Microfinance is the operation of affording small scale financial assistance to the rural poor, mainly loans and savings and generally other services like money transfer and insurance. Microfinance is a small financial service accessible to the poor instead of large scale commercial and other financial services. Generally, microfinance is defined as the provision of financial and non-financial services from microfinance institutions to low-income households and small business that were excluded by commercial banks. This paper demonstrates that the recent microfinance sector in India needs currently projected long-term financing to entirely address issues such as leading small enterprises, employment generation and alleviating poverty.

Key words: trend, development, assistance, services, enterprises

NETFLIX BIGDATA ANALYTICS-A STUDY ON IMPROVING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

SRIVATSA MADDODI¹, KRISHNA PRASAD. K.²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: srivatsa.maddodi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Netflix is one of the largest online streaming mediaproviders. It began its operations in 1997. Founded by two tech entrepreneur Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph. The Company's head office is in Los Gatos, California. Netflix's Main business is subscription-based online streaming services of TV Shows, Originals, Movies, etc. Being the largest media service provider, it has over 148 Million members operated across 190 countries except for China, Iran, North Korea, Crimea, and Syria. Netflix's initially started selling DVDs or provide them on a rental basis. Over the period with growth of internet users and the decline of DVD sales and rental services, it changed its business model to video on demand. From 2012 onwards, it started producing its original TV-series and movies. The biggest challenge currently faced by Netflix are Maintaining the existing subscribers and increasing the new subscriber count, increase in competition by other streaming providers like Hulu, Disney, Warner Media, Amazon, the rise of the cost to produce the original content. To overcome these challenges Netflix uses Bigdata Analytics. The main job of bigdata analytics is to help the organization to understand its customers better. By using data, provide better service or product to the customer. Netflix has heavily invested in research on bigdata analytics it spends over \$1 billion for it. As of today, they have a separate division called Netflix Research that mainly concentrates on data analytics areas such as customer experience, recommendations, machine learning, etc. Netflix collects huge amounts of data from a vast variety of subscriber base. It collects data such as the location of a user; content watched by the user, user interests, the data searched by the user, and the time at which user watched. Based on these parameters its algorithm gives a personalized recommendation based on the user interest. Netflix has constantly focused on changing business needs they have moved their business model from DVD rental to video on demand and currently producing original shows. In this paper we analyze various business strategies of Netflix, which includes operational, service, technology, Human Resource (HR), financial, marketing, and new product development. This paper analyzes how Netflix with the help of bigdata analytics focused on improving the subscriber's experience and how it helped to be more customer-centric and increased its user base.

Keywords: Netflix, Bigdata, Data analytics, Customer experience, Video on demand, Streaming

PAPER 80

OPINION OF TEENAGERS ON THE IMPACT OF A DIVORCED FAMILY IN MANGALURU

Anuradha Shetty

HOD, Dept of Rural Development, School of Social Work, RoshniNilaya, Mangaluru

ABSTRACT

Marriage is a union between spouses, establishing rights and obligations between them and the resulting biological or adopted children and affinity. The provision of breaking this marriage is called a divorce, which may be due to several personal reasons of the parents but it may affect the children born out of this wedlock in many ways that are physical and psychological in nature. A broken family can negatively affect all domains of the children and teenagers' development. The effects of a broken family on a child or young peoples' development depend on numerous factors, including the age of the child at the time of parents' separation, and on the personality and family relationships. Although infants and young children may experience few negative developmental effects, older children and teenagers may experience some problems in their social, emotional and educational functioning. Although this may not always be true, studies suggest that children from divorced families are more likely to exhibit such behavioral issues than those from non-divorced families. This study aims at learning about the impact that a broken family has on a teenager. It also aims at understanding the level of awareness among teenagers about maintaining a healthy family. This study is descriptive in design. The information has been collected using the questionnaire method.

Keywords: Divorce, Impact, Teenagers, Broken Family, Marriage, Children, Relationships, Mental Health

PAPER 81

**OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF ICCT
UNDERLYING TECHNOLOGIES IN SOLVING
PROBLEMS OF AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY**

Madhushree L. M¹, and P. S. Aithal²

¹Research Scholar, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangalore – India

²College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – India
E-mail: madhushreemraju@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Since the beginning of the 21st century, the world is witnessing a revolution due to accelerated growth in Information Communication and Computing Technology. IT can facilitate admittance to timely and correct information for improved agricultural production. Agriculture is a gigantic sector of the Indian economy as its share to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is almost 17 percent in India. Over 60 percent of the population adopts agriculture as its main occupation. ICCT based initiatives can be taken for the propagation of information, transfer of technology, procurement of inputs and selling of outputs in a way so that farmers can be benefitted. The timely information and practical solutions of the agricultural problems using ICCT help the farmers to adopt good agricultural practices, make better choices of inputs and to plan cultivation properly. ICCT in agriculture is a developing field focusing on the enhancement of Agriculture and Rural Development. It includes applications of innovative ways to use ICCT in the rural domain. The advancement in ICCT can be applied for providing accurate, timely, relevant information and services to the farmers, thereby facilitating an environment with remunerative agriculture. Thus, there is a need to understand as to how far the ICCT initiatives can address the farmers need to develop better solutions for addressing the unmet needs. This paper focuses on how ICCT underlying technologies are useful for innovations in the Agricultural industry and to know the applications of the above-identified technologies in solving agricultural problems with having a suitable methodology.

Keywords: ICCT Applications, Emerging Trends, challenges, and Agricultural industry.

PAPER 82

**OUTSOURCING: RECENT TRENDS IN
MANAGEMENT FOR DEVELOPING INDIA**

Dr. Pradip M. Joshi,

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce and Management, M. J. College, Jalgaon,
Maharashtra, pmj21575@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Entire world is a jointed with each other due to globalization. IT plays a vital role in it. By using IT techniques and new trends in Management, India can be take opportunity to be a developed country. This new trends of management is Outsourcing. Now a day developed countries outsource too many jobs to India. Such benefit should also to be taken by Indian. Indians Entrepreneurs are sharp minded, hard worker, creative, etc., just need to do some financial management, time management and stress management. To manage all these thigs need to accept foreign strategy i.e. Outsourcing. Outsourcing is strategic management model transferring business process to other country. As per a rapid growth of Indian Economy, very soon India will becomea Developed Country. As compare to other developing country, India moves upward in rank. Thus it beneficial as India can outsource their work to other country. And concentrate on main or core functions of the business. It helps to increase productivity, quality of product, reduction in cost, expansion of business, profit making and etc. This research paper discusses and focuses on various criteria of outsourcing which is useful for Entrepreneurs. Paper also evaluates the benefits and the challenges in outsourcing and offshoring.To take the reap of outsourcing, Indian Entrepreneurs must be accepted the outsourcing opportunity. This paper discusses that how Indians Entrepreneurs use this new trends inManagement i.e. outsourcing and become developed country very soon.

Key Words: Outsourcing, Entrepreneurs, Management.

PAPER 83

PANEL DATA IN TOURISM DEMAND

Kadek Jemmy Waciko and Ismail, B

Department of Statistics, Mangalore University, Karnataka, India
Email: kadekjemmywaciko@gmail.com; prof.ismailb@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study has explained the construction of panel data models, compared the estimation performance of Fixed Effects and Random Effects models in application of tourism demand analysis. Our novelty model of panel data focuses on the 10 best travel destinations according to Tripadvisor award 2018 ($i=1,2,\dots,10$). We have considered the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) related to the number of international tourist arrivals in country i (X_1), International tourism receipts for country i (X_2), International tourism expenditures for country i (X_3), Tax revenue in tourism sector for country i (X_4) and Total employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5), for the period 1995 to 2017. After fulfilling all diagnostic tests in panel data and based on the principle of simplicity (Parsimony), we found that the most appropriate model is Fixed Effect model with Individual Effect ($\log Y_{it} = 0.42 \log X_1 + 0.17 \log X_2 + 0.54 \log X_3 - 0.75 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$) where the values of c_i (Unobservable Individual Effects) for each countries such as : Paris (1.776); UK(1.776); Italy(1.839); Indonesia(1.819); Greece(1.736); Spain(1.573); Czech Rep.(1.589); Morocco(1.717); Turkey(1.826) and USA(1.877) respectively. Furthermore, Adj. R-Squared = 0.95054 and F-statistic = 1103.48 (p-value = $2.22e-16 < 0.05$), this implies that the Number of International Tourist Arrivals in country i (X_1), International Tourism Receipts for country i (X_2), International Tourism Expenditures for country i (X_3), and Total Employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5) are adjusted together explain Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) by 95.054% while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model.

Keywords: Fixed Effects Model; Random Effects Model; Unobservable Individual Effects.

PAPER 84

**POST GRADUATE STUDENTS EXPERIENCE IN
MOOC'S SWAYAM – A STUDY WITH REFERENCE
TO BELTHANGADY TALUK**

¹Robin Joseph Sera, ²Silvyn Shalita Lobo,

¹Lecturer Sacred Heart College, Madanthyar. Email: robinsera361@gmail.com

²M. Com Final, Sacred Heart College, Madanthyar.

ABSTRACT

Online learning uses technology for delivering the courses. Education with technology is considered as most promising development in education. With technology globalization, the concept of learning and teaching has undergone a tremendous change. Technological usage in education provides global learning environment, which allows accessing the course material anytime, anywhere, connect other learners, and get access to the content without considering any geographical boundaries. The significant changes in use of the technology in online education has seen emergence of the concept of Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). SWAYAM platform is indigenously developed by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) with the help of Microsoft and would be ultimately capable of hosting 2000 courses and 80000 hours of learning: covering school, under-graduate, post-graduate, engineering, law and other professional courses. University Grants Commission (UGC) has issued Gazette Notification dated 19th July, 2016, notified Regulation, 2016 regarding 'Credit Framework for Online Learning Courses through SWAYAM'. SWAYAM has been developed under a four-quadrant approaches: (1) video lecture, (2) specially prepared reading material that can be downloaded/printed (3) self-assessment tests through tests and quizzes and (4) an online discussion forum for clearing the doubts. SWAYAM is an indigenous (Made in India) IT Platform for hosting the Massive Open Online Courses. The study is conducted among the Post graduate students of Belthangady taluk to know the experience of usage and to know the various challenges faced by the students while accessing the various courses.

KEYWORDS: Mooc's – swayam, Higher education, Digital learning, Technology, Online course

PAPER 85

**PREDICTION OF PLAYING ABILITY IN KABADDI
FROM SELECTED ANTHROPOMETRICAL,
PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG COLLEGE
LEVEL PLAYERS**

Smt. Shilpashree S¹, Dr.HanumanthayyaPujari²

¹Research Scholar, ²Assistant Professor, Department of Studies in Physical Education and Sports Sciences, Akkamahadevi Women's University Vijayapur

The Purpose of the Study was to predict the playing ability in Kabaddi from selected Anthropometrical & Psychological Variables among College level Players, 96 Inter Collegiate Kabaddi Players were randomly selected from various colleges in Karnataka, India and their age ranged between 18 and 28 years. The subjects had past playing experience of at least Five years in Kabaddi and only those who represented their respective college teams were taken as subjects. A series of anthropometrical measurements was carried out on each participant. These included Standing height measured by Stadiometer; Body weight measured weighing machine, Two Length measurements - Arm length, Leg length, measured by Lufkin Anthropometric Tape. The data were collected by following standard testing protocol of International Society for the Advancement of Kinanthropometry. Psychological factors namely somatic anxiety, Cognitive anxiety and self Confidence were assessed by Competitive Sports Anxiety Inventory – II (CSAI - 2) questionnaire developed by Martens, Burton, Vealey, Bump and Smith (1990) and Sports Achievement motivation level was assessed by Kamlesh (1983) SAMT questionnaire. The playing ability which was taken as the performance factor was subjectively assessed by three qualified Kabaddi coaches. All testing was done two day before inter - collegiate competition by using scientifically approved equipment's. Mean and Standard deviations were calculated for each of the selected variables. The inter-relationship among the selected anthropometrical, and psychological variables and Kabaddi playing ability, were computed by using Pearson' product-moment correlation coefficients. All selected anthropometrical, psychological variables that statistically correlated with performance were used to form respective linear predictive models (step-wise argument selection). The results revealed that an Inter-relationship exists significantly between the anthropometrical and psychological variables among male intercollegiate Kabaddi players. The results also revealed that Leg explosive strength, Speed, Self-confidence, Muscular endurance, and Muscular power become the common characteristics which can predict the playing ability in Kabaddi players.

Key words: Prediction, Regression and Kabaddi

PAPER 86

PROBLEMS OF FIELD WORK EDUCATION IN SOCIAL WORK PRACTICUM

**Sushmitha K.Y*,Pushparaj P*,Meghana S*
& Abdul Rasheed K.M****

*1st year MSW,

**Assistant Professor & HOD, Nehru Memorial College Sullia

ABSTRACT

Social work students generally considered field work training as the most important component in their professional education. In social work curriculum, practice and knowledge (theory) are two integral components in the curriculum, and yet they are often regarded as separate and so some extent antithetical (the “theoretical” vs. the “practical”). A unique feature of fieldwork training is that training and practice take place in the same place. Hence, students are not learning “about” a practice as is the case in classroom instruction but learning “in” practice. Field placement is one of the most exciting and exhilarating parts of a formal social work education. It is also one of the most challenging. More than anything else, it requires students to look inside themselves and examine themselves as future social workers. However, most of the time, the students will feel better equipped for their professional career after finishing their practicum. The field work goal is to develop the student’s competence in the practice of social work. Field education is an experiential form of teaching and learning that takes place in a service setting. Field work practices offered the most opportunity to understand the requirements of the people in the background of prevailing cultural traditions and values and thereby, offered opportunities to indigenize practice. It also gave opportunities for innovation. Thus, the present paper highlights and reviews on the challenges and prospects of field work training in Social Work education.

Keywords: Problems, Prospects, Challenges, Field work training, Social work.

PAPER 87

PROMOTION OF E-LEARNING AND ONLINE COURSES: A CASE STUDY ON ‘THE MADRAS SANSKRIT COLLEGE’

K. G. Nandha Kumar

School of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, India

Email: professorsorkn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Madras Sanskrit College is a century-old college and one of the premier institutions for Sanskrit education. It offers from foundation program to doctoral program in various subjects of Sanskrit. It is globally well known for its traditional way of Sanskrit education and research. It has contributed a lot to the field of Sanskrit Literature & Language through the completion of larger research projects and conservation very rare palm-leaf manuscripts. It has produced a great number of scholars as well. Due to some socio-political changes in the state of Tamil Nadu, Sanskrit education was neglected in the last few decades. Opportunity to learn Sanskrit language and to learn other traditional subjects in the Sanskrit medium was not available at this period. Though people were interested to learn Sanskrit it was not accessible. But now, the evolution of the internet has opened the doors for learning Sanskrit through online and social media. The Madras Sanskrit College has recently started its digital campus to conduct basic level courses in Sanskrit and to provide E-Learning materials. It has a Facebook account, YouTube channel and very recently has released a mobile application for learning Spoken Sanskrit. This paper is an outcome of the study done on The Madras Sanskrit College and its digital approaches. It discusses the effective applications of ICT concepts initiated by the Madras Sanskrit College for the promotion of Sanskrit education through its Digital Campus, Electronic Instructional Materials, YouTube Channel, Facebook pages and other modern methods.

Keywords: Online course, Sanskrit, E-Learning, Facebook, YouTube, Mobile Application, Digital campus.

PAPER 88

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN INDIAN BANKING: A BOON OR BANE

***Mr. Jonsil – Ii B.Com Student, **Mrs. Florin Shelomith Soans,**
Department Of Economics, St.Aloysius College (Autonomous), Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Indian banking after nationalization made tremendous changes in developmental process. Banking sector has contributed very much to the gross root development. In recent years because of the changes in policies indicated by the government banking sector certain changes are made. With these backgrounds the main objectives of the paper are To know the recent development in Indian banking sector. To check the challenges in banking sector. To suggest certain measures to improve the loopholes in banking sector. To arrive at the said objectives, both the primary and secondary data considered as a part of primary data questionnaire will be prepared and collected information will be analyzed with the help of theories of banking and development.

Keywords: nationalization, banking, government banking.

PAPER 89

**ROLE OF ACTION RESEARCH IN THE
IMPROVEMENT OF SELF AWARENESS IN
TEACHING AMONG B.ED., TRAINEES.**

Dr.Jagadeesh Basapur,

Assistant professor,K.S. College of education,Ballari, Email jd-jbbsshreyas@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

Teaching and Research are the two faces of the same coin. Teaching is the practical part of the Research. Teaching plays the role of education and Action Research plays the role of the Philosophy. Research in any discipline dives deep into the ocean of knowledge to discover new relations, new theories and better understanding of various phenomenon. Besides the basic role of creating of fund of knowledge, research also acts as an agent of change and improvement. Every teacher becomes a researcher to the extent that he or she perceives the problem, designs an Action Research Project, experiments to test the hypothesis and finally comes out with solution, to improve teaching and there by enhance the learning on the part of learners. As the name suggests, Action Research is the methodology which has the dual aims of action and research. Action- To bring about change in some community or organization or programme. Research:- To increase understanding on the part of the research or the client or both. There are in fact Action Research methods whose main emphasis is an action with Research as a fringe benefit. At the extreme the research may take the form of increased understanding on the part of those most directly involved. For this form of Action Research the ot comes are change and learning for those who take part. In the present 2 year B.Ed., programme on of the areas of training is the school internship. One of the components is the class room based Research Project where the student trainee should undergo Action Research. This programme provides the plat form for the interns to give expression to their learning while planning and reflecting on their own experience.In present paper study on Action Research of the B.Ed., trainees is explained. The tool Self awareness in teaching was used to collect the data. Simple Statistics technique was used to analysis and interpretation of the data. The study revealed that the Action Research improved the self-awareness in teaching among the trainees.

Keywords: Self Awareness, Action Research, B.Ed Trainees

PAPER 90

ROLE OF AGE IN INVESTMENT DECISIONS

Shruti Maheshwari¹, Dr. Manish Mittal², Anurag Maheshwari³

¹Research Scholar, Banasthali Vidhyapith,

²Professor, Acropolis Faculty of Management and Research, Indore

³Trade Sales Manager. , Indusind Bank

ABSTRACT

Individuals project various biases in their investment decisions. It may vary from emotional to cognitive biases. Amongst many demographic factors age is analyzed in the present study. The objective is to observe influence of age on behavioral biases which later will affect investment decision. Investors across various cities of India were selected as sample respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaire. The study applied chi-square and kruskal wallis test to analyze the influence of age on decisions like expected return, portfolio size, investment objective, investment avenues etc. The study concluded that investors across various age groups vary in their investment decisions. Decisions are affected by cognitive ability of an individual and risk tolerance level. Also responsibilities, capital base and income levels vary across various age categories. All these forces play a crucial role in financial decision making.

Keywords: Age, behavioral biase, investment decision, chi square, demographics

PAPER 91

ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

***Malati Shankar Patgar, **Dr. Shridhar Hadimani**

*Research Scholar, Department of Economics, Karnatak University, Dharwad, M: +91 9480465168, Email: m spatgar06@gmail.com

**Teaching Assistant, Rural Development and Panchayat Raj University (KSRDPRU), GADAG. M: +91 9448056077, Email: shridharhadimani2013@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the Roles and solicit contribute to the uninterrupted reflection on the integration of technology into education. Information technologies have affected every aspect of human activity and have a potential role to play in the field of education. The need of technologies in teaching learning process grows stronger and faster. The technological information becomes an era of knowledge providing exchange of information, communication and exploration to strengthen the teaching methods, learning approaches, change in working conditions, handling and exchanging information, scientific research, and in accessing information. Information technologies help in promoting opportunities of knowledge sharing throughout the world. These can help the teachers and students having up-to-date information and knowledge. Accurate and right information is necessary for effective teaching and learning; and information technologies (Haag, 1998; p.10) are “set of tools that can help provide the right people with the right information at the right time.” It helps to Students are independent and they can make best decisions possible about their studies, learning time, place and resources. The objectives of the studies are 1) To study the why Information Technology is important in Education. 2) To understand the meaning of Information Technology and Education. The secondary information is used for the analysis of the study problem. It’s collected from the various sources like Journals, Books, Articles, etc.

Keywords: Information technologies, teaching learning process, knowledge, education.

PAPER 92

ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN BANKING SECTOR

Kavita Mahar

Assistant Professor, Department of B.Com ,Koshys Institute of Management Studies
Bangalore , E-mail- kavitamahar4@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The, purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between new technology implementation in the banking sector and customers. Here i want to give importance on how much customers are aware about the technologies and how much percentage of them are actually using it. Data for this study was collected from the customers of various Banking Sectors under the Reserve Bank of India. A simple percentage with pie chart analysis was done. According to questioners, 60 samples are collected and interpretations are given. Findings suggest that most of the customers of bank using ATM facilities. So, the banks should provide awareness about the E-banking services.

Keyword: banking, ATM, Reserve Bank

PAPER 93

SECURITY ISSUES IN SWITCHED NETWORKS

Subrahmanya Bhat B

College of Computer and Information Sciences,
Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.
Email: itsbhat@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Networks have been designed to achieve communication as well as resource sharing. But while designing such networks, one should see the potential threats on our resources that might arise due to its open internetwork architecture. Various security implementations are required at different levels of a network so as to protect the corporate resources. Implementing such security system over a Switched Network is need of the hour, as they are of Flat Network structure. Security on switched networks can be implemented by defining VLANs and assigning the ports only to specific VLANs. This will avoid packets flooding over additional switch ports and thus improves the network security. Designers can go for Dynamic VLAN association with MAC address value to avoid other devices hooking to any switch ports. In addition, design practices like Trunking the links with appropriate VLAN as well as defining ACLs will improve the security on switched networks. This paper will discuss on these different design practices and the levels of security achieved by them.

Keywords: Switched Network, Flat Network , VLAN, Trunking, MAC , ACL.

PAPER 94

SELECTIVITY AND MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED EQUITY DIVERSIFIED SCHEMES IN INDIA

Akshatha Suvama

Assistant Professor, Govt. First Grade College Haleyangadi

ABSTRACT

The mutual fund industry in India has grown to a remarkable extent in the recent decade, therefore performance evaluation is potentially important. The present paper is an empirical study of investment performance of 52 selected Indian equity diversified mutual fund (growth) schemes for the period from 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2019. The performance is evaluated in terms of rate of return, risk and diversification and stock selectivity skills of fund managers. Measures such as Jensen and Fama is used in the analysis of stock selection skills of fund managers. Results shows that about 63% of the mutual fund schemes were able to beat the benchmark markets. All the schemes under study were relatively exposed to less risk than the market, however with high degree of volatility. A majority of the funds were reasonably diversified. Empirical evidence also suggests that fund managers of some of the sample mutual fund schemes were engaged in micro forecasting (or stock selection) as the alpha values in about 38% of the schemes were found to be positive and statistically significant.

Key words: Return, Risk, Jensen alpha, Fama's measure, Selectivity

PAPER 95

SPORTS ANXIETY AND AGGRESSION AMONG VOLLEYBALL AND BASKETBALL PLAYERS

Kum. Kavita Rathod, Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari

Research Scholar, Research Guide,

DOS in Physical Education and Sports Sciences A W University, Vijayapura

ABSTRACT

This study was to analysis of sports anxiety and aggression among volleyball and basketball players. One hundred players selected randomly for the collection of data. Players were selected from the intercollegiate competitions from Bangalore University. Selected participants were classified into two categories volleyball (n= 50) and basketball (n= 50) players, between the ages of 18 to 23 years. The collected data were analyzed by the statistical treatments "T" test. The result showed that there was a significant difference between Volleyball and Basketball players on sports anxiety and aggression.

Keywords: Sports anxiety and aggression, volleyball and basketball players.

PAPER 96

**STARTUPS IN INDIA – REDEFINING BUSINESS
PARADIGM**

Dr. Vinod. N. Sambrani¹, Naveen Pol²

¹Professor, Kousali Institute of Management Studies, Karnatak University, Dharwad – 580003. Email: vinodsambrani@gmail.com

²Research Scholar, Kousali Institute Of Management Studies, Karnatak University Dharwad – 580003, Email: naveen.pol2007@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Business scenario in the world is taking unprecedented shapes due to the paradigm shift in technology buffeted with change in buying behavior and consumer demands. However India as a nation has raised eye brows through its innovative business practices that are attracting attention of world towards it. The blend of Indian consumers is unique as it has varied buying behavioral practices that are to be addressed in unique dimensions paving challenges to business organizations. The current research makes an attempt in understanding the innovative business practices that are being framed in a peculiar market setup like India. Startups are always treated as best innovative business practices that enables in forecasting the upcoming trends and markets for India. The study will assist in gaining insights towards the upcoming trends for the nation and way ahead for business propositions. The research is conceptual in nature wherein, through in-depth review of literature a frame work of current business scenario will be synchronized with that of upcoming business innovations.

Keywords: Startups, Innovation, Business paradigm.

PAPER 97

STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS CORE BANKING INCONVENIENCE& REMEDIES: A CASE STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO RURAL STUDENTS OF MANGALORE TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA

¹Malathy.K. , ²Dr. Subhashinisrivatsa

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Commerce, G.F.G.C. HALEYANGADI Research Scholar
Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in commerce,
Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Email id: malathyk93@gmail.com Mob. No.
9844041089

² Associate Professor, University College, Hampankatta,
Mangaluru ,Email id: subhashinisrivatsa@gmail.com, Mob. No. 9449333919

ABSTRACT

Technological advancements in the country gave great push to the banking field and brought massive changes in the mode of banking operations. Installation of Core Banking Solutions paved the way for the introduction of various digital initiatives by the bankers, which are highly appreciated by younger generation customers, particularly by students. This paper attempts to highlight the digital inconvenience in rural parts of Managalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, caused due to infrastructure deficit like lack of digital identity, lack of high speed network coverage, safe cyber etc. The study is based upon the opinions given by 100 rural undergraduate students of Managalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, residing in Haleyangadi, Pavanje, Challairu, Thokur and Aikala region. Majority of students, particularly female students are relatively recent entrants to internet based services. The study is carried out by conducting a survey by using a structured questionnaire. Understanding the attitude of students towards digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions, their expectations from digital initiatives, and understanding the digital inconvenience faced by the students are the objectives of study,

Key words: Technology advancements, Core Banking Solutions, Digital initiatives, Digital inconvenience

PAPER 98

STUDY ON EMOTIONAL DEPOSIT FOR HAPPY LIVING AND SOCIAL CHANGE

D'Mello Laveena *, N. Vidya **

*Associate Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

*Assistant Professor, School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: lavynoronha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

An emotional Deposit is the bank account of trust and not the money. These deposits are based on how you feel with the company of another person. Trust, understanding, act of kindness, concern and affection towards others, or getting support from other person may be the father – son/daughter, mother - son/daughter, Parents and children, husband - wife, among Siblings, friends, relatives, neighbors, college's etc, will make persons to deposit in their account. For any situation a person can react differently, either he can turn towards the person or he can turn away from the person. Just like bank account when you turn towards, you will deposit and when you turn away, you will withdraw. The positive and negative reaction and communications will bring drastic change in emotional deposits. Positive interactions will bring small change in the deposits, but negative interactions will bring big withdrawals, which is costly for an individual to keep deposits and balance. By means of understanding the individual's emotions, attending, observing and analyzing the emotions, keeping commitment in the relationship, the responsibility, always having concern for other persons, by clarifying the expectations of the other person, accepting our mistakes and genuineness will help in increasing the emotional deposits. The research paper deals with the concept Emotional Deposits, how to increase the deposits, Tips for increasing emotional deposits and as a result to bring change in the living pattern for highly effective people.

Keywords: Emotions, deposits, happy living, effective people, withdrawals, Bank account and social change.

PAPER 99

STUDY ON HRD CULTURE AND CLIMATE OF CHEMICAL BASED PUBLIC SECTOR ENTERPRISES IN KERALA

Balakrishnan A,

Research Scholar in Management, Srinivas University, Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Globalization dominates the competitive horizon and entails new markets, new products new mindsets ,new competencies and new ways of thinking about business. A major challenge for any organization in this era of international competition and recent economic recession seems to be survival and sustainability amidst cut-throat competition is increasingly argued that the organizations, best able to meet the challenges will be those that can acquire and utilize valuable ,scarce and inimitable resources. Human resources can fall in to this category, particularly, if they are effectively deployed through appropriate human resource practices and management of organizational culture. An organization that has better HRD climate and processes is likely to be more effective than an organization that does not have them. HRD climate can be grouped as General climate ,HRD (OCTAPACE) culture and HRD mechanisms. The study undertaken research study was aimed to analyze the Human Recourse Development culture and climate of chemical based public sector enterprises in Kerala. The population of this research study was the employees of chemical based public sector enterprises in Kerala .ie Kerala Minerals and Metals Ltd,Chavara,Kollam,Travancore Titanium Products Ltd, Trivandrum,and Travancore Cochin Chemicals Ltd, Cochin. An organization success is determined by the skills and motivation of the employees and competent employees are the greatest asset of any organization.HRD tools helps to acquire required competencies for improving work life balance that would enable them to enhance the productivity for better organizational performance. In the context, HRD culture and climate aims at developing the motivation of employees to the extent possible to make them contribute to the organization goals.Data was collected from the employees working at the organization using structured HRD climate questionnaire . The data was analyzed using several statistical tools such as sample percentage, mean value source etc. The result indicated that the HRD climate is an organization is average and the perception of employees regarding HRD culture and climate does not differs significantly on the basis of age ,job approval status and qualification. but it differs significantly on the basis of gender and experiences.

Keywords: HRD Climate, Octapace, Organizational performance, public sector employees

PAPER 100

STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF THE SUSTAINABLE INVESTMENTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY OF INDIA

Priyanka Nayak¹&Shilpa K.²

¹Research Scholar, School Of Management And Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore -575001

²Faculty, School Of Management And Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore -575001
Email- pinkian04@gmail.com, shilpakudroli@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Construction industry of India consists of real estate sector and public infrastructure development. Construction industry in India is the second largest employment contributor. Indian construction industry is expected to see a robust growth in another 10 years. By 2025, Indian construction industry is expected to rank third globally. We are in the era where 'live and let the future live' is the sole motto. Sustainable investment is about responsibility and potential the construction industry holds to reach the social and environmental sustainability targets. India has been at the forefront of the Sustainable Investment Movement. We have brilliant entrepreneurs coming up with innovative ideas to solve complex social problems faced by farmers, labourers, migrants and the environment. This is important to the construction industry because regulations and legal provisions require to minimise and mitigate their ecosystem impact and to compensate for the damage caused. This study through the vast literature review of journal publications, news articles and global summit reviews analyses how the Indian construction industry is marching towards sustainability and also finds scope for sustainable investments in Indian construction industry.

Key words: sustainable investment, real estate, green building, renewable power plants, GOI initiatives.

TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE: CAN EDUCATION BRING A SOCIAL CHANGE IN A SOCIETY?

Prof. Ketan V. Sutaria¹, Jay V, Gala²,

¹Lecturer, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce,

²Student, Bal-Bharati's MJP College of Commerce

ABSTRACT

For shaping the character of an individual education plays a very important element in life and to bring social order in the society there should be a social change. Therefore Education and Social Change goes Hand in Hand. Education preserves the values, morals and beliefs and keep factual data record which will act great utility for the future generations. It gives learner an ability to think, take rightful decisions and to innovate. It eliminates the lack of knowledge which is main stimulus for human stagnation. Learning can initiate a social change in to order o change the viewpoint and mind-set of an individual person. Slowly there is an increase in automation in education system. This results in absorbing large volume of informational material in short time but it reduces the judgment ability of the learner because of dependability of learners on classes rather than self-learning. It distracts the liberal thinking of learners. Society will change socially and culturally only because of education. Education act as a link for learners between socialization and expectations of society. Education is the essential technique of social progress and reform. It leads the learner towards new principles, ethics, standards, morals, ideals and help in growth of intelligence and improves the society potential for a good change. The present paper focuses on the role of edification and technology as a mechanism of social change and growth with introduction of technology for the development of teaching-learning process. It also focuses on obligatory professional knowledge and channels the educators to develop the teaching skills so that it can be more effective. The most influential and valuable instrument of social change and social growth in current time is the education. It emphasize that education has major impact in society, but that it is allocated a conventional role because its main utility is in the socialization of the leaner and the preservation of the social order. Economically when things are going good, more support is given on education experimentation and more optimistic objectives are achieved, such as equity of educational opportunity.

Keywords: social change, teaching, channels, teaching - learning process

TEACHING FOR SOCIAL CHANGE

Shivaprakash K M

Assistant Professor, T M A E Society's College Of Education, Gamgavathi-583227,

Email: Spkalmat@Gmail.Com

ABSTRACT

“Education is not a preparation for life but is life itself.” Dewey reflected extensively on the page about the role of education in a healthy, ever-evolving democratic society, and he believed classrooms aren't just a place to study social change, but a place to spark social change. Dewey wrote about these topics in the early twentieth century, at a time when debates raged about whether teachers should be tasked with preparing students to conform or to actively push for progress and improvement where they are necessary. These same debates continue today with real implications for education policy. Dewey remains one of our clearest voices on the argument that the classroom ought to be seen as an important locus of social change. For present and future teachers, it's one thing to appreciate Dewey's views on education and social change and quite another to create a classroom environment that embodies them. So, how can teachers build real classrooms that exemplify Dewey's ideals for education in society? Teachers are seen as key actors of change within programmes and projects on global learning. But all too often they are regarded in an instrumental way or as promoters of some form of ideal global teacher. Evidence from the UK and elsewhere suggests that if a pedagogical approach is taken to the role of teachers within the process of learning, then three distinct locations of teachers as change agents can be identified. These are as change agents within the classroom, within the wider school, and within society as a whole. When we speak to teachers, they often express the need to understand the modalities of teaching subjects better. They also want help in completing the syllabus for the year on time and for ensuring that most students pass the examinations with flying colours. The reputation of the school, and teachers, depends on how the students score in examinations. On the other hand, when you speak with some of the best educationists, they wonder about the relevance of subjects in overall education, given the essence, role and purpose of education described in the national policy documents. They also say that the real purpose of education is to help students realise their inner potential. While describing the role of education in India, the policy explains that “education is fundamental to our all-round development — both material and spiritual. Education refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national cohesion, builds scientific temper (ability to think rationally and draw conclusions based on evidence and data) and independence of mind and spirit — thus furthering the goals of socialism, secularism and democracy enshrined in our Constitution. Education also develops person power for different levels of economy contributing to the country's self-reliance.”

Keywords: Global learning, critical thinking, transformative learning, social justice

TECHNOLOGY AS AN INSTRUMENT OF BRINGING A SOCIAL CHANGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A STUDY OF MANGALORE CITY

Vyshnavi Bhat M, Melita Fernandes,

1st year M.Com, St. Agnes Centre for Post Graduate Studies and Research, Mangalore.

E-Mail: vyshnavibhat4@gmail.com, fernandesmelita918@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The dynamic progress in technology in the past 30 years is very vibrant especially in the field of higher education. Technology has not only contributed towards education but also to a wide areas in the society. While considering education, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has made a major impact towards bringing a social change. E-learning and Smart Classroom Teaching when compared to traditional method of teaching in higher education are leading to individual transformations. This individual transformation is playing a vital role in bringing about a social change which is tangible. Mangalore being one of the education hubs in Dakshina Kannada has also implemented these technologies in imparting education. To what extent Smart Classroom Teaching, ICTs, E-learning is being implemented in higher education and on the other hand how is a student being the beneficiary of it is being studied in this research article. In this context the 'Social Learning Theory' proposed by Albert Bandura in 1976, is also put to re-search so as to know its existence and reliability in this fast progressing digital world of higher education system. A study regarding the implementation of E-learning, Information and Communication Technology, Smart Classroom Teaching in Government as well as Private Colleges in Mangalore and the extent to which the students have been benefited from such implementation is widely being studied in this research.

Keywords: Smart Classroom, higher education, technology

THE COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CSR ACTIVITIES IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR BANK'S

Archana, Deeksh

1st year, MCOM, St Agnes College (autonomous) ,Mangalore 575002,.
archanamary41@gmail.com , deekshdeeche52@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A bank should have in its DNA. A sense to work for the welfare of the community. CSR is an extension of individual sense of social responsibility. Active participation in CSR projects is important for a bank's. Social responsibility becomes an integral part of the wealth creation process, which managed properly should enhance the competitiveness of bank and maximize the value of wealth creation to society. To increase the brand awareness and employees satisfaction. CSR is used as a tool. Banking sector is not an exception to do it. Most of the bank's are going for CSR activities because to spread over the world and to get good images in the Society, to grow continuously in competitive world. Good reputation or good will have an a positive vibes for all the banks in attracting customers. In order to prove it bank's undertake certain CSR activities such as EDUCATION, HEALTH CARE, SKILL DEVELOPMENT and LIVELIHOOD, CREATION AND ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION. But every banks not undertake the CSR activities only few banks are going with the CSR activity. The objective of this study is to analyze and compare the CSR activities under taken by public and private sector bank's. The study is based on secondary data that has been collected from annual reports of SBI and HDFC bank 3 years from 2016-2019.

Keywords :cooperate social responsibility (CSR). State Bank of India (SBI). Housing development finance corporation(HDFC).

PAPER 105

THE EFFECT OF JUMP ROPE EXESICES ON THE BODY MASS INDEX OF 12 TO 16 YEARS SCHOOL CHILDREN

Kumari Vidya Manohar¹, Dr.D.M.Jyoti²

^{1&2}Research Scholar, Research Guide, DOS in Physical Education Sports and Sciences, A.W. University, Vijayapur. Karnataka, Email: preeti.mped@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The main aim of this study is to find the effect of jump-rope exercises on the Body mass Index of 15 years school children. Considering the mentioned objective, 40 students of B.I.P. School Bagalkot, Karnataka State are selected as cases for this study and they are randomly divided into training group and controlling group. The first group, participated in Jump Rope Exercise training process continued 8 weeks, while; the latter group did not participate in any exercise programs and continued with their daily activities.

Key words: Jump Rope Exercise, Body Mass Index

PAPER 106

**THE EFFECTS OF STAD ON STUDENT'S
MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT**

Dr. G. P. Bahubali

Asst. Professor. University College of Education,
Bengaluru North University, Chickballapur - 562 101,
Email: bahu.gp62@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) is a cooperative learning technique in classroom teaching. Students are divided into four-member learning teams. The teacher presents a concept, and then students work within their teams to make sure that all team members have mastered the concept. Finally, all students take individual problem based on the material given and solve individually. This study explores the effects of STAD on student's Mathematics achievement. Quasi-experimental research and pre-test post-test design was constructed for the purpose of this research. Results revealed that, there is a significant difference between experimental group and control group in their mathematics achievement.

Key Words: Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD), Cooperative learning, Mathematics achievement.

PAPER 107

THE GROWTH OF A SERVICE ORIENTED IT COMPANY THROUGH OUTSOURCING –A CASE STUDY OF INFOSYS LTD.

M. Rajeshwari¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹ Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

² College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India, Email: rajimuraleedhar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Infosys Limited is an Indian multinational company that provides information technology, business consulting and outsourcing services. Its headquarters is located in Bengaluru, Karnataka. It was founded in the year 1981 by seven engineers in India with an initial investment of \$250. Infosys has been ranked fifth most -valued IT services brand globally in 2018-19 (brand value up 8 percent to \$6.5 billion). Since its establishment till 2014, N. R. Narayanmurthy(CEO), leading the company in its initial 21 years. On March 29, 2019, its market capitalisation was \$46.52 billion. In 2019, it has 228,123 employees working at different roles and campus, around the world. Infosys provides software development, maintenance, and independent validation services to companies in finance, insurance, manufacturing, and other domains. Infosys planned to reduce the amount of work performed onsite by their staff travelling visas in US, by shipping more work offshore. By this way, Infosys aim to protect and improve margin benefits. Onsite projects are billed 3-4 times higher than projects delivered out of India. Infosys has nearly 25% work performed onsite and remaining from India. Infosys provides Insurance Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services for the customers. Infosys ranked No.1 in offshore service providers in securities processing BPO. Infosys Business Process Management (BPM) was set up in April 2002. It employed 34,366 people, from 80 nationalities, operating across 32 global locations. The Infosys BPM customer service practice understands the client's specific expectations and addresses them in a sustainable and comprehensive manner. Forrester research has rated Infosys as a leader for simple offshore capabilities using Forrester wave methodology. The report also reviewed that Infosys to be the largest of the six in terms of revenue for application-related services using a low-cost GDM or offshore-delivery model. This case study focuses on different objectives- business vs. operational metrics, profit vs. cost savings, and reduced need for service vs. better service. Also, case study helps to explore the benefits of outsourcing (onshore and offshore) regarding financial growth and the demand of the customer.

Keywords: Infosys Limited, Offshore project, BPO, Forrester Wave Methodology, Application-related services.

PAPER 108

THE STUDY OF PHYSICAL FITNESS PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS.

Ashwini Venkanagouda Patil^{1*} and Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari²

¹Research Scholar, Department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India-586108.

^{1*}corresponding author, e-mail address: ashwiniv.patil90@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of physical education, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Bellary- 583105.

Contact number: +91-9740108853.

ABSTRACT

The intention of this study is to reveal the effect of physical fitness parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this study, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and physical fitness measurements were recorded and analyzed. To be specific, age, height and weight were taken for anthropometric profile and for physical fitness profile, explosive strength measurements were taken. In addition to that, endurance and agility tests were also documented. A 12 minute endurance run and 4x10 m shuttle run test for both endurance and agility tests were conducted respectively. The recorded data was interpreted to determine the physical fitness of the players.

Keywords: Physical fitness, volleyball.

THE STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS.

Ashwini Venkanagouda Patil^{1*} and Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari²

¹Research Scholar, Department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India-586108.

^{1*} *corresponding author, e-mail address: ashwiniv.patil90@gmail.com*

²Associate Professor, Department of physical education, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Bellary, Karnataka, India- 583105.

Contact number: +91-9740108853.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of psychological parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this investigation, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and psychological measurements were recorded and analyzed. Basic anthropometric parameters like age, height and weight were recorded. Players responses to 27 questionnaires were documented. For psychological study, anxiety and self-confidence measurements were taken. Anxieties like cognitive anxiety and somatic anxiety were analyzed. The recorded data has been interpreted to determine the psychological status of the players.

Keywords: Psychological parameters, volleyball.

TRENDS IN GROWTH OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA: EMERGING CHALLENGES IN ACCESS AND EQUITY

Dr. V. Ramakrishnappa, Jagadisha, T

Associate Professor, Centre for study of Social Exclusion and Inclusive Policy (CSSEIP),

Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199. Karnataka, **Email:** ramakrishna_vin@rediffmail.com

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri - 574 199. Karnataka, **Email:** str.jagadish@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Indian higher education is the third largest in the World in terms of students' enrolment. Higher education sector in India has witnessed a tremendous increase in the number of Universities, University level Institutions, colleges and enrolments since independence. As per All India Survey of Higher Education AISHE (2017-18) statistics, 36.6 million of students have been enrolled in higher educational institutions with 19.2 million boys and 17.4 million girls. Further, Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education in India for age group of 18-23 years age group has increased from 21 per cent in 2011-12 to 26 per cent in 2017-18. Currently, there are 903 universities, 39,050 colleges and 10,011 stand-alone institutions in the country. Over the last 70 years, higher education in India has grown remarkably with an increase of student enrolment ratio by 34 times in universities and 74 times in colleges. However, the major challenge that confronts is in the disparities in access to higher education, low enrolment ratio, lack of quality education etc. In this background, the present paper is an attempt to analyse the growth & trends in the higher education sector and discusses the various issues related to access, equity and problems of higher education. The paper is based on the secondary sources of data and information, which have been collected from MHRD, NSSO, News Papers etc.,. The higher education has grown rapidly in India. The growth of universities has increased from 723 in 2013-14 to 903 in 2017-18 by almost 25 per cent. Whereas the number of colleges has also increased from 36,634 in 2013-14 to 39,050 in 2017-18 for same corresponding period. The secondary analysis shows that the total estimated student enrolment is 3.66 crore, out of which nearly 52 per cent are male and rest 48 per cent are female students. Across social category, Scheduled Caste (SC) student enrolment is around 14 per cent of the total enrolment and students belonging to Scheduled Tribe (ST) category constitute only 5 per cent of the total student enrolment. The GER of students in higher education continues to grow at a slow pace even though the country witnessed rapid increases in the number of universities and colleges. The aim of Draft National Education Policy 2019 by Government of India is to double GER from the present 26 per cent to 50 per cent by 2035. Therefore, the study suggested that the respective state governments should take measures to increase representation of SC, ST, minorities and women in higher education.

Keywords: Higher education, Gross enrollment ratio, Access and equity, Education policy, MHRD, India.

VALUATION OF E-BUSINESS WITH REFERENCE TO MYNTRA AND FLIPKART

Vaishnavi Prerana¹, Ayshath Azmina²

^{1&2} IIND Year M.com, St Agnes Centre For Post Graduate Studies and Research, Mangaluru

ABSTRACT

This research paper deals with the concept of valuation of e-business with reference to myntra and flipkart. The value of business is not just applied by its financial performance rather multiple of factors affect the valuation, similarly valuation process is not error free. Valuation of an online or offline business does not differ that much significantly, but still there are differences in their valuation. The process of valuing a business and its units helps to identify source of economic value creation and destruction within the company. Business need to be valued for a number of reason such as their purchase and sales, obtaining a listing inheritance tax and capital gains tax computations. Generally valuation difficulties are restricted to unlisted companies because listed companies have quoted share price. The firm further goes through many a common mistake too and these are the result of relying upon traditional practices and hence need is to find out such factors and problematic contents that distorts the valuation and misinterpretation of business and its financial position. The main aim of our research is to put light on strategies used by myntra and flipkart for valuation. Of e-business and to find the current position of these companies and to examine how e-service initiative affects the firms market valuation. To provide further insight paper also assess the impact of technology acquisition mode, the firms organizational position , industry characteristics and service introduction strategies on firm values. Secondary data is selected as major tool in the process of data collection to this study. The purpose of this research is also to investigate the method used for valuation of e-business and how it is further applicable .this study would be beneficial for further research.

KEYWORDS: E-business, valuation, myntra, flipkart, strategies, valuation creation

A STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IMPULSE BUYING BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG WOMEN

Mitali Madhusmita¹&Sampada Shah²

¹Student, 2nd M. Com IB, Mount Carmel College, #58, Palace Road, Vasanth Nagar,
Bengaluru – 560052. E-mail ID: mitalimishra972@gmail.com

²Student, 2nd M. Com IB, Mount Carmel College, #58, Palace Road, Vasanth Nagar,
Bengaluru – 560052. E-mail ID: shahsampada2@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study focuses in understanding the factors influencing the impulse buying behavior among young women. In this study a survey was conducted among women between the age group of 18 to 25 years. The study is based on primary data collected through questionnaires and also secondary data collected from books journals and the internet. Impulsive buying behavior is better understood by examining the impulsive buying tendency that shapes such behaviors. Due to globalization the younger generations now have easy access in purchasing a wide variety of goods or products. Apart from this there are wide varieties of psychological/social as well as marketing factors that pushes impulsive buying. Hence this study is made to find out more regarding such factors that pushes young women into impulsive buying.

Keywords: impulse buying, buying behaviours, women buyers, psychological factors.

PAPER 113

A STUDY ON LEGAL ASPECT RELATED TO THE BIO-MEDICAL WASTE MANAGEMENT IN INDIA

Pavithra Kumari

College of Management and commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwara

Mangalore- 575001, India

E-mail: pavithrakumarishetty@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Hospital is a Health care institution a place basically to treat any patient. Since the origination, the hospital is known for the treatment of sick persons. There are different types of hospitals like Teaching, Specialized, General, Acute care etc. but the primary goal of the hospital is to treat a patient. But while treating the patients the hospitals are ignorant of the environment. Now it is well-established fact that there are many adverse and harmful effects to the environment including human beings which are caused by the biomedical waste produced during patient care. Bio-medical waste indicates any waste which is produced during the diagnosis, treatment or immunization of human beings or animals or in research activities pertaining thereto or in the production or testing of biological and including categories mentioned in the schedule one of biomedical waste rules by Ministry of environment and forest notification. The hospital waste like body components, organs, tissues, blood and body fluids along with solid linens, cotton bandages and plaster from infected and contaminated areas are very essential to be appropriately accumulated, separated, stored, transported, treated and disposed of carefully to avert nosocomial or hospital-acquired infections. Bio-Medical Waste Management and Handling have assumed tremendous positive results in the emerging discipline of healthcare law and ethics. The bio-medical waste and management and handling have been given priority in the overall purview of public health hazard. This paper mainly aimed to study and discuss the law related to the bio-medical waste management in India as per the Bio-Medical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules of 2016. The sources of information for this paper is based on secondary data.

Key words: Bio-Medical, Diagnosis, Tissues, and Nosocomial.

A STUDY ON TRANSFORMATION OF ON ROAD AUTOMOBILES TO ELECTRIC VEHICLES IN INDIA

Anumesh Kariappa

Assistant professor

College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University

City Campus Pandeshwar, Mangalore -575001

E-mail anumesh5@rediffmail.com Ph: 9742283392

ABSTRACT

The Indian government has a clear agenda of moving to an Electric Vehicles (EV) only regime, with a complete phasing out of vehicles that are driven by Internal Combustion Engines (ICEs). The Ministry of Heavy Industries and Public Enterprises had also launched the FAME scheme (Faster Adoption and Manufacturing of (Hybrid &) Electric Vehicles in India) in 2015 under the National Electric Mobility Mission Plan 2020 (NEMMP 2020) to promote faster transformation from ICE to EVs. The FAME scheme focuses on a three phased approach to achieve the target of introducing six to seven million electrified vehicles on Indian roads by 2020. Subsequently, multiple state governments have been providing incentives to attract electric vehicle (EV) manufacturing in their states, and to fast-track adoption of EVs. Karnataka became the first state of the country to notify an EV policy. Telangana and Andhra Pradesh are expected to release their respective policies in due course. In addition, NITI Aayog's 'Three Year Action Agenda is to be implemented by 2019-20' also emphasises the need to migrate from ICE to eco-friendly automobiles. Firstly Vehicular pollution Ten Indian cities are among the world's twenty most polluted cities of the world according to the Global Urban Ambient Air Pollution database, 2016. ICEs are one of the major contributors to air pollution emitting high levels of sulphur dioxide and suspended particulate matter amongst other pollutants such as carbon monoxide, ozone, oxides of nitrogen and hydrocarbons. Secondly Impact on health in the congested Indian cities According to State of Global Air 2017 report, India accounts for the second highest number of premature deaths due to air pollution in the world. The Lancet Commission 2017 also ranked India as no.1 in pollution related deaths with air pollution being the biggest contributor. Thirdly Impact on balance of payment as oil is the largest imported commodity in India Of the total oil consumption in the country, nearly 70 per cent of diesel sales and 99.6 per cent of petrol sales occur in the transport sector. The growth in energy demand from this sector outpaces growth in all other sectors and is estimated to reach 280Mtoe (Million tonnes of oil equivalent) in 2040, if the present trend continues. Transition to electric mobility can significantly ease out the pressures of balance of payment. This paper will analyse the aspects of Electric vehicles into Indian market.

Key words: Electric vehicles, automobile industry and Air pollution

PAPER 115

**CONSUMER PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS
ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN AND AROUND UDUPI REGION**

Mrs. Pratima R Shetty, Mrs. Sowmya Shetty, Ms. Meenakshi Acharya
Poornaprajna College, Udupi

ABSTRACT

The term “organic” refers to the way agricultural products are grown and processed. The regulations vary from country to country. Organic crops must be grown without the use of synthetic pesticides, petroleum-based fertilizers, and sewage sludge-based fertilizers. Organic livestock raised for meat, eggs, and dairy products must have access to the outdoors and be given organic feed. They may not be given antibiotics, growth hormones, or any animal by-products. How your food is grown or raised can have a major impact on your mental and emotional health as well as the environment. Organic foods often have more beneficial nutrients, such as antioxidants, than their conventionally-grown counterparts and people with allergies to foods, chemicals, or preservatives often find their symptoms lessen or go away when they eat only organic foods. The market for organic food products in India has been growing at a rapid pace over the last few years. Rising health consciousness among middle class consumers in major cities across India has been the key factor contributing to growth in the market. The demand for eco- friendly products and health oriented products such as organic products has been increasing nowadays. Thus, this paper analyses the perception of consumer towards organic products in Udupi region and it aims to identify the level of awareness towards the use of organic products among the consumers of Udupi region

Key words: Organic products, perception, awareness, health consciousness

PAPER 116

CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT WITH FOCUS ON THE COOPERATIVE BANKING SECTOR

Arati.N.Rawal

Research scholar, Department of commerce,
Rani Chennamma University, Belgavi,
Mail.id: aru265@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Credit risk is most common risk in the cooperative banking sector. It is one of the hidden features, if not timely controlled, will negative impact on banking business. Therefore, it is necessary to implementing the credit risk management processes in the banking transactions. It helps the banks in identifying, measuring, monitor and control the risk and also act as most important tool for survival of banking business. The purpose of the present study is to focus on the state of credit risk management process in cooperative banks in Dharwad district. Further, the paper makes an assessment of the extent to which cooperative banks were following the standard practices and identify the focus area of improvement in near future.

Keyword: Credit risk management process,

PAPER 117

EMERGING TRENDS IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fiona Rodrigues

Poornaprajna Institute of Management

ABSTRACT

HRM means managing the functions of employing, developing, compensating, and utilizing human resources, resulting in the creation and development of human and industrial relations which would shape the future policies and practices of human resource management, with a view to contribute proportionately to the individual, organizational, and social goals. Continuous change in technology, economic, social and psychological understandings and structure have influence on both human resource and its management. Human resources of paramount importance for the success of any organization. In the present complex milieu organizations are greatly influenced by the changes taking place in internal and external environment, no business can change, exist or grow without appropriate human resources, therefore HRM has become the focus of attention of every progressive organization. HRM must be viewed through the prism of overall strategic goals of the organization instead of a standalone unit that takes a unit based on a micro approach. Organizations have to adopt a holistic perspective towards HRM that ensures that there are no piecemeal strategies and it should evolve according to changes in the present times. Hence the organization that changes its practices will tend to survive profitability in the long run. Human resource management is a process of bringing people and organization together, so that the goals of each other are met, Indian organizations are also witnessing a change in systems, management, culture and philosophy due to the global alignment of Indian organization. As globalization has been a challenging issue for the organization because international human resource management has placed great emphasis on the number of responsibilities and functions, such as relocation, orientation, translation services to help employees adapt to new and different environment outside their own country. Henceforth the necessary attention must be taken by the HR managers in formulating policies, motivation, maintaining the relationship and stressing on the quality in administration. Thus, in the end HRD plays the role of initiator, planner, executor in every organization.

Key word: HRM, Emerging trends.

PAPER 118

ENCOURAGING INNOVATIVE THINKING THROUGH DIGITIZATION OF EDUCATION

Venkatesh Sali ¹, Santosh T. D ²

¹ Assistant Professor in Economics, C.G. Bellad GFGC Akkialur – 581102,
Hangal (Taluk), Haveri (District), E-mail ID: vmrmchsali@gmail.com,

² Assistant Professor in Sociology, C.G. Bellad GFGC Akkialur – 581102,
Hangal (Taluk), Haveri (District), E-mail ID: tdsantosh8@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the present competitive world Education in the right direction shape the future of the students. The demographic dividend which India has right now can be exploited through providing education in right direction. Affordability and accessibility of education in India is addressed through Reservations and Acts like Right to Education. But because of Colonial masters, India is mastered in education system where memorizing things and collecting factual information play important role. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 2014 had ranked India 66 out of 140 countries in terms of local dynamics of innovation. This shows very dismal picture of the Indian education system. Added to this the NASSCOM – Mckinsey report “Perspective 2020: transform business, transform India” (2009) said only 26% of India’s engineering graduates were employable. This shows the lack of opportunities created by Indian education in the classrooms because of lack of infrastructure facilities namely digital modes. We have in our research paper conducted experiment explaining the concept of Inflation by employing black board and combining explanation and points, pictures and animated videos. We have taken fifty students and asked the solution to overcome the problem of Inflation, in situation without using digital tools we have succeeded in clarifying the concept but failed to build the more imagination and creativity in them for longer period. Finally we conclude that digital teaching will enhance or stimulate creativity among the students and successful in clearing the concepts.

Keywords: Education, Affordability, Development, Creativity and Innovation.

PAPER 119

IMPACT OF CUSTOMER ORIENTED BEHAVIOURS OF SALESPERSONS ON SALES PERFORMANCE – AN AUTOMOBILE DEALERS INDUSTRY PERSPECTIVE IN INDIA

Dr. Kusuma¹; Dr. Raja K. G.²;

¹Faculty, College of management & commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore

²Principal, MalikDeenar Institute of management studies,Seethangoli, Kasaragod

ABSTRACT

In today's highly competitive markets where competitors offer products that are largely homogenous, the effectiveness of salespersons during the interaction with the customer is critical to the sales success. Research has shown that firms that successfully implement the marketing concept or consumer orientation enjoy superior salespersons performance and business performance (Hinson *et al.*, 2008, Narver and Slater, 1990; Kuada & Buatsi, 2005, Rueket, 1992; Jaworski, Kohli, et. al., 2000, Kotler and Philip 2014). This study aims at studying the impact of salesperson's customer oriented behaviours on his/her performance and automobile dealer's performance in Indian context and, therefore, offers a detailed insight from an Indian sales force perspective. A model was tested using survey data collected from salespeople and top marketing managers within a automobile dealership firms located in selected cities of India. A structural equation model was used to test the hypotheses. The findings suggest an interesting interplay between salesperson's customer orientated behaviours and his/her sales performance. The relationship between the customer orientated behaviours and salespersons performance is fully mediated by salesperson's organizational citizenship behaviours, salesperson's perception of market orientation, market turbulence and competitive intensity. Results support the role of these variables as driver of favourable individual level customer orientated behaviours and their performance which will be of great interest in future research in this area by the academicians and automobile dealers managers.

Key words: Customer Oriented Behaviour ,Organisational Citizenship Behavior, Market Orientation, Competitive Intensity & Market Turbulence, Salespersons performance, Organizational performance

PAPER 120

INNOVATIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR HOTEL INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SEA ROUTE MULTI CUISINE RESTAURANT

Mr. Sagar Srinivas

Assistant Professor;Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: sagarsrinivas@ymail.com

ABSTRACT

The hospitality industry is one of the fastest and largest growing sectors in the world. The hotel industry is being the most visible sector within the hospitality industry and its currently experiencing setback that threatens the attractiveness in the industry. Thus marketing in this industry has gained a leading role in today's competitive world. Innovative marketing strategies are adopted in the industry to attract customers and gain benefits, sustain the increasing level of exterior market competitiveness and improve the internal and external competitive level in the hotel and yet keeping the environment safe to visit and have a memorable experience. Promoting the hotel in the domestic market and in global world will help the hotel to strengthen the acquired position in the domestic market. The arrival of e-commerce in India has brought every eatery under a single roof and it's a challenge to be addressed. Promoting and branding is essential to get every customer associate with the hotel when they think of food. Social media plays an important role in reaching the customers and to convince and attract them to visit the place. A satisfied customer is necessary to keep a fixed amount of revenue to meet the expenditure. The objective of the paper is to assess the role played by marketing in development of hotel and to identify different innovative strategies of marketing that will help in promoting the hotel in the current challenging industry.

Keywords: Marketing strategies,hotel industry,hospitality industry and e- commerce

PAPER 121

MAKE IN INDIA CAMPAIGN AND FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

Dr.(smt)Shilpa Danappanavar

Lecturer in Commerce; LE's Sri Mrityunjaya College of Commerce and Arts,
Email- shilpahosagoudar@gmail.com; Mob.no-9481009954

ABSTRACT

Make in India Campaign is an initiative of Government of India to encourage domestic as well as foreign entrepreneurs to produce their products in India. The main focus of make in India is to make full utilization of the skill, talent, discipline and determination which is found in ample in the people of India and this is also an international marketing strategy to attract investments from businesses all over the world and transforming India into a global manufacturing Hub. In this context the present study makes an attempt to study the recent initiatives taken by various companies and to analyse the Inflows of Foreign Direct Investment after launching the "Make in India" campaign. The study reported that over all scenario of make in India and FDI was a positive summon to prospective investors from all over the world. It helps to solve the so many devil problems of our country and also leads to economic development of the nation.

Key Words: Foreign Direct Investment, Make in India, Growth and Development.

PAPER 122

**PARENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS SCHOOLING AND EDUCATION
OF CHILDREN**

Praveenkumar¹ and Khushbu Varma²

¹Praveen Kumar, Research Scholar, Department of Studies and Research in Social Work,
Rani

Channamma University, Belagavi. Email: praveenkumarsw88@gmail.com

²KhushbuVerma, (MSW), School of Social Work, RoshniNilaya, Mangalore. Email:
khushbubsw@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study was aims to assess the attitude of parents towards the education and schooling of their children. The study has adopted explorative research design. With the help of simple random sampling technique research has conducted personal interview with 30 families. The age range of the sample was 30-45 years, and they all belongs to Vijayapura city of Karnataka. A 23-item questionnaire was used to collect the data. The data were collected and analyzed by using SPSS software. The findings of the study will be discussed in full paper.

Key words: Parents, Attitude, Education, And Children.

PAPER 123

SHATTERING GLASS CEILING IN HEALTHCARE SECTOR

Ms. Prathibha.R¹, Dr. Puttanna.K²

¹Research Scholar Dept. of Business Administration Mangalore University Mangalagangothri - 574 199 Email:prathibha.R25@gmail.com

²Associate Professor Dept of Business Administration Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri Email:puttannak@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Women have been struggling a lot in achieving equality in all areas of life and this applies in medicine too. In this regard Glass Ceiling is a term used to describe the barriers that restricts the women from advancing the growth. Although women make up the majority of the healthcare workforce, they often experience career advancement challenges and remain significantly underrepresented in formal leadership positions and specialty areas. The main objective of this paper is to identify whether the career growth of female doctors progress in the same way as that of male doctors or do they have to break the ceiling to climb up the career ladder. The study is conceptual in nature based on the literature review focuses on Glass ceiling concept by identifying various factors that give rise to it and attempts to identify various barriers which restricts the female doctors from advancing their career growth and the role played by them in breaking it which is represented with the help of a Ishikawa model.

Keywords: Glass Ceiling, Female doctors, Healthcare, Barriers, Ishikawa Model.

PAPER 124

THE IMPORTANCE OF CORPORATE YOGA WELLNESS PROGRAMMES FOR INDIAN BPO COMPANIES

Zeljka Ciganovic¹, Dr. K. Krishna Sharma²,

¹Research Scholar, Dept. of Human Consciousness and Yogic Sciences, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Karnataka, India, E-mail: zeljka.ciganovic@gmail.com

²Guide, Dept. of Human Consciousness and Yogic Sciences, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Karnataka, India, E-mail: drkrisharma@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Fast technological and economic developments have helped Indian organizations to grow, and restructure and reorganize their business processes. In order to decrease their costs of business processes, organizations outsource them to other organizations. Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sector has been an important growth catalyst for the Indian economy. The major part of business is being done for the international markets which make employees work in different time zones, usually in night shifts. “Graveyard shifts” interrupt circadian rhythm, cause sleep disorders, poor cognitive and executive functioning, depression and a predisposition to infection. Due to “repetitive brain strain”, fast-paced work environment, various work stressors, constant repression of own emotions and inability to achieve work-life balance, increased risk for physical and psychological disorders might develop, resulting in low employee morale, absenteeism, high employee turnover and reduced productivity. There is a growing need for a worksite solution that focuses on the health needs of BPO employees. Several analyses of workplace health promotion programs have proven that they are the perfect tool for impacting employees’ long-term lifestyle choices – making employees with good health habits have lower medical costs and increased productivity. As one of the fruitful solutions, the research is pointing to yoga. Yoga is an ancient Indian system of practices focusing on individual’s physical, mental and spiritual development. Practicing yoga can decrease stress and anxiety, relieve physical tension, reduce pain, reduce risks of injury, improve posture, improve lung function, increase energy and attention span, and improve concentration and communication skills. Due to its cost effectiveness and numerous health benefits, number of corporate yoga wellness programmes has increased significantly all over the world over the past two decades, and still there is a huge scope for growth.

Keywords: corporate yoga wellness programmes, occupational stress, BPO, IT sector

PAPER 125

A NEW CONCEPT OF CIRCULAR MODEL OF MANAGEMENT FOR ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE SUCCESS AND GROWTH

Keerthan Raj¹ & Dr. P.S. Aithal²

Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore- 575 001

Email: 2keerthanraj@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

According to the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), sustainable development has been defined in many ways, and it states that: "Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." We have seen a lot of focus on sustainable development starting from the initiative of the United Nations which has made all nations focus on Sustainable Goals to be achieved by 2030, to large conglomerates and small business enterprises likewise focussing on sustainable business practices, which if well planned would yield success and growth. In the light of the global challenges faced in relation to environmental, economic and social resources sustainable development leading to sustainable success and growth calls for a significant rethinking in the management of resources within the and external to the organization. In this paper we propound the furthering of a circular economy concept to management as 'circular model of management'. Borrowed from the concept of circular economy, a circular economy (as against a linear economy) is an economic system aimed at minimizing waste and making the most of resources. Moving towards a circular economy delivers benefits such as reducing pressure on resources, increases competitiveness, stimulates innovation and boosts growth. This study is developed through extensive work in subsistence communities (base of the pyramid customers) in emerging markets. A circular economy promotes social, environmental, economic and overall restorative and regenerative capabilities, similarly a circular model of management will as envisaged promote regenerative and restorative capability in the organization which will ensure sustainable growth and success.

Keywords: Base of the pyramid, circular, economy, model. sustainable,

A STUDY ON OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FACED BY BUDDING HOTEL PROFESSIONALS IN INDIA.

Bibin Eldho Thomas¹

¹Assistant Professor, College of Hotel Management and Tourism, Srinivas University,
Karnataka, India

Email: eldho.bibin@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Tourism is an industry which creates large number of employment opportunities to the nation. Hotel industry is an integral component of travel and tourism industry. The growth of travel and tourism depends on availability of accommodation options provided by various hotels around the globe. The manpower requirement of hotel industry is in huge numbers which the industry is finding it difficult to meet. Today there are hundreds catering colleges and schools spread across length and breadth of country trying to cater to the human resource needs of this industry. These institutes provide a wide range of programs starting from diploma to three and four year degree and also post graduate programs. Then also we find that hotel industry has large number of job opportunities round the year. These large job opportunities are due to widespread opening of new hotels with all latest luxury facilities and another reason for this scenario is the movement of work force to international job market after they receive the required experience to move out of the country. The shortage of manpower in the hotel industry is also due to some of the odd practices that prevail in industry which has to be rectified as soon as possible. One of the odd practice followed is lengthy shift pattern which can go up to 10 to 12 hours a day. Another factor is low remuneration received for the work done. Fresher's who had completed their studies and when they starts there career in an organization in city like Bangalore they will receive an average salary of Rupees 14000.00 and with this amount they has to manage their repayment of education loan accommodation and transportation in a metro city like Bangalore and also his personal expenses. This paper analyses various opportunities and challenges faced by budding hotel professionals in India

Key words: Hotel Industry, New Hotels, Experience, Long Shift, Low Remuneration

AN ATTEMPT TO STUDY THE REASONS BEHIND THE FAILURE OF JET AIRWAYS -CASE STUDY

Pavithra Kumari¹, Kavyashri²

¹College of Management and commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwara
Mangalore- 575001, India; E-mail: pavithrakumarishetty@gmail.com

²College of Commerce and Management, Srinivas University
E-mail- kavyarairail8@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

One of the most expeditious-growing airline industries in the world is the Indian aviation industry. On December 1912 with the first domestic air route between Karachi and Delhi paved a way for the history of Indian Aviation Industry. Later till the mid-1990s, the Indian aviation industry was dominated by regime-owned airlines. When the regime adopted the Open-welkin policy in 1990 and other liberalization policies, it led to a rapid and dramatic transformation in the aviation industry and set up as a steppingstone for the incorporation of Jet Airways by Naresh Goyal. Jet Airways was incorporated on 1st April 1992, as a private company with inhibited liability under the Companies Act. It commenced its operations as Air Taxi Operator on 5th May 1993 with a fleet of four leased Boeing 737-300 aircrafts. Jet Airways was the second-most sizably voluminous airline in India as of 2016 February, both in terms of market share and passengers carried. 51% of Jet Airways was owned by Naresh Goyal who was the CEO of Jet Airways. Jet Airways was prosperity for many years. In 2006 Jet Airways purchased Air Sahara for the US \$ 500 million and rebranded it as Jet Lite by inditing off its entire investments. In August 2018, DGCA (Directorate General of Civil Aviation) conducted a financial audit of Jet Airways. Full-accommodation airline jet airways optically discerned losses worsen in the quarter ended June 30, 2018, as the impact of fuel price hike and the falling rupee weighed heavily on the carrier's financial performance. Poor Management, incompetence, inability to find investors were the main factors which led to shutting down of Jet Airways. In this paper, we endeavoured to study what was the reason falling abaft the failure of jet airways operation in aviation industry even after putting several efforts by the government as well as Jet Airways to revive.

Keywords: Expeditious-growing, Air Taxi Operator, Liberalization, and Voluminous

BRIDGING THE GAP IN HOSPITALITY EDUCATION AND INDUSTRIAL REQUIREMENTS

Swaminathan S

Dean, College of Hotel Management and Tourism,
Srinivas University, srinithisp@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Hospitality sector growth is very high in last two decades. The manpower need is also more in current scenario. But the hospitality graduates face problems in finding a job placement in the industry. The need and expectation of the industry is not matching with their standards. In other words, what the student learn in the class room and the actual work place needs are not satisfied. This paper conceptually analyzes the problem behind the gap and tries to bridge the gap. From the pass out hospitality graduates who are working in the industry, got the feedback from them, reveals some common drawbacks are identified, they are multi-lingual barrier, short period of internship, inadequate computer training, not making them psychologically strong and so on. So as a hospitality educator the above mentioned important skills need to be added in the syllabus, which help them to be part of the industry, and graduates will be ready to take up operational skills, management skills, HR skills etc. These skills are meant to make them more resourceful to their employers and the customers they will be serving. Hospitality education is more of practical oriented subjects. All the core area's such as food beverage service, Food production, House keeping & Front office are all taught practically with the support of theoretical explanation. Even though basic fundamentals are taught to the hospitality student, to understand the reality they should work in the industry as a trainee, so that they can compare themselves with that they had learnt and what has been practiced in the industry currently. Most of the students are leaving the industry after a short term, the main reason is they are not able to withstand the industry work pressure. The main reason for this is because of lack of long period industrial training. Due to the academic structure, long period of industrial training is out short for shorter period resulting in this problem, due to more number of young hospitality graduates high turnover in the job, reflecting bad experience to the hospitality industry. So the hospitality educator should train the hospitality students for not only skills and competencies at the front line level, but to also train them for critical thinking skills, emotional intelligence etc.

Keywords: hospitality education, sector , industry

CHALLENGES AND WORK LIFE BALANCE AMONG WOMEN STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHERS OF KARNATAKA- A STUDY

Sonia DelroseNoronha¹ &Dr. P. S. Aithal²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Management, Srinivas University,
Pandeshwar -575001, Karnataka, India.

^{1,2}Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru –575 001, India
E-Mail: soniadelrose@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

One cannot overlook the realities of the present-day work situations, which has made the lives of the individual's complex and has created stress extending beyond the boundaries of the organizations. Because of expanding enrolment of women in all aspects of education and different areas of employment the most recent years saw developing support from policymakers, increase of women in the decision-making process and senior administration positions in both private and public sectors. This is true even in the education sector where recent developments show a greater role for women in teaching and top leadership positions. Regardless of the considerable role of women in the society, the literature suggests that working women in various positions are confronting a different reality due to Individual, Family, organizational and cultural challenges that hinder their effectiveness as professionals. A work-life imbalance is often expressed with psychological and physical strains in employees resulting in low productivity, employee engagement, low quality, and employee retention. There is a well-defined need to adopt well-planned work-life Balance strategies that should be credible, strategic and rational with the Human resource policy framework and organizational goals. This will help in developing a performance-based culture in the organization. Through a survey of 422 women state university teachers, this paper attempts to identify the challenges that women teachers face in State universities of Karnataka. Work-life balance is a cause of concern and should be considered religiously to achieve a mutually beneficial situation for the individuals and the organization in the long run.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Challenges, State Universities

CHANGING PERSPECTIVES IN INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

Kamath Anusuya¹, B.K. Veena B²

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email. kamathanusuya@gmail.com

²Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email. veenabk19@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education is a unique asset for human beings to reach their goals in life. Through education any sort of knowledge that is gained can be put into practical basis and by practicing this in our day today life activities will help us to develop our knowledge and get experience. Earlier Gurukula system was one of the unique residential learning systems and here the Guru, the teacher will help his pupil's to acquire knowledge and get an eternal success in their life. In Gurukula the pupil's help their Guru in house core activities and also learn to lead their life in a positive manner as a down to earth learning is been taught to the pupils and as a gesture of respect shown to the Guru they give Gurudakshina at the end of their learning. After Gurukula we can observe the existence of British education policies and they introduced the circular learning system. After independence the government introduced the education is right to all and implemented a free and compulsory primary education to all. Later in education system many innovation and experiment has happened and they introduced an online base learning and teaching by the collaboration with other countries we can get our degree by online courses. The educationists thought that vocational learning is a best method of learning which helps the individual face the competition in this present world than curricular learning system. In present scenario we can observe the global partnership with various countries to get an education in various fields. The changing trends in education has made the people to gain knowledge through practical thinking and bring change in the society and is a part of nations development as Education is the only property that cannot be stolen by anyone.

Key words: Education, System, Development, Vocational learning, trends in education and Knowledge.

DIGITAL EDUCATION CHALLENGES AND BENEFITS OF AN INDIAN SOCIETY

Dr.Lingaraj G Pujar

Principal, Vidyadayini College Of Education,
K R Nagar,HariharDist; Davangere State; Karnataka 577 601,
email id :lingarajpujar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Digital education means digital learning. It is a type of learning that is supported by digital technology or by instructional practice that makes effective use of digital technology. Digital learning occurs across all learning areas and domains. Digital education gives win-win opportunities for all, at one side School, colleges and other institution finds the rapid rise in enrolments and added revenue because of digital education, and on other side students view this as a flexible and alternate option allowing them to study as per their convenient time and pace. Teachers and professors too find it convenient to prepare their teaching plans aided by digital technology. Teaching and learning becomes a smoother experience as it includes animations, ramification and audio-visual effects. Education sector in India has seen a series of rapid expansion in last couple of years which helped to transform the country into a knowledge haven. The study clearly points that development of education infrastructure is required for the development of digital education across the country. This will lead to considerable increase in infrastructure investment in the education sector. Democratic governance, English speaking tech-educated talent and a strong legal and intellectual property protection framework are required for the development of digital education in Indian society. Government of India has also taken major Initiatives for the development of digital education in India like opening of IIT's and IIM's in new locations as well as allocating educational grants for research scholars in most government institutions.

Keywords: Digital education, India, challenges

GLOBAL ECONOMICS COLLAPSE SINCE 2008 TO 2013- CAUSES, CONSEQUENCES & MEASURES

Nelson Pereira¹

Lecturer, School of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India.

Email: anelsonpereira @gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The causes of the financial crisis are complex. Mainly the excessive debt burdens of Western especially US households particularly in the last decade. Within this context, the crisis was triggered by the proliferation of mortgage loans, the famous subprime loans granted to low income households. The specific about them was high interest rates and long repayment period which targeted modest households with relatively high risk of default. In order to attract clients very low interest rates prevailed at the beginning was increased significantly after few years. During 2000 US had good Economic Growth raising confidence of the traders with then popular subprime credit which nearly six million low income households, were on the threshold of receiving these loans. Many households opted for subprime loans had to default as they could not meet the brutal increase in their monthly repayment. These defaults were amplified by the spike in US interest rates starting in 2004 and by the unexpected fall in real estate prices during the beginning of 2006. The securities linked to these sub-primes quickly lost their value, which is when the complex financial products showed their truly toxic character. Banks stopped transacting since it has no longer confidence upon the financial products available in the market. This lead to the gigantic financial paralysis initiated through inter banking crisis of July 2007. Major Banks were either totally or nearly bankrupted. In order to reduce the risk of stocks and bonds which are losing value and hedging the risks inherent to financial speculations, banks created complex financial products and hedging instruments in the form of derivatives allowing to sell a portion of risky subprime securities. This paper analyses the causes, consequences and measures to overcome the global economic recession.

Key words: Financial Crisis, Global, Sub Prime Loan, Financial Products, Securities, Economic recession.

PAPER 133

INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN THE HOSPITALITY TECHNOLOGY IN VIEW OF VARYING CUSTOMER EXPECTATIONS

Mr. Subrat Saraf

Assistant Professor, College of Hotel Management and Tourism, Srinivas University,
subratsaraf@gamil.com

ABSTRACT

Hospitality industry is one among the fastest growing industries in the world. In terms of employment generation, one among every five new jobs in the world is created by the hospitality sector. This is owing to the increased and never ending desire and need of its customer market to travel and explore its diaspora. In the recent times, the hospitality industry has been witnessing innovations owing to certain reasons based on the preferences of the travellers that is expected to be the future trend of its existence. The entrepreneurs can see a fertile ground for themselves in the hospitality sector by understanding the varied customer preferences. Apart from entrepreneurs as stakeholders of hospitality sector, new types of travellers such as millennials, Generation Z travellers and others such as business guests have paved a way to the hoteliers to bring changes and innovations in their services keeping in view the needs and aspirations of them. Such innovations and changes have been now able to serve guests with more customisation and convenience. Many such changes like new technology in guest services, concept of micro hotels, chatbots and robots, Facial recognition technology have been in trend to completely change the way hotels serve. But the greatest challenge here is to maintain the human relations and the human touch throughout such transactions as personal relationships can only build a strong client royalty.

Keywords: Millennials, Generation Z travellers, Human relations, Customisation

PAPER 134

ISSUES RELATING TO VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN INDIA- PREVALENCE, CAUSES AND IMPLICATION

Pavithra Kumari

College of Management and commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwara

Mangalore- 575001, India

E-mail: pavithrakumarishetty@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Women of India today are faced with incipient situations, trapped by incipient quandaries and encountered many challenges. Violence against women is an impediment to the achievement of the objectives of parity, development and placidity. Violence against women in India is an issue rooted in societal norms and economic dependence. Discriminatory practices are underlined by laws favouring men in several situations. Inadequate policing and judicial practices gainsay the female victim's proper protection and justice. Albeit female participation in public life is increasing and laws have been amended, India still has a long way to go to make Indian women equal denizens in their own country. Violence against women is not an incipient phenomenon. Women must bear the burns of domestic, public, physical as well as emotional and phrenic violence against them, which affects her status in society at a more astronomically immense extent. The statistics of incrementing malefactions against women is shocking, where women are subjected to violence attacks i.e. foeticide, infanticide, medical neglect, child espousments, bride burning, sexual abuse of girl child, coerced marriages, rapes, prostitution, sexual harassment at home as well as workplaces etc. In all the above cases women are considered as an aggrieved person. Prosecution policies need to be evaluated carefully to determine whether they avail avert violence and ascertain they do not result in more preponderant harm. In this paper, my argument would be how women have become victim to the violence in India and what are the influencing causes behind such violence. This paper is analysing the data based on secondary sources.

Key words: Impediment, Denizens, Phrenic violence, Foeticide and Infanticide.

QUALITY ASSURANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS

Vidya N¹, D'Mello Laveena²

¹Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India Email:vidyakrithi.n@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India.lavynoronha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education is the process and complete activity aiming to pass knowledge and skills, which are preparing the individual to lead an effective life in the society. And Higher Education Institutions play a vital role in the development of the Nation. Constant improving of educational quality is one of the significant tasks of the educational institutions. In the era of market economy, the process of attracting students may be analyzed from different grounds but it also ensures that they have to maintain the quality. This can be assured by internal and external environment which we call as the 'Stakeholders'. They are the people who are able to influence the objectives of a given organisation. Stakeholders in higher education include Students, Alumni, Parents, Academic Faculty, Non Teaching Staff, Administrators, Board of Directors, Donors, and Government Officials etc. Higher education should identify the important Stakeholders collect feedbacks and improve their results. This study will highlight on the role of the stakeholders and their involvement in the development activities of the educational institutions. New governance principle expects active stakeholder's engagement in all phases of policy making. Quality Assurance is one, where Stakeholder input areas strongly encouraged. Higher education is being pushed forward for competitiveness. The pressure requires continuous improvement. This paper is mainly attempting to find the quality assurance both internal and external stakeholders and its impact on the higher educational institutional functioning, environment, staffs qualification, institutional culture, management and development. And also predict the interests, needs and requirements of all key players in the environment.

Keywords: Higher Education, Stakeholders , Quality Assurance, environment and Educational institutions.

STUDY ON CONSUMERS BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS GREEN TECHNOLOGY PRODUCTS

Vishal¹, Nithin Gonsalves², Jayaprakasha.K³

¹Faculty college of management and commerce Srinivas university Mangalore

Email:vishalknayak0@gmail.com

²Faculty in commerce Vikas college Mangalore

Email:gonsalvesnithin1@gmail.com

³Faculty college of management and commerce Srinivas university Mangalore

Email:jai4appu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The industrial revolution has unleashed unprecedented economic growth over the last two and a half centuries, mobilizing massive resources and improving the standard of living in many parts of the world. However, this progress has been uneven, with billions of people still mired in abject poverty, and it resulted in increasing pressures on the natural environment. The study of green technology involves a group of methods and materials, from techniques for energy-generating to non-toxic cleaning products. In the future, this field may bring tremendous changes in the day to day life of people. The environment global issues act as motivating factor in producing more environmentally friendly products, that will diminish the harm towards the global environment and result in the acceptance of green technology. The rate of consumption increased enormously all over the world, which resulted in the rapid growth of the economy and the higher rate of consumption also resulted in a decline in the environment. The consequences of this environmental degradation have resulted in pollution, global warming, etc. which has become a cause of public concern which in turn leads to the green movement for the preservation of the environment. Since individual producers and consumers are typically not be charged the true cost to society of using these resources, they tend to disregard this cost in their production and consumption decisions. These technologies are identified as green or clean technology. Green technologies involve energy efficiency, recycling, safety and health concerns, renewable resources, and many more. The key objective of this paper is to understand the variables affecting the consumer buying behavior of green products.

Keyword: Green technology, Green environment, Consumer behavior, Environment, Non-toxic

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL RESILIENCE OF WOMEN OF MANAGEMENT INSTITUTION

Sharmila S Shetty

Lecturer, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Email: sharmilasshetty21@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Emotional stability plays a major key role in one's personal life as well as in professional life. Maintaining a static behavior is a greater task for the human being. Ups and downs in family and profession push human being for a stressful situation where she will find difficult to move forward. This situation leads Women employees to burnouts which decline the performance. Resilient is ready to accept the change and challenging task quickly and adopt it. All employees are having resilience power which differs from one another. A person can be successful if they have a clear goal which boots resilience as well. Planning effectively, managing workload a balancing both family a workplace makes an employee more resilient. Some factors like renewing energy, good health, well-being, spiritual thinking help to build resilience among employees. Management also gives more important for resilient employees, as their performance gain by their positive behaviour. Today's generation is loaded by working schedule which makes them block their minds for positive thinking. Accepting change will take a long time. The Company as to lie down more important for the good environment of employees. This study reveals how the emotional resilience of women in management institutions helps the organization for success.

Keywords: Resilient, Adopting change, Balancing, Burnouts

A STUDY ON MULTI-LEVEL MARKETING WITH REFERENCE TO INDIAN ECONOMY

Revathi Radhakrishnan¹, P.S Aithal²

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: revathiradhakrishnan93@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Multi-level marketing is also called as direct selling, pyramid selling, referral marketing, and network marketing. Even though it is known in different names it is a strategy used and successful in more than 140 countries to sell products and services. There are many MLM companies in the world where their revenue or income is derived from a non-salaried workforce selling the company's products and services. Multilevel marketing is a strategy which some direct selling companies use to encourage existing distributors to recruit new distributors who are paid a percentage of their recruits' sales. The recruits are the distributor's "down line." Distributors also make money through direct sales of products to customers. There are many companies in India which provide direct selling facilities like Mi Lifestyle Marketing Global Private Limited, Amway, Herbalife, Forever Living Products, Vestige, Naswiz Retails, Win Nature International Pvt Ltd, Safe & Secure Online Marketing Pvt. Ltd., etc. Indian economy is a developing mixed economy and it is the 7th largest economy by nominal GDP and 3rd largest in purchasing power parity. Indian economy is the fastest growing service sector in the world. India has become a major exporter of IT services, Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services, and software services with \$177 billion revenue in 2019. In this paper, we are discussing multi-level marketing and what this business can contribute to the economy in large and how it affects the overall development of the country. The paper also discusses the direct selling companies in India and abroad which help to generate revenue for the economic growth.

Key Words: Multi-level marketing, Direct selling, Indian economy, Economic development,

PAPER 139

AVIATION MARKET AND DEVELOPMENT

MS.MINOSHKA ANGELINA FERNANDES¹, MRS. FLORIN SHELOMITH SOANS²

IB. Com student ST. Aloysius College (AUTONOMOUS)

Department of Economics MANGALORE8861494847

ABSTRACT

The civil aviation industry in India has emerged as one of the fastest growing industries in the country during the last three years. India is currently considered the third largest domestic civil aviation market in the world. Indian Aviation promises huge growth potential due to large and growing middle class population, rapid economic growth and rising aspirations of middle class. Therefore with this background the main objectives of the paper are as follows, to analyse Problems faced by Indian Aviation Market. To give Suggestions on how to support Indian Aviation Market: The Airline Industry should be viewed as a tool of economic growth and job creation. It is also one of the most challenging sectors of the economy. If the government accepts such suggestions that will benefit the aviation industry, then it will support more in the country's GDP and growth.

Keyword: airline industry, aviation market rapid economic

PAPER 140

EFFECTS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES ON THE PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF CRDB BANK

Peter Gwesso¹, Dr. T.N Sreedhara²

Research Scholar, Department of Business Administration;
MANGALORE UNIVERSITY
Professor, Department of Business Administration
MANGALORE UNIVERSITY
gwesso2010@gmail.com mobile: 9731168565

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to examine the effects of marketing strategies on the performance of CRDB Bank. The study adapted a descriptive research design which was exploratory in nature to obtain qualitative information. The target population was customers of two branches of CRDB Bank in Dar es Salaam City. For the study, a questionnaire was the preferred instrument for data collection and before the study was conducted, the questionnaire was pre-tested to gauge its validity and reliability. In addition, the data analysis with the help of SPSS illustrated the relationship between market strategies and performance of CRDB bank. The findings revealed that marketing strategies considered in this study namely customer relationship management and customer satisfaction have a positive relationship with performance. Additionally, the relationship was significant at 95% confidence since $p < 0.05$ for all the four marketing strategies implying that they are important factors affecting performance of CRDB bank. When the relationship between each marketing strategy and performance was considered individually, customer relationship management had a strong positive correlation with performance followed by customer satisfaction. The study therefore recommends that the bank should bear in mind factors related to customer relationship management and customer satisfaction in order to attract more customers and increase retention levels. Perhaps, the bank should explore market driven strategies which seeks to address customer needs and use segmentation, targeting and positioning as opposed to mass marketing.

Key word: Marketing Strategies, Performance, Customer relationship management, CRDB BANK

PAPER 141

E-NAM: A BETTER HOPE FOR THE FARMERS

Mrs Vinutha H K¹, Mrs Savitha Kotian ², Mrs Shruthi Pai³

Faculty of Commerce, Sri Mahaveera College, Moodabidri.

E-mail: vinu314ath@gmail.com, savithakotian819@gmail.com shruthisdange@gmail.com

Contact No: 8050813931, 9900662914 , 9845699845.

ABSTRACT

Electronic National Agriculture Markets (e-NAM) is an online trading platform for agricultural commodities in India. Most farmers in the country are unable to reap the benefits of their hard labour as they get cheated by middlemen. But, e-NAM, an online market which the government launched in 2016, holds the promise of increasing the earnings of the farmers by connecting them directly to the buyers across the country. Thereby Government has targeted to double farmer's income by 2022. This article highlights the better integration of APMCs across the country through a common online market platform to facilitate pan-India trade in agriculture commodities, providing better price discovery through transparent auction process based on quality of produce along with timely online payment to the farmer's bank account and reduced chances of collusion among traders. In the near future we can expect significant benefits through higher returns to farmers, lower transaction costs to buyers and stable prices and availability to consumers through e-NAM.

Keywords: e-NAM, APMC, online market, farmers, pan-India.

PAPER 142

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF SELECTED FMCG COMPANIES IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Bharathy¹ & Dr. Kushalappa S²

¹Assistant professor, Department of Post - Graduate studies and Research in commerce, Govinda Dasa college, surathkal, Mobile no. 9902814400. Email: bharthicharvi@gmail.com.

²Assistant Professor, Department of management, Govt. First Grade College Belthangady, Mob:9686324188. Email: kushalkayarthadka@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The FMCG sector has presently proved itself as the fourth largest sector in the Indian economy. It is highly competitive industry which makes a comparatively large contribution to the Indian economy in terms of GDP. In fact rural India with more than 70% share of the total Indian population has emerged as the most significant FMCG market. The FMCG industry plays a significant role in shaping a country's economy and development. This sector can drive growth, enhance quality of life, create jobs and support penetration of technology. The financial performance is the representation of the overall soundness of a business concern and it also discloses how a business has prospered under the leadership of its management. The present study is an attempt to evaluate the financial performance of selected FMCG companies in India. The main aim of the study is to suggest the most financially sound company to the investors group and others stakeholders of FMCG industry. The entire study is based on secondary data extracted from various sources like books and websites. Financial statements of the companies are obtained from money control website. Sampling technique used in the study is judgmental sampling and the sample is top 5 FMCG companies in India selected on the basis of market capitalisation. Descriptive statistics is used for the analysis and One-Way ANOVA test is used for testing the hypothesis. The test is conducted at 5% level of significance.

Key words: Financial performance, profitability, solvency, turnover.

PAPER 143

GREEN TECHNOLOGY AND DEVELOPMENT

Mr. ADEN¹, Mr. SIDDHANT², Mrs. Florin Shelomith Soans³

I B. Com St. Aloysius College (Autonomous)

Assistant Professor Economics St. Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangalore-575003

ABSTRACT

Green Technology is also known as sustainable technology that takes into account the long-term and short-term impact something has on the environment. Today, Economy, Energy and Environment are crucial topics of discussion with a special emphasis on the key words like sustainability, environment friendship and equity. The definition of “green energy” is vital and its backbone “green energy engineering” or “green technology” is the key. As time has passed by, major industrial companies have come up and have created technology or products with the only motive of earning profit without a thought about making it environment friendly. Due to the large boom of production of industrial technology or industrial products, the eco-system has entered the cycle of imbalance due to the dumping of e-waste and other toxic wastes. After realizing the backfire of nature through various natural catastrophes, the nations have brought up new means of creating technology that could help in making uses of renewable resources, efficient energy management and economy inter-relation. Energy efficiency, recycling, health and safety concerns and renewable resources, all go into the making of green products or technology in development. With these ideas the main objectives of the paper are as follows,

Although there are some defects of Green Technology, everything done have both positive and negative impacts. Global warming and energy crisis cannot be solved within one or two years. It really requires determination and continuous effort in improving the situation. Green Technology will definitely be the solution that gets potential in helping us to solve those problems and improve our environment.

KEYWORD: Global warming, Green technology, Recycling

PAPER 144

HEALTH, SAFETY & ENVIRONMENT MANAGEMENT – A CASE STUDY OF MCF Ltd., MANGALORE

Miss. Shridevi

HOD, Department of commerce Govinda Dasa College Surathkal 575014
Karnataka Ph: 9535628832 Mail ID : shridevi431@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Social justice and economic growth cannot be achieved without safe, clean environment as well as healthy working conditions. Safety and healthy working environment are regarded as a fundamental right of human being. The use of chemicals, the indiscriminate use of agro-chemicals like pesticides, agricultural machineries and equipment, industries with major accident risks, in many modern jobs pose serious safety, health and environmental risks. The fundamental purpose of National policy on Health, safety and environment at work place, is to eliminate the incidence of work-related injuries, disease and disaster. At the same time to ensure occupational safety, health and environment performance through proactive approaches. Today most of the organisations strive for sustainability internally by providing workplace conditions that are conducive to employee's health and safety. Now safety, health and environment management has become a discipline that studies and implements practical aspect of an environmental protection and safety at work place. So, organisation must do to make sure that their activities do not cause harmfulness to anyone. Their intention is to be enhancing the well being of the employees and society at large. Organisation should encourage those attitudes and methods which will lead to improve physical, mental health of employees as well as environment.

MCF is the largest manufactures of chemical fertilizers in the State of Karnataka, India. The factory is located at Panambur, North of Mangalore city. The aim of the present case study is to find the safety and health measures adopted by MCF in order to protect the health of employees and also to know environmental management strategies developed to ensure welfare of the society.

Keywords: Social justice, clean environment, Healthy working conditions, Health, Safety and Environmental management & Performance.

PAPER 145

IMPACT OF JET LAG ON PERFORMANCE OF CABIN CREW IN AVIATION INDUSTRY

Kavyashri¹ & Pavithra Kumari²

¹College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwara
Mangalore – 01, India. E-mail- _kavyarairail8@gmail.com

²College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwara
Mangalore – 01, India. E-mail: pavithrakumarishetty@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aviation industry encapsulates the development, operations and management of aircrafts. One of the recognizable asset and key players to aviation sector is cabin crew. Cabin crew or flight attendants who are also known as airhosts/ hostesses, stewards/ stewardesses, cabin attendants are members of an aircrew employed by commercial flights, on select business jet aircraft and on some military aircraft. The primary role of flight attendants are to provide regime services and respond to the predicament to ensure the safety and comfort of airline passengers while ascend planes. Cabin crew has to travel different places on board and have to cross various time zones. A time zone is a geographical region which has the same time everywhere within it. Aircrew sleep is extremely significant in the current scenario of airline operations. Jet lag also called as desynchronizes, weariness and flight fatigue, is a temporary disorder that causes fatigue, day time sleepiness, insomnia, loss of concentration and alertness, depression, disorientation and other symptoms as a result of air travel across time zones. When the flight attendants move across different time zones it will disrupt their circadian rhythm. Desynchronize in body clock will have an adverse impact over the performance of flight attendants. It decreases the work efficiency, crew coordination, vigilance, and attention; briefly the entire job content of cabin crew suffers. By undertaking better precautionary measures the cabin crew can avoid the impact of jet lag on their performance on board to a certain extent.

Keyword: Flight attendants, Circadian rhythm, Time zones, Jet lag

PAPER 146

PERCEPTION CREATED AMONG PEOPLE ABOUT ONLINE MARKETING

Ms. Haniya

St. Aloysius College (Autonomous)Mangalore-575003

ABSTRACT

Marketing is nothing but the actions or business of promoting and selling products or services, including market research and advertising. The world is now in the digital space. We have reached a time where 170 million active users are log in to social media every day. Technology and the market were always linked to each other. Today when most of the potential consumers are present in the cyberspace, companies are also reaching there and devising marketing campaigns to target market. Companies like Google, Facebook are increasing their profit margin by increasing the number of advertisement, for which they get paid by the advertising companies. It is pivotal for the company to analyse people's opinion on the advertisement.

Keywords: Market, Online marketing, Social media, Advertisement.

PAPER 147

SIGNIFICANCE OF STRESS-FREE ENVIRONMENT: INDIAN BUSINESS

Ms. Haniya, Mrs. Florin Shelomith Soans

II B. Com Student,

Assistant Professor Economics St. Aloysius College (Autonomous)Mangalore-575003.

ABSTRACT

Stress is very common in this present generation. People sometimes take stress knowingly or unknowingly. It is a natural phenomenon. It is nothing but a kind of pressure which is excreted on an individual. So, it very important to have stress free environment in present generation for sustainable business. Supporting your employees through their stress can ultimately make them more engaged and motivated to do their work. The national institute for occupational safety and health defines job stress as the harmful physical and emotional response that occur when the requirement of a job does not match capabilities, resources or needs needed for the workers. Job stress can lead to several problems including illness and injury for employers as well as higher in-service costs and cost productivity for employers.

Key words: Stress, environment, productivity, employers, business.

PAPER 148

WOMEN IN STEAM: A PERSPECTIVE OF PRESENT TRENDS, OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

Dr. Ramakrishna N Hegde¹ & Mr. Srinidhi Kukkila²

Professor & Head, Department of Automobile Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.

Email: rkhegderk@gmail.com

Assistant Professor, Department of Aeronautical Engineering, SIT Mangaluru.

Email: srinidhikukkila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the major contributors to education policies and curriculum choices in schools. STEAM has been mainly applied and addressed to the preschools, schools and predominantly in high schools. It has played a major role in the overall development of the students and nowadays, is being applied to the Higher Education Institutes (HEIs). The major drawback in the STEAM field is found out to be the discrimination of women in STEAM fields and it has led to a lot of negative effects on the society. The research focuses on the students' perspective of women in STEAM fields and a lot of discussions are done to understand the reasons behind the disparity. Both urban and rural backgrounds were considered for the discussion to understand the kind of support and equality, the learning environment and in the STEAM field professions. Many constraints for women in STEAM fields are taken into consideration like lack of equality, safety problems, financial constraints and pay gap with the male counterparts. Lately, there are some visible changes in the mindset of parents irrespective of different backgrounds. The curtains of old traditions and restrictions are slowly but definitely, are opening and the girls have the urge to learn, compete and to take responsibly even in unconventional branches of engineering like automobile and aeronautical. But still, a lot of women graduate in STEAM fields but fail to make a successful career out of it. A lot of statistical data from PISA is also taken into consideration for the research.

Keywords: STEAM, disparity, HEI.

PAPER 149

A STUDY ON EMERGING TRENDS IN ACADEMIC STAFFS AND AWARDED RESEARCH DEGREES IN INDIA

Priti K Rao¹

Assistant professor, Government First Grade College, Punjalakatte,
E-mail pritijeevan@gmail.com , Ph.: 9535583800

ABSTRACT

India is one among the oldest educational system in the world became the greatest legacy of knowledge. The educational delivery is done through schools, colleges, higher education institutions, Universities, Research Institutes with its highest rostrum of learning. Knowledge, information and new ideas will drive the country towards economic exploration. The formal education provides a solid platform to the aspiring students to become competent in meeting global aspirations. Educational system is deemed to be the community of teachers, scholars and other stakeholders. Every year, millions of students enter the threshold of higher education for their graduation, post graduation and research degrees. Governance of Higher education is the shared responsibility of both Central and State Governments. The quality of higher education is determined by the standards prescribed by the regulatory authorities including University Grants Commission (UGC), All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) and National Council for Technical Education (NCTE). Efforts are in the pipeline to create Higher Education Evaluation and Regulatory Authority (HEERA) and Higher Education Regulatory Council (HERC) for enriching quality of higher. The paper describe regulations on appointment and promotion of teachers highlighting about minimum qualification, pay, superannuation, recruitment, selection, leave, working days and code of professional ethics for the academic staffs. The paper reveals about the latest regulations governing the M. Phil and Ph.D. degrees on the issues connected to admission, allocation of research supervisors, course work, research advisory committee, evaluation, award and depository.

Key Words: Knowledge, Higher Education, Governance, Standards, Appointment, M. Phil & Ph.D., Economic Growth.

PAPER 150

DIGITAL BANKING – “AS A TIME SAVER TOOL”

Mrs.Mallika¹

Assistant Professor, Department of MBA;Srinivas Institute of Technology,
Valachil Mangalore, Karnataka, India, ;Email: mallikatian@gmail.com
Ph.: 9632503652

ABSTRACT

Digital banking or digitalisation is moving online of all the traditional banking activities and transactions that initially were only available to customers under the bank roof. This includes activities like money deposits, withdrawals and Transfers (E-Payments).It is a part of the broader context for the move to online baking, where banking services are delivered over the internet. The shift from traditional to digital banking has been gradual and remains on-going. In the old days, banking used to be a time-consuming business, where the basic transactions like cash deposits and withdrawals were taking long time, the customers had to stand in a queue to avail the facility. Everything was done under the token system. All that thankfully, is a thing of the past now after transition all banking activities became Hassel free. Moreover, going digital allows you the perfect opportunity to enjoy paperless banking experience, where you no longer need to keep track of your transactions or banking history through physical documents. With Digital Banking, you can transact with higher speed, ease and convenience. It served as “Time saver tool” for customers as well as for employees. Most banks in the country offer Digital Banking Services today, and these have become an integral part offer E-Banking services today, the meaning true Digitalisation is transformation. Digital Banking has drastically changed the way banks and customers interact with one another. And in a booming technological and financial economy like India, more and more people are being connected to Digital Banking Platforms with each passing day.

Key Words: Banking, E-Payment, Digitalisation, E- Banking, Customers, Employees.

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SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN MANGALORE CITY: A STUDY TOWARDS SWACCH BHARAT MISSION

Dr. Prasanna Kumar M. G¹, Dr. Ramyashree M. G.²

¹Faculty Member, Commerce Department, Besant Women's College,
Mangalore-575003; M:09945299678

²Faculty Member, Commerce Department, Government First Grade College,
Kumta-581343; M:09481019954

ABSTRACT

Solid waste management is a challenge for the cities' authorities in developing countries mainly due to the increasing generation of waste, the burden posed on the municipal budget as a result of the high costs associated to its management, the lack of understanding over a diversity of factors that affect the different stages of waste management and linkages necessary to enable the entire handling system functioning. This study impressed and towards Swacch Bharat Mission how stakeholders actively involved in action. An analysis of literature on the work done and reported mainly in publications from 2015 to 2019, related to waste management in developing countries, showed that few articles give quantitative information. The objective of this research was to determine the stakeholders' action/behavior that has a role in the waste management process and to analyze influential factors on the system, in Mangalore city area. A combination of methods was used in this study in order to assess the stakeholders and the factors influencing the performance of waste management in the cities. Data was collected from scientific literature, existing data bases, observations made during visits to city areas, structured interviews with relevant professionals, exercises provided to participants in workshops and a questionnaire applied to stakeholders.

Keywords: Swacch Bharat Mission, Waste Management, Diversity of factors, Stakeholders' action.

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E-BANKING AND GREEN BANKING: A STUDY IN DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT

Dr. Raghavendra B¹, Mrs Madhura K²

¹Lecturer, Dept. of P.G. Studies in Commerce, Besant Women's College, Kodialbail,
Mangaluru -575003. raghavendrabadiar@gmail.com

²Research Scholar Dept. of PG Studies & Research in Economics, Mangalore University,
Mangalagangothri -574199, Mb: 8971428033

ABSTRACT

Green Banking is a new phenomenon which is creating a buzz in the financial world. Green banking means to promote environment friendly practices and to reduce the carbon footprint from banking operations. However, the majority of the respondents rated positively to the efficiency of green projects/CSR activities, which implemented by green banks in Dakshina Kannada district. Regarding the effective green banking strategies, banker seems that reducing paper saving is the appropriate strategy followed by the sponsoring tree plantations. A survey was conducted on green banking which included the banks and well as the customers of the banks to know the various green banking initiatives taken up by the banks and the customer's knowledge on green banking activities adopted by the banks.

Keywords: Green Banking, E-banking, Green Banking Strategy

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IMPACT OF DIGITISATION ON RURAL BANKING IN DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT

Harinakshi¹, Ashitha² & Mithun Chandra R. K³

¹Faculty, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru, Karnataka, Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

²Faculty, Department of Commerce, Shree Gokarnanatheshwara College,
Mangaluru, Karnataka,

³Faculty, Department of MBA (IB), University Evening College, Mangaluru, Karnataka,
Email: mithoonchandra008@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Today's generation is much more dedicated towards digital planet. The digital India program was established with the view of transforming the country along with the list of developed nations. Digitalisation can be viewed as a truly ground-breaking initiative to re-engineer our country into digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. The modern banks are more privileged with all the digi-infrastructure and services, than the traditional banks operating then. Rural areas are no longer limited to illiterates or unawares, recent decade has recorded the significant growth in the banking sector with the introduction of various govt schemes in the rural economy. The view of public towards banks has changed significantly in terms of banking services, segment banking and community based financial inclusion program pooled together with modern solutions. The banking sector in India has a notable growth but due to lack of assistance and urge towards digitalisation the bucolic areas are those which are least supported with basic amenities, infrastructure and resources, thus making it hinder to establish the digital platform in the planned manner. This research is an attempt to understand the challenges faced by rural people with digitalisation and banking services.

Keywords: Digitalisation, Digi-Infrastructure, Banking, Rural Area, Government Initiative.

PAPER 154

IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATION AND AWARENESS –A STUDY OF COMPUTER INDUCED HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG COMPUTER PROFESSIONALS

Mrs. Jayalaxmi¹

Lecturer, Department of Commerce and Management, Poornaprajna College Udipi
Mob: 9964282714, Email: jaibhat72@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Information Technology is an important emerging sector of the Indian Economy. It has become indispensable part of the global world that keeps us connected. Efficient utilization of skilled labour forces in the Information Technology sector can help an economy achieve a rapid pace of economic growth. To propel this growth IT professionals spend massive amounts of time in front of the computer screen involving themselves in monitoring networks, configuring application or managing technology projects. Overtime work at the computer puts their health in danger. This study throws light on the various computer induced health problems, their causes and precautionary measures to overcome the problems. Musculoskeletal problems, eye and vision related problems, repetitive stress injury, stress disorders, headache etc. are the most common complaints of regular computer users. Lack of physical exercises, rest breaks, improper sitting posture, poor lighting, complicated software, bad glare or flickering image etc. are the main causes for computer induced diseases. Information are collected from 100 computer professionals working in different jobs such as data entry, clerical dept. etc., through a well-structured questionnaire and personal interview. Simple statistical tools such as averages and percentages are applied for testing the hypothesis and for analysis. The study reveals that many computer professionals are aware of these causes but, with over work load and work pressure they find it difficult to cope with these problems. However, unless they take care of their health, they cannot work efficiently. The management of the organisations also should focus on these problems and enforce suitable preventive measures.

Key Words: Information Technology, skilled labour force, Overtime work, Musculoskeletal Problems

PAPER 155

MARKET ANALYSIS OF EV'S INDUSTRY IN INDIA- A CASE STUDY FROM CUSTOMER PERSPECTIVE

Sajan M¹

Lecturer, Department of Post -Graduate studies and Research in Commerce,
Govinda dasa College Surathkal.

Email:sajanachaya916@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

“Global warming”, “Greenpeace” and “ozone layer depletion are the emerging topics which are discussed often. As human beings are more aggressive towards consumption and production somewhere we are harming our environment. Evidentially we have witnessed many natural calamities now a day. These free resources are the gift of nature which we should care about. To protect the scared resources government and houses are coming up with many schemes and eco-friendly products, today green products have emerging market and many are aiming at the same. Most of the eco-friendly products and services have a wide market, it has been boosted by industry as well as consumer side. But when it comes to EV'S neither business houses nor consumers are impressive. Of course both are dependent on each. Air pollution is the one of the emerging issue. Major cause for the air pollution is automobile industry. Extent to which the automobile industry grow extent to that environment is harming. We should avoid fuel cars with strong reason, because gases that are emitted out from the exhaust on automobile contain various poisonous gasses like carbon monoxide and nitrous oxide. These two can block sun-rays and these pollutants will harm the living beings, destroy plants and this is the core reason for the depletion of ozone lasers. Though India is looking forward to reduce 37% emission by 2030 and allowing only Ev's from 2023 onwards, they failed to create infrastructure which it required. Even business houses are not analysed the customer perspective in depth. So this case study is all about the analysis of EV market and also emphasis on the customer perspective towards the same.

Key words: Ev's (Electrical Vehicles), green marketing, ozone depletion,

PAPER 156

MICRO FINANCE SCHEMES OF SKDRDP – A CASE STUDY OF SELECTED MEMBERS OF SHGS

Praveena D¹, Dr. Shrinivasa Mayya.D², Dr. Ajoy S Joseph³

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of MBA, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Valachil, Mangaluru; pravi1988@gmail.com

²Principal, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Mangaluru. srimayya@gmail.com

³HOD, Dept. of MBA, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Mangaluru. ajoysj@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In India, the history of Micro Finance, rural credit, and poverty alleviation are inextricably interwoven. The forces and compulsions that shaped the initiatives in this area are best understood in context of state and banking policy over a time. The Government of India has expressed a strong commitment to Micro Finance as a means of reducing poverty. Micro finance in general is a practice of providing the poor with credit, savings and insurance facilities to set up or to expand Income generating activities relating to agriculture and its allied activities and non-farm sector and thereby is poverty reducing mechanism. Micro finance is needed a very traditional and familiar form of business. Microfinance has turned out to be useful development assistance product. It reached millions of poor people and emerged as a revolution. Shri Kshetra Dharmasthala Rural Development Project (SKDRDP) is a brilliant example of a truly innovative microfinance institution. Founded in 1991 as a charitable trust promoted by Dr. D Veerendra Heggade, SKDRDP concentrates on the empowerment of rural women through self-help groups (SHGs) on the lines of Joint Liability Groups (JLBs), and provides infrastructure and finance through micro credit for the rural people. Presently SKDRDP is actively involved in implementing the financial inclusion plan of the government of India by working as Banking Correspondent and Business Facilitator (BC and BF) in all the areas of its operation. Under the programme SKDRDP is promoting Self Help groups enabling the poor people in the remote villages to access banking facilities at their door steps. SKDRDP is BC and BF to State Bank of India, Union Bank of India, Canara Bank, Corporation bank, IDBI bank, Pragathi Krishna Grameen Bank, Bank of Baroda and Syndicate Bank. The paper is an attempt to understand the stories of SHGs members after taking micro finance service from SKDRDP. The current study helps the researcher to understand the experience of SHGs members relating to SKDRDP Micro Finance Schemes.

Keywords: Self Help Groups, Micro Finance, Business Correspondent, Business Facilitator

PAPER 157

RUPEE VALUE DEPRECIATION: CAUSES AND REMEDIES

Dr.Radhakrishnan¹, Arjun, KR²

¹Associate Professor, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Mangalore.

²Asst Professor, SNES IMSAR, Calicut, Kerala 673571

ABSTRACT

This paper will analyze the trends of the Indian currency depreciation against the dollar from 1947. It is viewed that in the year 1947: 1 US\$ = 1.00 INR which became 1 US\$ = 70.80 INR in the year 2019. The paper also tells the theoretical back ground of the methods of fixing currency value such as fixed rate system, floating rate system and demand and supply mechanism. This paper underscore current account deficit is the major reason for rupee value depreciation. The paper also discuss the terms like rupee devaluation, appreciation, currency market, trade balance and FDI. The data collected for the study is secondary one which is mainly from RBI website. The study concluded that the rupee value is depreciating year by year against dollar. At the end of the paper it is discussed the reasons for rupee value depreciation and also suggest remedial measures to arrest rupee value depreciation. Economy is severely affected by the currency depreciation and people are affected due to drastic change in their monthly budget. Currency depreciation effects inflation which results too much money chasing too few goods. Depreciation refers to a fall in the value of the domestic currency which is caused by the demand for foreign currency exceeding its supply in the market. A decrease in the value of a currency with respect to other currencies means that the depreciated currency is worth fewer units of some other currency. The demand and supply forces in the currency market determine the price of each currency. If the government or RBI fixes the exchange rate of a currency such a system is called the Fixed Rate system. Most of the countries including India changed to Floating Rate System where currency market determines the value of a currency. One of the major reasons for rupee value depreciation is high Current Account Deficit. CAD occurs when a country's total imports of goods, services and transfers are greater than the country's total export of goods, services and transfers. Unreasonably high Imports Of gold, Import of crude oil, Very small manufacturing base of India, etc are all contributing to the rupee value depreciation. India's regulators has to toughen rules for derivatives trading in currency markets, RBI has to tighten liquidity; Relaxing of FDI, Import Duty on Gold to be increased, capital control etc are the measures to be undertaken for safe guarding Indian currency.

Keywords: Rupee value, depreciation, RBI, devaluation

PAPER 158

AN ANALYSIS OF INNOVATIONS IN INDIAN TEACHER EDUCATION AS PROPOSED IN DRAFT NATIONAL EDUCATIONAL POLICY 2019

Dr. P. S. Aithal* & Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal**

*College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, India

**Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

India, being population rich but still developing country can prosper only by effective implementation of quality education at school and college level. To implement an accelerated effective quality education in the entire country, developing qualified and updated teachers with current knowledge and skills is essential by providing systematic and innovative teachers education. In this regard, the National Educational Policy proposal has suggested a great step of providing an integrated four years bachelor degree in education as a compulsory qualification requirement to become a teacher at any stage of school education. In this paper, we have studied the new School education model proposed by NEP-2019 and analysed the new curricular and pedagogical structure for school education. The competency levels required for the teachers to implement the reforms as per the NEP 2019 proposal are discussed. The new innovative suggestions given in the proposal to redefine teacher education in the country for all the levels of school teaching from 5 years Foundation stage to 4 years Secondary stage including the minimum qualification for the teachers and to empower the teachers to be competent to develop global quality students are also analysed. Various improvements suggested in NEP proposal for liberalization of undergraduate integrated B.Ed. programme are also listed along with possible implications on the quality of teachers education. A focus group method based ABCD analysis framework is used to list advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the innovations proposed in the teachers education part of the proposal and finally, some recommendations are given to the effective implementation of the proposal.

Keywords : Teacher education, National Educational Policy, Quality of School education, Innovations in teacher training, ABCD analysis.

PAPER 159

EDUCATION, RESEARCH, AND EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCE GRADUATES – A SYSTEMATIC EXPLORATIVE STUDY

Architha Aithal¹ & Dr. P. S. Aithal²

¹Fifth year Pharm. D. Student, Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Valachil,
Mangalore – 574143, INDIA

²Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, M
angalore – 575 001, INDIA
E-mail : psaital@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical Science is a relatively new discipline and is concerned with fostering a multi-disciplinary approach towards the study of exciting new developments in the chemical, biological and biomedical science areas focusing upon the biochemistry, pharmacology, design, methods of analysis and delivery of pharmaceutical substances to develop effective drugs to cure various diseases of living beings. In this paper, we have explored the various education opportunities at UG, PG, and research level, in different continents of the globe, and the type of research opportunities for the prospective research graduates in these countries. The paper discusses and analyses the global employment opportunities and constraints in different countries for securing employment for graduates, postgraduates, and research graduates with the field of specialization. The paper also suggests some of the improvements and advances required in the curriculum of Indian curriculum for these courses to make them globally competitive in terms of utilizing opportunities effectively with transferred course credits.

Keywords : Pharmaceutical Science, Pharmacy graduates, Global opportunities, Pharmacy education, Pharmacy research.

PAPER 160

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AT UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL & ITS IMPORTANCE IN DEVELOPING A RESPONSIBLE CITIZEN

Dr. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal

Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail : shubhraaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

It is well known that the environment which we live in is the basic teacher to every human being and has full control over him for sustainable basic living, safety, and comfortable life. A human being will become educated only if he studies his environment and works for its sustainability. By understanding this reality, higher education system adopted Environmental studies as one of the compulsory subjects even in undergraduate courses. Even if a student studies his environment from school days, further inclusion of this subject as a compulsory paper is mainly to remind its importance of preserving a sustainable environment for human beings against all technological progress. Now higher education institutions have two responsibilities: (i) further educating students on sustainable environment, (ii) involving them in various programs to be conducted by the institution on environmental sustainability. In this paper, the objective of environmental education from students point of view, how environmental education can be re-defined as green education, difference between environmental and green education, concept and curriculum for green environmental education, ABCD analysis of Green environmental education, UGC model curriculum for environmental education, comparative study on UGC Environmental curriculum and Green Environmental education, and Possible impact of Green environmental education on youth & society are proposed and discussed.

Keywords : Environmental education, Green education, Green education curriculum, Environmental sustainability.

PAPER 161

HOW SMART CITY CAN PROVIDE SMART SOLUTIONS TO SENIOR CITIZENS – A FUTURISTIC ANALYSIS

P. S. Aithal

College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The concept of Smart Cities is developed to promote cities that provide core infrastructure and give a decent quality of life to its citizens, a clean and sustainable environment and application of 'Smart' Solutions to day to day problems. Smart cities use data and technology to create efficiencies, improve sustainability, create economic development, and enhance the quality of life factors for people living and working in the city. It also means that the city has a smarter infrastructure for providing and managing Nutritious food, Potable water, Systematic environmentally harmless transportation, Green energy production & usage, quality education, business, quality health services, etc. In this paper, we have initially discussed the essential infrastructure and facilities required for senior citizens from smart city solutions point of view and to develop a model to plan and provide essential infrastructure requirements for senior citizens for their day-to-day needs and how the use of digital technology and solutions can help such old-age people until their end of life. These suggestions support to the realization of a smart city with innovative programs to senior citizens of the country.

Keywords: Smart city, Essential infrastructure for smart city, Smart solutions using technology, Smart city solutions for senior citizens.

PAPER 162

HOW TO CREATE EMOTIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS : SOME CASE BASED ILLUSTRATIONS

P. S. Aithal

*College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Infrastructure requirements for brand excellence in Higher educational institutions include Physical infrastructure, Digital infrastructure, Innovative academic infrastructure, Intellectual property right infrastructure, Emotional infrastructure, and Networked infrastructure. Emotional infrastructure, being intangible, is difficult to create and maintain. Emotional infrastructure requires creating a sense of belongingness with the organization by all stakeholders. It is a process of developing a positive attitude towards the HEI for its stakeholders. Since, attitude and behaviour of a stakeholder depend on feelings, which depends on belief, which further depends on his previous and present environment, HEIs should focus on developing a conducive environment for education and research. The major elements of emotional infrastructure include Acceptable leader as role-model, Trust among stakeholders and outsiders, Institutional values (Core values), Institutional Rituals & Tradition, Create rich communication channels, Alternative strategy & Support network, Set vision in every student, Safety & Security, Search for proximity (Local friends. Local food, local culture), Comfortability but need not luxury, Legacy of the system, Respect & perception about organization, Openness in terms of information, Ability of the institution to fulfil the promises, and Accountability measures are considered as some emotional infrastructure components. In this paper, we have analysed these components and discussed how they can contribute directly and indirectly on the emotional infrastructure of the higher educational institutions. The arguments are supported by some case based illustrations by analysing & comparing the strategies of 20 top universities in the United States of America.

Keywords: Accelerated growth & development of HIEs, Infrastructure for brand excellence, Emotional infrastructure, Components of emotional infrastructure.

PAPER 163

INDUSTRY-INSTITUTE INTERACTION: SOME NEW PERSPECTIVES

P. S. Aithal

College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

There are infinite amount of innovation opportunities in higher education service model due to the fact that the expectations of higher education aspirants are changing. In this paper, we made an attempt, in the form of a model, how HEIs and industries in the society can collaborate to exchange knowledge and skills of their stakeholders. Since networking with stakeholders is a very important infrastructure of HEIs, they can prosper and develop as one among world leader in education through such effort. The network collaborative model contains a systematic plan of involving industry experts in HEIs teaching-learning process. Starting from planning the courses and the subjects, developing the curriculum, collaborative training, collective evaluation, and offering employment, industry-institute interaction has the opportunity to synergize. Connecting with the industry, with the alumni, with other higher education & research institutions creates synergy for collective development. By means of properly planned collaborations and implementing the objective of collaboration leads to a positive-sum game. Organizations which focus on effective networking can encash more opportunities for self and mutual developments along with their brand image. Collaboration and partnership with local, national, and global agencies can be used to support other infrastructures like innovative academic infrastructure, intellectual property infrastructure, and emotional infrastructure. In this paper, we have also identified and analysed various components of networked infrastructure required for a university using focus group discussion and found the optimum level of such networked infrastructure to be utilized to develop universities to the world class level.

Keywords : HEIs, Universities, Networked infrastructure, Industry-institute interaction, Alumni network, Employability skills

INFORMATION ASSURANCE: EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM AT BACHELORS LEVEL—AN INTERNATIONAL LOOK

P. K. Paul¹, & P. S. Aithal²

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Security has become an important name these days for different reasons. Today organizations and institutions are engaged in information affairs and in which IT Components become important and valuable. Worldwide manpower requirement in this field is highly solicited, different educational institutions viz. colleges, universities, technical institutions are doing well in this context. There are different areas closely related to Information Assurance such as Cyber Security, Information Security, IT Security, Computer Security, etc. Information Assurance is a broader version of IT Security which talks and deals with both manual and computational security related affairs. Information Assurance moreover comes with the topics in policy designing for healthy information systems designing and development. The framework, guidelines for sustainable information systems designing is also part of Information Assurance. Initially different universities have been started Information Assurance program at Doctoral level and in recent past apart from Masters degrees few have started Bachelors as well. This paper has highlighted the basics of Information Assurance and mainly the available programs of Information Assurance at Bachelors degree level. Paper mentioned the emerging areas and topic of interest as well. It is noted that few universities offer the areas as a full-fledged manner and few as a specialization within a broader domain.

Keywords : Information Assurance, IT Security, Security Education, Information Privacy, Educational Development, Information Science, BS Information Assurance, Cyber Security

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INFORMATION ASSURANCE: *THE WAY TO INTRODUCE IN UG EDUCATION IN INDIA—A POLICY FRAMEWORK*

P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal² A. Bhimali³

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

³Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

²Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Information Assurance (IA) is an important and emerging concept related to information security. Information Assurance (IA) is also required for managing and implementing information security related policies. There are two types of security; firstly traditional security and another one is computational security. Traditional security is about the manual documents and content related security whereas; computational security is deals with various components based security viz. Network Security, Web Security, Database Technology, Multimedia Technology, etc. Information Security is very close with the Information Assurance (IA), as it also deals with Manual and Computational areas; though it additionally deals with the policies, regulation, and guidelines of security. Many universities internationally offered degrees and academic programs on Information Assurance (IA) and allied fields viz. Information Assurance and Security, IT and Information Assurance, Computer and Information Assurance, IT Security and Assurance, etc. The degrees are offered at different levels viz. Bachelors Degree, Masters Degree, PG Diploma, PG Certificate, Doctoral, and Post Doctoral level; there are different universities. In India, a very few universities have started security related degrees and most of these are offering traditional nomenclatures. There are potentialities to offer the degrees at UG levels with little initiatives and policies. This paper talks about such potentialities and the situation in detail.

Keywords : Information Assurance, UG Education, Indian Higher Education, Research Degrees, IT Security

PAPER 166

INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS THEORIES AND TOURISM INDUSTRY PARADOX

P. S. Aithal* & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal**

*College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

**Faculty, College of Engineering & Technology, Srinivas University, Mangalore, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Despite the fact that international business is a positive sum game where all the participant countries are gainers, many international business theories propose the countries strategy should be to increase export and decrease import to have a stable balance of trade and currency exchange rate. If a country's trade account is such that when exports are not equal to imports, there is relatively more demand or supply for its currency, which influences the price of that currency on the world market. Many developing countries focus on increasing their export and decreasing their import to reduce their trade deficit and have positive economic growth. Thus based on international trade theories, a country should focus on increasing its exports and decreasing the imports to have a stable economic growth, stable exchange rate of its currency and to control its trade deficit. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the export and import strategies of the developing countries and to find a way to maintain the balance of trade. While doing so, we have surprisingly observed a paradox that though in many industry sectors, the export of commodities contributes to increasing the demand for the country currency and imports of commodities contribute to decreasing the demand for the country currency, but in tourism industry sector reverse is found true. The paper explains how the tourism industry encourages a country to increase import of people to it and decrease export of people to other countries. The findings of this research suggest that (1) Tourism is a industry sector where the paradox against the common understanding on import and export strategy of countries is observed, (2) In tourism industry, trade deficit can be minimized by importing more external people than exporting internal people to other countries as tourists, and (3) Developing countries should focus on improving Tourism industry based business in the country.

Keywords : International Business, Balance of trade, Trade deficit, Tourism paradox.

M.TECH. IN IT AND COMPUTING AREAS WITH POSSIBILITIES IN INFORMATION ASSURANCE SPECIALIZATIONS: *THE INNOVATIVE FRONTIERS IN EDUCATION*

P. K. Paul¹, A. Bhumali², P. S. Aithal³, & R. Rajesh⁴

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal,
India

²Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, West Bengal, India

³Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

⁴Principal, Rohini College of Engineering and Technology, TN, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Information Technology is an important domain within Applied Science and Technology responsible for information affairs leading to collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination. Information Technology consists of different components and among these important are web technology, network technology, database technology, multimedia technology, etc. As far as Information Assurance is concerned, this falls under the area of network technology mainly within IT and partially database and web technology. The IT and Computing education in India offered in two platforms, in one it is the area of Science (Applied) and in another, it falls under the area of Technology/ Engineering. The IT programs come with BSc/MSc and BTech and MTech nomenclature. However, the BTech and MTech are also offered as BE/ME Degree in some respect. In the recent past, many universities in India have started the IT and Computing programs with specialization or Honors or Major. The importance of Information Assurance and Cyber Security is increasing; this paper is proposed about the Information Assurance major with MTech-IT and allied degrees keeping in mind Indian need in industry and policies of higher educational institutions. Paper highlighted the model curricula in this context as well. As a whole, complete SWOT has been mapped of Information Assurance programs in MTech-IT and allied fields.

Keywords : Information Assurance, IT Security, Information Management, Systems Management, MTech Information Technology (Information Assurance), Indian Higher Education, HEIs, India

NETWORK SECURITY: THREAT MANAGEMENT

P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²

¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Security these days is a very important issue and required in all the organizations and institutions irrespective of nature. Computer Security is closely associated with Information Technology Security. Network Security is a vast world and it has a close connection with the Database Security, Web Security, and Cloud Security. Network Security is required due to various issues viz. vulnerabilities, malware, spyware, ransomware, Trojan, virus, phishing, denial of services, web shells, etc. There are different threat management defending systems viz. computer access control, application security, authentication, authorization, firewall, intrusion detection systems, mobile secure gateway, etc. Day by day the intelligence system is developing and as a result, threat is also increasing. Corporate world, industries are employing different smart devices and there threat management systems are highly required. This is a basic paper on Network Security and talks about the aspects of Network Security with special reference to the threat management. This paper deals with the fundamentals affairs of threat management as well.

Keywords : IT Management, Information Assurance, Threat Management, Network Security, IT Security Policies

PAPER 169

OUT OF MIND, OUT OF SIGHT: A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF SOCIAL INITIATIVES TO CURB MIGRATION IN UTTARAKHAND

Dr. Amanjeet Singh Sethi,

Assistant Professor, FCBM, Amrapali Group of Institutes, Haldwani, Uttarakhand

E-mail : amanjeetsinghsethi@gmail.com

Contact: +91983741525

amanjeetsinghsethi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The existing state of affairs in the hill and rural areas of Uttarakhand is very dangerous as the state has more than fifteen hundred ghost villages and this number is growing day in day out. The villagers from these places are moving out to plain areas within and outside the state mainly for employment opportunities and a variety of other reasons also contributes to this unfortunate process. Comprehending the urgency of the situation several individuals, non government organizations, self help groups and the different agencies of the government have started a number of initiatives to curb this serious issue of migration. This research article makes an effort to study the circumstances, current scenario and predominant causes in relation to migration for the state of Uttarakhand. The research article mainly focus on some of the successful cases of social initiatives attempted for helping to create a viable environment so that people do not have to migrate out of their home in search for facilities. The article concludes that such kind of social initiatives have the potential to stop the process of migration and to initiate reverse migration in the state but still a fair distance has to be covered to make this vision palpable.

KEYWORDS: Migration, Employment, Social, Hills, Rural, Entrepreneurs, Infrastructure, Uttarakhand, Philanthropists.

PAPER 170

RESEARCH & FUNDING AGENCIES FOR MEDICAL PROFESSIONALS

Dr. Edwin Dias

Professor and HOD, Department of Paediatrics,
Srinivas Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Mangalore, India

E-mail : dredwindias@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Research and Academics are complementary to each other. They arouse interest in each other and doing research does not have any negative effect on the academicability. Research can offer significant information about disease trends and risk factors, interventions or outcomes of treatment, public health issues, functional abilities, patterns of care, and health care costs. Clinical research is a branch of healthcare science that determines the safety and efficacy of medications, devices, diagnostic products and treatment regimens intended for human use for prevention, treatment, diagnosis or for relieving symptoms of a disease. Tracking clinical experience during drug administration is important for recognizing comparative rare adverse effects and for determining the effectiveness in different populations or in various conditions. It is also vital to record and assess experience in clinical practice in order to develop evidence-based guidelines for best practices and to ensure high-quality patient care. These forms of health research have led to significant discoveries, the development of new therapies, and a remarkable improvement in health care and public health issues. Economists have found that groundbreaking medical research can have an enormous positive impact on human health and longevity resulting in increased productivity of the population which in turn contributes greatly to the national economy; in addition to the individual benefits of improved health. As far as research in medical sciences is concerned, India scored 12th position among the productive countries of the world in medicine during 1999–2008 with a mere 1.6% share. The main deterrent being lack of funding, well paid jobs in the research sector. In this presentation, I have made an attempt to address the benefits of doing research and various funding agencies.

KEYWORDS: Research, Medical Professionals, Funding, Benefits.

PAPER 171

REVISITING PHILOSOPHY OF STUDENT LEARNING

Dr. Suresh Kumar P. M.

Professor, Department of Sociology and Social Work,

Christ University, Bangalore - 560029, INDIA

E-mail: sureshpmsk@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Over the years the focus in teaching-learning has been shifting from students as objects of learning to subjects of learning, to recipients of learning, and customers of learning. A further shift that is taking place in Higher Education is to view students as partners in learning. In the paternalistic view, knowledge is available in the form of books and resources and the teacher is not inventing anything new. Since students by themselves are unable to take it the teachers help them with this. But such a perspective fails to address the behavioral angle of the entire process governing the interaction and ignores the need for a philosophy which would better understand the student involvement. Critical assumptions which are central to the philosophy of student behavior namely 'Theory X' and 'Theory Y' modeled after the organizational behavior theories portray two extremes, either students are inherently lazy and must be forced to learn, examinations are perceived as threats etc or that students are interested and given required motivation they would learn. Viewing of teaching-learning as a partnership process is still ahead of these, guided by shared understanding of 'what we know is little', 'what we don't know is more' and 'what we ought to know is much more'. That students are reservoir of unlimited freedom by virtue of their age, developmental stage, socialization; peer group influence and adolescent characteristic etc and the teacher do need to renegotiate their behavior so as to conform with forces of social control, and expected behavioral and institutional norms. It is here that partnership process start. This paper discusses the variety of approaches and aims to explore the philosophical base for partnership based learning in Higher Education.

Keywords : Teaching-Learning process, Higher Education, Partnership based learning.

PAPER 172

SECURING MULTITENANCY WITHIN IAAS DEPLOYMENT MODEL UNDER OPENSTACK

Dr. K. SAI MANOJ¹, Ms. K. Mrudula², Mrs. G. Maanasa³, & Dr. K. Phani Srinivas⁴

¹CEO, Innogecks Technologies and Amrita Sai Institute of Science and
Technology/Reviewer, Vijayawada, AP, India

²Director, Innogecks technologies, Vijayawada, AP, India

³Research Scholar, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur Dist, AP, India

⁴Director R&D, Innogecks Technologies and Amrita Sai Institute of Science and
Technology, Vijayawada, AP, India

ABSTRACT

Modern days, cloud computing playing an important role in both academic research as well as in IT Industries. There are huge numbers of cloud service providers offer various computing resources in many forms. In this research, we investigated clearly in the aspect of Infrastructure-as-a-service facing the problem of security especially when multiple users are in the same virtual machine. Many Developers are focusing on research related to cloud security. Still, there are so many issues in the situation of service over the cloud. Also, there is an issue in the research survey pointing to Multitenancy. Our research as per the industrial standards mainly concentrated on securing the IaaS which a very important requirement for cloud computing. In this research, we used cloud computing software such as OpenStack. It is a very popular software in the deployment of infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) Solutions. In this research article, we investigated pointing to the security related to Infrastructure as- a Service which is facing security problem especially in the case of multiple users. Especially, when multiple users have the same virtual machine and therefore need to be secured. We investigated this problem in the new dimension such as with security-based components.

Keywords: Multitenancy, IaaS, virtual machine, OpenStack.

PAPER 173

STRATEGIES FOR COMPETENCY BUILDING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Dr. Suresh Kumar P. M.

Department of Sociology and Social Work, Christ University, Bangalore - 560029, INDIA
E-mail: sureshpmsk@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Higher education institutions are critical focal points which transform youth into economically productive and socially useful citizens. This could be realised if they provide total learning experience which goes into developing competencies. Apart from reorienting main stream academic activities, value additions, certification programs, skill enhancement courses, competency gaining activities are being increasingly incorporated to enrich student learning experience. **Three main factors** play a role in developing competency. One for example is the **education and training** that is the primary function of higher education. Side by side there is the **hidden curriculum**, such for example, the entire set of factors which together may be called campus atmosphere – peer interaction, mentor influence, co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, sports and games, programs and activities, opportunities leading to discovery of potentials and development of self. Finally the **personal attributes** such as punctuality, discipline, commitment etc. which are largely shaped by ones early life experiences and institutional norms of the organisation of employment. All the three contribute to the holistic ‘performance competency’. Education and training, and hidden curriculum are two sides of the same coin. One which allows formal learning and the other informal and experiential. This paper on challenges for competency building aims to find out the strategies that could be employed by higher education institutions in developing competency among the students.

Keywords: Competency building, Hidden curriculum, Performance competency.

PAPER 174

THE ROLE OF POLICE IN THE CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM OF BANGLADESH: NEED FOR REFORMATION

Sunjida Islam

Department of Law, Rajshahi Science and Technology University,
Natore, Rajshahi, Bangladesh

E-mail : sunjidaislam199320@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Police and their functions are very important in criminology. Because it is the principal duty of the police to arrest criminals and conduct them until the conclusion of trial for preventing crime. Police are legally authorized to use force and other means of coercion to execute public and social order. The basic knowledge of crime and criminology is must for the police and that's why almost in every country of the world has a criminology division for police. And police are manually trained for the knowledge of criminology. It is true that an honest, sincere and effective police force can ensure a happy and peaceful society. Although it is not possible for the police to reduce crime from society completely but it can be controlled and retained in a satisfactory stage. Otherwise, trick, corrupted, unlettered and disingenuous police force can give facilities to the criminals and make the life of the general citizens miserable. This study has an assertion and provided some recommendations to the knowledge of criminology for police and to reform the police system in Bangladesh. This article provides strategic policy guidance for the police personnel.

Keywords: Police, Crime, Criminology, Reform and Justice.

PAPER 175

TRAINING EVALUATION MODEL-BETTER ALTERNATIVE TO SMILE SHEET IN MEASURING TRAINING EFFECTIVENESS

Dr. (Lt. Cdr) P. K. Suresh Kumar

Research Professor, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
India

E-mail : cdrsuresh@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

In the fast changing scenario of business, science and technology, the importance of training cannot be underestimated. Training is often one of an organization's biggest budget line items, nowadays (Wentworth, 2016). Institutions spend millions of dollars every year toward training. Yet, it is a debatable factor that, how far these trainings are effective in attaining their desired objective. Often, institutions resort to stereo-typed evaluation methods, which never measure the real training effectiveness. Even today, as described by Kirkpatrick D.L (1993), organizations often resort to "Smile sheet", where both trainers and trainees aim at a smiling outcome after the training. It is observed that, these smiling outcomes are never an indicator nor aid in attaining desirable targets for the trainees in their performance in practical fields. Thus, it can be said that in most cases, the training leads to wastage of precious resources like manpower, time and money. Instead, it is seen that a structured "Training Evaluation Model", evaluates the training with an inherent intention of achieving improvement in performance of trainees in their practical fields after certain time periods after training. In this study, twenty important Training Evaluation models are explained and compared. These models explore various factors of training and their effectiveness. After evaluating these models, this study recommends that, in order to achieve the desired outcome of training, for the trainees in their professional fields, it is desired to impart training and to measure its effectiveness by adopting any of the suitable "Training Evaluation Model" than resorting to "Smile sheet".

Keywords: Training, Training effectiveness. Smile sheets, Training evaluation models

PAPER 176

WORLD ECONOMIC RECESSION 2020 – PREDICTIONS & PRECAUTIONS

P. S. Aithal

College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the history, the world has witnessed many economic recessions and depressions due to different reasons including war and chronic health diseases. The year 2020 is predicted as the year of second global recession during the 21st century after 12 years gap with the first economic recession took place during 2008. One of the main reasons for first economic recession during the 21st century is due man-made mistakes in banking industry like sub-prime lending, growth of housing bubbles, easy credit conditions, weak and underwriting fraudulent practices, predatory lending, deregulation, increased debt burden, financial innovation & complexity, incorrect pricing of risk, Boom and collapse of the shadow banking system, use of wrong banking models, etc. But the predicted year 2020 recession is expected due to technological progress and mishandling of technological opportunities by political decision makers. In this study, we have elaborated the effect of technology and the inability of human beings to take the advantage of it due to their failure in forecasting & foreseeing the future. The main reasons responsible for the anticipated economic crises, the effect of such crises on the job market, and its possible consequences are discussed in detail. Finally, we also suggest, with illustrations, how the anticipated economic crisis can be controlled and minimized by taking precautions by the concerned governments and political leaders.

Keywords : World economic crises, First economic crises of the 21st century, Second economic crises of the 21st century, Man-made banking crises, Technology made job crises.

PAPER 177

Therapeutic Effect of Combined Treatment, Physiotherapy and Efficacy of Yoga, Meditation

Dr. Ajay Kumar,

College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University, Mangalore Karnataka, India

E-mail : drajay@srinivasgroup.com

ABSTRACT

Physiotherapy being a health care professional is a holistic approach that is concerned with maximizing quality of life by prevention, diagnosis, and management of disorders and pain to enhance the health and welfare of an individual and community at large. Yoga an art of healthy living is a spiritual science that is intended to bringing harmony between body and mind. The practice of Yoga increases mobility and motility of the body which is also the base of physiotherapy that helps to rehabilitate the movement and function of an affected individual. Within the scope of several existing similarities researchers, Physiotherapists and Yoga practitioners can obtain additional valuable ideas through the integration of underlying concepts of Physiotherapy and Yoga. The practice of yoga and its positive influence on an individual's mind and body, its complexity, multidimensional aspects their relationships can contribute towards the better practice of Physiotherapy. This conceptual enrichment can be a motivation to the physiotherapists who are well concerned about the overall health and betterment of their patients. In this research paper, an attempt is made to emphasize the importance of the integration of Physiotherapy and Yoga in clinical aspects. There is a wide range of types of contemplation, which can be formal situated or laying rehearses with a center (frequently the breath), and the casual routine with regards to care. It more often than not has a point of internal center, for instance, the breath, a word or express, or a sensation. It is a mindfulness state, where the psyche is quiet yet alert, which prepares our focus and consideration. Breathing is a piece of any training, it is essential to have the option to sit with the breath, without judgment and watch it under its standard oblivious control before bringing it into cognizant control if rehearsing breath adjustment. A typical misguided judgment is that you must most likely quit reasoning, this isn't the situation the psyche is intended to think however can end up over dynamic and our self-talk in our contemplations may not be useful. Our language is something we spread in instructing sessions. With training, we can figure out how to pick which musings to cooperate with and which to permit to cruise by, breaking the chain of regular contemplations and taking the regard for the present minute. Your contemplations can be viewed as like waves in a sea and can be seen with all their evolving tides.

Keywords: Physiotherapy, meditation, Yoga, Integration, Motivation.

PAPER 178

THE CHANGING DIMENSIONS OF LEGAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

Smt. Shubhalakshmi P.

Asst. Prof. of law-SDMLC, Mgllore; And Research Scholar
Karnataka State Law University Hubli

Abstract

Law is a subject which is present in every discipline in one or other way. So, it is said that ignorance of law is no excuse. Legal education is also one of the fastest growing educational sectors in India. Earlier the legal education was pursued in traditional manner and after completion of degree in law legal practice was the motive. But, reforms in the area of legal education started with the enactment of Indian Advocates Act 1961 wherein maintenance of uniform standard was monitored. The Bar Council of India maintains other procedures relating to legal education. The Legal research also got prominence and at the same time teaching pedagogy in law also changed a lot. Deductive and inductive methods of teaching and learning developed. Practical exposure in teaching also enhanced. Even in legal education, scientific method of imparting education was adopted. As further development, to impart legal education, private universities emerged and they are striving to improve the quality of legal education in India. Job and placement opportunities for law graduates also expanded and new openings are found. So, we can identify and locate lot many changes in legal education in India.

Key words: Changing Dimensions, Legal Education, India

PAPER 179

SECURING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE THROUGH CONTINUING EDUCATION FOR HUMAN RESOURCES IN AN ORGANISATION

A. Sathyavathi,

Research scholar at Mother Teresa university,
Attuvampatty, Kodaikanal.

ABSTRACT

A company's greatest assets are its employees and if competitive success is achieved through them, then the skills of those employees are critical. Consequently one of the most obvious implications of the changing basis of competitive advantage is growing importance of having a work place with adequate skills. Developing those employees skills can be one of the greatest tasks. Today's knowledge management system assists the company in training, tracking, assessing and building a greater resource- its people. One of the human resource practices is investing and continuously investing in skill, knowledge acquisition development in its human capital. This requires administering a variety of training education aimed at increasing and maintaining each individual job-related skills and providing development opportunities for which individuals which will broaden their skill base. Management will recognise need for development and retraining when they realise that employees are an asset and not an expense and development is the core for improving the competitive advantage.

Key Words: competitive advantage, human resource management, strategic management, selection, reward performance

PAPER 180

GREEN MARKETING IN INDIA: EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

RAGHU K.V

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR; DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE; GOVERNMENT FIRST GRADE COLLEGE, UDAYAPURA
CHANNARAYAPATNA TALUK; HASSAN DISTRICT - 573225
MOBILE: 9844572224

E-mail: bhavya3raghu86@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Green Marketing is a phenomenon which has developed particularly important in the modern market. In the emerging world the concept of pollution free activity is given more importance in all the sectors and in all stages. The environmentalists are targeting the industrial sectors as the major contributors for depleting natural resources and environmental destruction. Hence, both production and marketing divisions of industries are stressed more to take utmost care in these areas along with fulfilling the market demands. To overcome these difficulties a new concept has born in the present globalized world where production, consumption and also marketing of the products can be carried effectively ensuring environmental safety. This concept is named as 'Green Marketing'. Awareness about the destruction of natural resources has raised the issue of environmental protection which in turn has created eco-friendly consumption called 'green consumerism'. Smart business houses have accepted green marketing as a part of their strategy. Many global players in diverse businesses are now successfully implementing green marketing practices. Various studies by environmentalists indicate that people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavioral pattern. The most of the consumers, both individual and industrial, are becoming more concerned about environment-friendly products. This has become the new mantra for marketers to satisfy the needs of consumers and earn better profits. This paper aims to give information about concept of green marketing, global and Indian scenario, green products, opportunities and challenges in green market.

Key Words: GREEN MARKETING, EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES

PAPER 181

A STUDY ON GEERT HOFSTEDES CULTURAL DIMENSIONS IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

¹Dr. V.T. Shailashri, ²Dr. P.S.Aithal, ³Dr. Surekha Shenoy
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore 575001
India; shailashrivt@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Culture is the ideas, customs, and social behavior of a particular people or society. So culture is mainly identified by the behavior of an individual by simple terms. It consists of a person's values, norms, customs and ideas. This can be different in each person depending on the culture they belong to. Culture has various impacts on the individual and the organization at large. Understanding the culture of individuals by the organization helps it to build one and also enables in achieving its goals. Every organization also has its own culture; in the case of international business houses their culture will be different from the domestic firms as it has foreign assignees. Geert Hofstede has provided dimensions which help organization understand the type of cultures from different countries. This study is an attempt to identify the organizational culture of select companies in the various continents and proceed towards finding similarities and dissimilarities. Also understanding how different national cultures have an influence in the international business by using Geert Hofstede cultural dimensions.

Key words: Geert Hofstede, Cultural dimension, International Business

PAPER 182

ROLE OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SATISFACTION THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA IN HOSUR

Dr B N Sivakumar¹, Sridharan G², Sunil R³

Director in MBA, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering (Autonomous), Hosur
2&3. Third Semester MBA Student, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering, (Autonomous),
Hosur

ABSTRACT

An exploratory qualitative study was conducted to identify the relevant engagement experiences. Subsequently, multiple quantitative studies were conducted to examine the proposed relationships. Further, the propensity to provide electronic word of mouth is non-linear in customers with higher levels of engagement and may not vary directly with satisfaction levels. The findings of this study contribute to the emerging literature on customer engagement and mobile app-usage domains. Future studies may examine such a relationship in different businesses and on varied digital platforms. The findings of this paper may provide actionable insights to marketers, giving them a mechanism to segment customers based on engagement levels and using discretion while focusing on satisfaction levels among different segments. This study validates the proposed moderating role of customer engagement in the satisfaction loyalty relationship.

Keywords: Customer engagement practices, Satisfaction through Social Media

PAPER 183

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS POLICIES OF TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES LIMITED (TCS)

K. Vikranth¹ & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²College of Computer Science & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru,
Karnataka, India

Email: vikranth.kadya@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Company analysis is one kind of tactic in research methodology to study the different aspects of the company such as growth in terms of asset or economy or employee strength etc. There are several industries and numerous companies in each industry. Here each company follows different strategies to step up the industries there by to survive and make profit. Software industry is also a type of industry is a big boon for most of the young population who are anticipating to beginning their career in this field. Software and Information Technology (IT) is one of the segments where number of departments are working together to develop product or to give services. TCS (Tata Consultancy Services Limited) is one of the most reputed Indian based IT company particularizes its business all over the world around 46 countries. It is leading information technology firm and software outsourcing organization in the world. In its journey of business, it was partner with many companies from past 50 years. TCS deals with consulting-led, cognitive powered, integrated portfolio of business, technology, services and solutions. In terms of market capitalization, TCS is the second largest company in India. According to Forbes' most innovative company list TCS placed 64th rank in all over the world and 1st rank in India. It service provider sector TCS has second place in all over the world. In this paper is scrutinized how the company's growth takes place from 1968 to till date. And what are the other software companies in India that compete with TCS, Different industries in which TCS expands its business wings, different products and services of the company and various strategies used by the company to expand its business and market capital. Contribution of the company to software industry as well as our nation and listed number of awards and accolades received by the company and also explored some problems faced by software companies in India including TCS. And finally we analyze the business strategies of the company using SWOT analysis.

Keywords:, SWOT, ERP, Consultancy,, Artificial Intelligence, Cloud compute, software Technology.

PAPER 184

ADVISEMENT OF EDUCATION BEFORE AND AFTER ADOPTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

MANISHA R

Student; Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Commerce
St. Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangaluru. Manishasuvama20@gmail.com
7483547253

VELISHA SHARAL VEIGAS

Student; Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Commerce
St. Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangaluru.; Sharalveigas97@gmail.com
9483887092

ROOPA KIRAN

Student; Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Commerce
St. Aloysius College (Autonomous) Mangaluru.; kroopa478@gmail.com
7899263186

ABSTRACT

Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Education includes moral value, positive thinking, attitude of helping, attitude of giving to society and ethical values. Our Indian social system is going through massive changes to meet the needs of modern world. The society has different sub system and education is one of them. It is evident that with the changing time, education has transformed itself to meet the demands of the society. The education system of ancient period has unique characteristics and qualities which were not found in the ancient education system of any other country in the world. Gurukul was the type of school in ancient India, which is residential in nature with pupil living in proximately to the teacher and it entirely consists of Vedas, epics, literature, archery and modern education consists variety of subjects. Rabindranath Tagore has assessed it long back that the Indian education system need to change. We live in a society where child spends his parents earnings and still not getting the standard education and struggling to get the desired employment. The increased competition in education sector sometimes crushes the creativity of millions of students and drives them to commit suicide. Education is treated as a means of achieving wealth. There is a need to think again and redefine our education system.

Keywords: EDUCATION, ADOPTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY

PAPER 185

**APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN
DIGITALIZATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES**

¹Dr. Babu Tejavath, ²Dr. Wahed Mohiuddin

¹Assistant Professor, Department of HRM, University Arts and Science College,
Hanamkonda, KU, Warangal. Email ID:babutejavath@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of Management Studies, Nigama Engineering College,
Karimnagar. Email ID:wahedhr@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

In a fierce competitive era, organizations have moved from traditional human resource management to digital human resource management for their survival and to be market leaders. Present days the companies are having competitive edge with the digital technologies from one another in order to dominate the business empire. To be global, companies are digitally transforming their human resource management. Innovations and advances in digital technology has made easier for HR manager to take decisions and manage the people. Companies are incorporating digital technology in order to transform their business. Digitalization of human resource management also reduces costs, improves the speed and quality of human resource processes. We are using technology to deliver human resource management activities. Digital work place can be created fully with the help of HR technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, robotics, cloud computing etc. The organizations have to identify the area of their opportunity to betterly work and efficiently use the HR tools.

The workplace of present days is infused with technology and systems. Digitalization processes now have come as angels for the companies which will help them to predict different aspects such as attrition, engagement level, retention and development of employees. The aim of this paper focuses on the application of artificial intelligence and digitalization of human resources with the objective to accelerate and withstand in a global competition of the companies.

Keywords: Collaboration, Resources, Application, Global, Development, Technology.

PAPER 186

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES IN THE AVIATION INDUSTRY

Jayaprakasha.K¹

Faculty, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka,
IndiaEmail: jai4appu@gmail.com

Pradeep M.D.²

Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru, Karnataka, India ;Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Employee retention is an art of using various unique techniques to influence an employee to stay in an organization for the longer duration of his service. It involves the effective management of organization through retaining eminent work force thereby considered to be the mastery of managing resources. Every organization invests its time and money to groom newly recruited and developing them to be an efficient employee. Hertz Berg's and Maslow's in their theory have quoted about factors influencing for individual growth and development. Aviation business is facing a serious problem of high attrition since long due to the shortage of technical, non-technical and other skilled professionals. The retention strategies in business help in reducing employee turnover, recruitment and training cost. It also preserves talent and organizational knowledge. The businesses have inculcated trending tools of competitive salary, fringe benefits, skilled hiring, work life balance, career development, friendly work culture, employee engagement, branding, bonding, open communication, work from home, flexible working, fancy designation to demark employee retention. Innovative strategies for employee retention in aviation sector are the need of the day. This paper highlights upon various modern tools and strategies on employee retention and also covers the effectiveness of organization culture and HR-Policies with special reference to aviation industry.

Key Words: Employee Retention, Efficient Employee, Techniques, Aviation Industry, benefits

PAPER 187

MOBILE APP BASED SHOPPING IN INDIA – A NEW SHOPPING CULTURE AND TREND

RASHMI¹

Assistant Professor, MBA Department, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Valachil, Mangaluru.
rashmi.mba702@gmail.com

Dr. SHRINIVASA MAYYA D²

Principal, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Valachil, Mangaluru.

Dr. AJOY S JOSEPH³

Head, MBA Department, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Valachil, Mangaluru.

ABSTRACT

Mobile app based shopping in India is evolving as a new shopping culture and trend. Thanks to the increased availability of bandwidth, cheap data plans, and increased awareness about the availability of mobile application in India. This paper is aimed in exploring the gradual change from website based shopping to mobile app based shopping. It also intends to find the contributing factors that led to the development of such change. Recently individuals tend to shop over their phone using various applications. It is noted that the country saw the fastest growth in app downloads among major countries between 2016 and 2018, led by a surge in food delivery and finance. According to statista.com which states that the total app downloads will increase tremendously and expected to reach 258 billion by 2022 these figures includes all categories of the applications. Analysing the different category, gaming app is the first top category of active app when compared with the business category in India. The major players in Indian app market include Seasia Infotech, Signoryle, 5ine, Webgen, Nextwebi, BlazeDream. The first major Indian e-commerce firm to change its business model to fit the changing need as app-only was fashion retailer Myntra. There may be various factors that contributed to the increased internet users and opened up a way for app developers, a notable reason for this internet wave which turned the way of doing business for m-commerce is Reliance jio effect in the year 2016. It is also noted that there is increase in the popularity of shopping app both world wide as well as in India.

Keywords: mobile app, app developers, app based shopping culture, e-commerce, downloads.

QUOTA SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ADMISSIONS: A STUDENTS' PERCEPTUAL STUDY

Dr. Preethi Keerthi Dsouza

Assistant Professor,

Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Commerce,

Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri, Mangalore-574199

E-mail ID : preethimauni@gmail.com Ph : 9845596555

ABSTRACT

Historically, attempts towards development and ensuring equality and justice for all have commonly been found to conform to the norms and systems of the majority. Most of these attempts have articulated the need for inclusion of all segments of the society – however, in most cases this articulation took the form of ‘special care systems’ that ultimately led to further exclusion of these communities – physically, mentally and psychologically. Discourses on the principles of social inclusion and exclusion are integral to any debate and dialogue on the principles of justice and equality. Over time the element of ‘Inclusion’ has been incorporated into the mainstream discussion on Education Policy as well. Common ways of thinking about inclusion and exclusion are: 1. Inclusion as a right, 2. Inclusion as effective, 3. Inclusion as political. Inclusion may also be looked at as – A philosophy built on the belief that all people are equal and should be respected and valued, as an issue of basic human rights, and An ‘unending set of processes’ in which children and adults with ‘disabilities’ have the opportunity to participate fully in ALL community activities accessible to people who do not have disabilities. This paper has the following objectives: Know the perception of students towards the existence of quota system, Explore the dimensions of inclusive development in the educational inclusion, Know the perception of students about higher education. This paper explores these objectives through an empirical study which was conducted among the post graduate department students to find out their perception and to identify various issues related to inclusive development in educational sector. The respondents are students who have got their admissions in higher educational institutions based on roster system. The sample was selected at random. The study reveals the respondents views on the quota system in the admission processes.

Key words: Admissions, Quota system, Inclusive development, Educational inclusion

PAPER 189

HEALTH INSURANCE – AWARENESS AND WELL-BEING OF HUMANS

Sahana Chengappa P¹, Rachna Bollamma J.M²

Mount Carmel College;Bengaluru.

ABSTRACT

Health insurance playing a major role as a protection for health is one of the rapidly growing sectors in the Indian economy. People are being conscious about their well-being both in rural and urban areas. Health insurance is not only provided by the government of India, it is provided by the private insurance companies also. There needs to be proper awareness about the benefits offered by these insurance companies by including subjects on insurance and banking in the academics, mobile vans, integrating of all the affiliated hospitals in the google maps etc and also understand the underlying facts of being insured. Before an individual gets himself insured, it becomes a necessity to analyse the opportunities available and the costs associated with it. The major opportunities offered by the health insurance are for the educated youths, middle class, BPL card holders etc; At the same time there are reasons as to why individuals do not prefer health insurance and the reasons may vary with regard to the schemes offered to the public. Health insurance protects the individuals by paying huge amount of medical services with the payment of considerable premium amount in return and this can be partial or full amount. The insurance companies should carefully frame their messages or the content that influence the public in acquiring such insurance schemes. When there are many plans being offered, the individuals need to analyse the loop holes of it and then proceed further and this requires proper understanding of those plans.

Ayushman Bharat Yojana is a newly launched scheme by the Central Government of India in the year 2018, and its main aim being covering both preventing and promoting health, to largely address healthcare. It is expected to cover approximately 10 crore poor families for time being by setting up 1.5 lakhs wellness centres across the country. In order to provide cashless benefits E- cards had been generated and are trying to pool in more private hospitals along with government hospitals to provide this scheme and its benefits.

This paper showcases the awareness level of health insurance amongst people residing in Bangalore and their opinion regarding the newly launched scheme 'Ayushman Bharat'.

Keywords – Health insurance, government and private schemes, opportunities and access, urban and rural people, Ayushman Bharat.

PAPER 190

ROLE OF TEACHERS IN SOCIAL CHANGE: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO SOCIAL WORK TEACHERS

GANESH PRASAD G. NAYAK ¹DR. DUGGAPPA KAJEKAR²

¹Research scholar, Kannada University, Hampi; ganeshprasadsys@gmail.com

²Asst. Prof. ,GFGC Thenkanidiyur, Udupi; dkajekar5@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Change is the fundamental nature of society. Social change which occupies a prominent place in the consciousness of humanity is universal. Man and society have evolved through the times immemorial and have seen rapid changes. In this course, both men and their social institutions have undergone changes that generate contradictory feelings of hope as well as anxiety. The formal education system exists to meet the needs of individuals in order to obtain information and skills necessary to live full, satisfying and capable lives. Education also makes the individual to be a responsible and productive citizen. This paper is focused on exploring the role played by social work lecturers in bringing social change in social work students. This study is based on primary data where 50 respondents have selected based on purposive and snow ball sampling method.

Education has gained more importance and become a priority sector in developing nations. In a modernizing and democratic society the educational system has new values and an altogether different set of roles to perform. Basically education is expected to reach everyone. Rapid developments in science and technology coupled with new economic and political pressures are bringing about unprecedented demands with a constant review of education at all levels, in the developing countries particularly. The question to be asked is that whether the programmes of education are sufficiently geared to the national objectives, the principal among which is to relate education to the life needs and aspirations of the people and thereby make it an instrument of social, cultural and economic transformation necessary for the all-round improvement in the standard of living.

Youngsters in any country represent the future of that country. Role of teachers becomes important in molding shaping the personalities of the youth. They have a vital role to play in the development of that country. In order to make the students to inculcate social values and in order to make them responsive citizen teachers play a major role in molding students. Majority of social work teachers have said that field work practicum makes student to explore the society and also they have agreed that classroom atmosphere is equally significant in making students to develop interpersonal relationship.

Keywords: Social institution, Social transformation, Youth, interpersonal relationship

PAPER 191

EMPLOYEE ATTRITION AND RETENTION – A CASE STUDY ON ARVIND MOTORS PRIVATE LTD., MANGALORE

Mrs. Shilparani K

Lecturer, Department of commerce; Govinda Dasa College; Surathkal 575014
Karnataka; Ph:+918971923582; Mail ID : shilparanisalian@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Employee **retention** is the ability of an organization to retain the employees. It is very important to the management to hold the employees for a longer period of time. If the **organization** maintains 80% of the employee in the same company then we can say they have maintained retention. It is true that organization survives with the bunch of employees who works towards the company. one of the biggest task is to see whether **managers** understands to create and sustain the growth of the company. Both Employee Retention and Attrition are major deciding factors for the success and growth of the organization. **Employee Attrition** or Employee Defection can be explained as the gradual decline in the number of employees through retirement, resignation and death. There are many different ways for a company to lose employees, most of which are typically taken into account to ensure that the organization is able to operate efficiently.

Country like India majority of the company face the problem to recruit and retain the employees. Attrition and Retention rates are often used in business to identify employment trends, overall business growth, motivations and challenges. It is observed that in the global competitive scenario, organizations are investing considerable amount of effort, time and money on **employee retention**. This study is an outcome of the topic called “A study on employee attrition and retention of an employee in Arvind Motors. The main objective of the study is to know the reason, why attrition occurs, to identify the factors which makes employee dissatisfy, to know the satisfactory level of employees towards their job and the working conditions in the company.

KEY WORDS: Attrition, Retaining employees, Retention, Managers and organization

PAPER 192

BREAST CANCER PREDICTION THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING

¹Dr. Shashidhar Kini K, ²Mrs. Akshatha C.H.

¹rofessor, Dept. of MCA;Srinivas Institute of Technology;Valachil, Mangaluru – 574 143
E-mail:skinipa@gmail.com

²Asst Professor, Dept. MCA;Srinivas Institute of Technology; Valachil,
Mangaluru – 574 143.E-mail:haiakshatha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Breast Cancer is the most common cancer and it can lead to death of a women. The long duration of the manual process of identifying the symptoms and later availing treatment may cause the death of the patient. Early detecting the symptoms can effectively reduce the death rates due to breast cancer. This can be achieved by performing various tests, such as Ultra sound, MRI and Biopsy. The uncontrolled cells of the breast are referred to as Breast Cancer. To identify whether the cell is healthy cell or tumor cells the patient has go undergo certain tests.

The Diagnosis of Breast Cancer is classified it into either Benign or Malignant. Here Malignant tumors are more cancerous than Benign. To identify the breast cancer cells we have used Machine Learning techniques. This will help to identify the cells is either Benign or Malignant. This system will helpful to save patients life. It act as second opinion for Doctors and very much helpful for Lab technicians also.

Key Words: Breast Cancer, Malignant, Benign, Machine Learning.

PAPER 193

CHEQUE TRUNCATION SYSTEM THE ROAD AHEAD

¹Mr. Amith Donald Menezes; ²Dr. Prakash Pinto;

¹Assistant Professor, College of Management & Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore; & Research Scholar at VTU
E-mail- amith.menezes@yahoo.co.in

²Professor and Dean/ Research Guide; Department of Business Administration
St. Joseph Engineering College, Vamanjoor, Mangalore; E-mail- prakashpinto74@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Payment system is the heart of any financial institution. They are the social infrastructures which supports all the economic activities. Hence the financial markets require a dynamic payment system which has greater option regarding safety and efficiency. Payment systems were since before known as “behind the scene activity” which means it was not of much importance. But off late a lot of importance is currently being given to improvement of the payment systems.

This paper is an effort towards finding out the history and evolution of cheque clearing system in India along with the effectiveness of the latest system of clearing known as Cheque truncation system. We are using the survey method wherein we will be concentrating our study in Dakshina Kannada district which has 5 taluks and 85 banks. Our respondents would be the customers of major private and public sector banks along with the bank employees involved in the clearing work. We have used statistical techniques to check the authenticity of the data. This work is useful to the bankers to know if the present system is working as per the requirement or any modifications are required. It also throws light into the usage and the preference of the customers of these banks.

Keywords: Cheque clearing, Cheque Truncation, private sector, public sector

PAPER 194

PRODUCTION CULTURE IN MICRO AND SMALL INDUSTRIES AND THE USE OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

Sathyaprakash A^{1,2,a)}, Shrinivasa Mayya D^{3,4, b)}

¹Research scholar, ²Department of ME, Srinivas Institute of Technology Mangaluru

³Research Guide, ⁴Principal, Srinivas Institute of Technology Mangaluru

^{a)}sathya2148@gmail.com ^{b)}sri_mayya@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This article outlined the culture of manufacturing in micro and small sectors. Knowing the answers from the manufacturing culture gathered from 20 manufacturing sectors through study with 87 questionnaires. With the assistance of Agile manufacturing enablers, all the questionnaires prepared. The sample companies are customer-based manufacturers of identical products with distinct shapes and sizes. It has been observed from the study that micro-and small-scale sectors do not work with a single production methodology and no strategic method has been adopted. Most sectors face skilled labor shortages and market requirements shift. The main reason for this issue is bad data storage and reuse and bad adoption / non-adoption of the method of knowledge management in micro and small sectors.

Keywords: Agile Manufacturing, Data storage, Knowledge management

PAPER 195

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SHRM IN SUSTAINING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

Dr. Robin Manohar Shinde

Senior Faculty, College of Business Management and Commerce
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar Campus, Mangaluru

ABSTRACT

Competitive Advantage is the continuous pursuit of an organisation in today's global scenario to maintain its sustainability. Over the years as proposed by Porter it was assumed that organisation's strength in having superior financial resources, technological capabilities and differentiation techniques would help to attain Competitive Advantage for businesses. In considering these three factors as the only source of business growth and sustenance due to its imitability and fast following by rivals is having impact on its relevance in present times. Researchers in different fields especially in SHRM are disputing this fact adding a newer dimension in sustaining Competitive Advantage, which previously were linked with capital and technology. This implies that organisational success does not depend on how capital is being invested or merely how sophisticated technology has been put to use. The key aspects for success include skills sets of employees, complex work systems, simplistic structural network, communication patterns and able to generate confidence among stakeholders. This paper highlights presents a detailed review of the past studies conducted to highlight the linkage of SHRM with Competitive Advantage.

Keywords: strategic human resource management, competitive advantage.

PAPER 196

EVALUATION OF TIME MANAGEMENT ISSUES OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

M.S. Kotian,

Professor, Research: Srinivas University, Mukka

The curriculum of tertiary education often demands students to study for long and strenuous periods of time, especially at times of increased workloads such as prior to tests or examinations. Medical students face a huge volume of different subjects with which they are not familiar and on the other hand remembering the various facts and new diagnostic and therapeutic methods seem difficult. The use of study schedule has many benefits, including better academic performance, higher perceived control over time, resulting in largely reducing and preventing stress, anxiety and ultimately panic and more control over both study and leisure time. Hence this study made an attempt to determine the effectiveness of time management and to assess their knowledge about its benefits. Also to see the efficacy of time management skills amongst the genders. As per the sample size estimation, a total of 400 students were selected from 1st and 2nd year students of a Medical college in Mangalore by convenience sampling. 51% Males and 49% females in which 18.3% were KCET quota and 62.5% belonged to Private quota and 10.3% were NRI's. Of those who managed their time effectively was found that the day before the exam as the number of hours of work put increased the Academic performance. Spectral analysis (time series analysis) was proved with greater score with time management properly. Among these main aspects are methods, study strategies, time and place, exams before and during, anxiety and miscellaneous)

Key words: Time management, Medical students, Evaluation

**CONSTRUCTS OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AND ITS
IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG
THE EMPLOYEES OF MANUFACTURING SECTORS IN
DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT**

Rakesh Kumar B,

Assistant Professor, AIMIT, St. Aloysius College, Beeri, Mangalore 575 022

rakesh@staloyssiu.ac.in

Dr. Babu Thomas

Professor, AIMIT, St. Aloysius College, Beeri, Mangalore 575 022

ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to examine the various constructs of Quality of Work Life and to understand its impact on employee turnover intention.

In the recent past Quality of work life (QWL) has gained thrust in the academic research and its importance has been greatly stressed by HR managers. The concept of QWL deals with providing improved working conditions to the employees at their workplace so that they contribute their best in the work in any organization. For any organization's success there should be committed employees. When organizational commitment is high, it should help to achieve organizational objectives without any problem.

Employee Turnover Intention has been an issue of increased importance in manufacturing sectors. Turnover of skilled employees can be very expensive and troublesome for firms. As employees are very critical component of any organization, some measure must be taken to improve the quality of work life and make employees more engaged and satisfied, which may in turn reduce employee turnover intentions. Managers must understand turnover intent to know how to curb it, because this places monetary and indirect stress on the company.

The study tries to identify the major constructs of QWL and its impact on the employee turnover intention in selected manufacturing industries in Dakshina Kannada District. In order to test the stated hypothesis a structured questionnaire was framed and data was collected using convenience sampling from 398 employees of the selected manufacturing organization in Dakshina Kannada. This study used descriptive and different inferential statistics (i.e., factor analysis, correlation and multiple regression). The conceptual framework and hypothesis were tested by using correlation and simple liner regression with version 20.0 of SPSS.

According to the data analysis a strong correlation is found between QWL and Employee turnover intention. From this investigation, it can be inferred that well-balanced quality of work life substantially reduces employee turnover intention.

Keywords: Quality of work life, work Employee Turnover Intention, Organizational Commitment, Job satisfaction, Manufacturing Sector

EFFECTIVENESS OF CUSTOMER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RAYMONDS GROUP

Mrs. Reshma

College of Management & commerce, Srinivas University, reshmabsalian@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In a higher level the effectiveness in a Business organization with which a task or process is carried out, ultimately leads to its overall business performance. It is how well the Business organization and the people in it perform value based activities by creating tasks, and how well the business functions work together. Effectiveness can be applied to many parts of business activities. The more consistently employees perform their tasks properly, the more effectively the result will come out through proper communication, technology, organizational, resources etc. Effectiveness maintains the Manufacturing, Production and Supply of various places and it makes the customer happy and operation or activity is that which aims to achieve the desired goal as a whole and the company's overall objectives in particular.

Understanding customer complaint behaviour, including how and why they complain, can help to minimise negative perceptions and improve the business by using innovative techniques of customer service.

Keywords : Performance Goal, Standards, Customer Satisfaction, Efficient and Effective Methods.

Dr. AMOL GORE

E-mail: dr.amolgore@yahoo.com; Mobile: 91-9892144819

KEYNOTE

Abstracts

The World is seeing an upheaval as trade wars intensify and people attempt to protect their turf paradoxically, while being thrown in the path of a juggernaut of technological developments and nebulous philosophies of hypermodern business environment that pulls away even beyond the ontological emptiness of postmodernism imploring certitude in the realm of unknowables. Are we then on the threshold of a new World order or more assuredly at the gates of the next industrial revolution that would change the way we do things physically and cognitively forever? Probably, since wealth and prosperity have become more dependent on the access to knowledge than to natural resources, institutions of learning with active strategic plans now can construe better. The emerging trends in Management, IT and Education are building on a terrain with an unusual hiatus of deconstruction and extirpation of paradigms deemed irrevocable. The discussions, debates and research-based perspectives of evolving models in education and effective businesses take the lead from practice of developing facilities to experiences of disruptive supply chains.

Prof. Dr. K. V. M. Varambally

Former Director, School of Management, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

CHALLENGES IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

ABSTRACT

Management education is ever-changing due to change in industry requirements and their business models. It includes Role of the education system in an economy, Emergence of Management education, and Type of knowledge needed in total personality development. Challenges in imparting management education include the creation of emotional surplus with respect to employees and customers, shift from teaching to learning, Lean management in the education system, Partnership for customized management education program, and innovative culture to convert resistance to resource. In this talk, I will elaborate on the challenges anticipated based on changes required in management education in the 21st century.

Keywords : Management education, Challenges, Innovative education culture, Emotional surplus, Shift from teaching to learning.

DR. NARAYAN KAYARKATTE

Former Director of MSNM Besant Institute of Post Graduate Studies, Mangalore,

EMERGING PEDAGOGIES IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

ABSTRACT

With the dynamic changes taking place in the global economy, business and technology, the management education is undergoing palpable and continuous changes to be current and industry compliant. The bi-dimensional developments in the contents and methods of teaching, based on objective and predefined learning outcomes, can only enable the B Schools to prepare industry ready management professionals. There is a dire need for facilitating young professionals to explore themselves to their best in the workplace.

The talk would focus on the changing scenario of pedagogies followed in leading institutions in India and abroad and the perceived need of the hour to inculcate value and commitments in the younger generation of learners, especially the MBA students. The ultimate objective is to prepare them to be open for sustained learning, updating and becoming socially responsible and economically productive managers.

Dr. MANJIAH D.H

Professor & Chairman Dept. of PG Studies and Research in Computer Science Mangalore University
Mangalore. 09449444638 (M) ylm321@yahoo.co.in / manju@mangaloreuniversity.ac.in

IMPORTANCE OF OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE [OSS] COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS FOR RESEARCHERS

ABSTRACT

GNU/Linux is probably the platform of choice for scientific computing. There exists a wide variety of high level languages, debugging tools and other code development tools for programming, numerical subroutines for solving various types of equations, plotting and visualization packages, word processing software which can display equations and figures and in fact parallel programming software to construct a supercomputer with off the shelf PC parts and some hardware. This document aims to provide a list of free software for carrying out the above tasks and links to tutorials and other documents on how to setup and use these software applications. There are several numerical computational packages that serve as educational tools and are also available for commercial use. Matlab is the most widely used such package. The focus of this study is to introduce three additional numerical computational packages: GNU Octave, FreeMat, and Scilab, Rlab, Algae and provide information on which package is most compatible to Matlab users. More over the features of these tools and corresponding advantages and disadvantages and example for each of these tools provide excellent research ideas. There are several statistical programming languages like Rproject, STAT / SAS etc having highly mathematical features, examples for each tools. There are several computer algebra system like maple, sage etc. there are several web based systems, interpreted programming languages like webmin, labview, yorick etc.

Dr. Mohan S. Singhe

Asst. Professor, Department of Social Work,
Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri
E-mail: drmohansinghe@gmail.com

**INDIAN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM: RECENT
TRENDS AND CHALLENGES**

Abstract:

The growth in the system of higher education in India has been impressive over the years. There has been an increasing trend, both in the number of private higher education institutions and enrolments in recent years. The share of enrolment in private unaided higher education institutions has also gone up. Despite the growth in number of higher education institutions, higher education in India has many challenges to be faced on in terms of expansion, excellence and inclusion. The present paper highlights on emerging issues of higher education such as Quantity of Institution, Fields of Education, Enrolment Pattern, Teacher Availability, Constitutional Provision on Higher Education, Disparities in Access to Higher Education, Governance Practice, Quality Control Mechanism, Trend in Finance and so on. Recent trends like privatization and globalization emerging in the field of Indian higher education are also highlighted in this analysis.

Dr. Sharan Kumar Shetty

Professor of International Finance & Banking
Department of Business Administration - MBA
Sahyadri College of Engineering & Management. – Mangaluru.
Email Id; sharansai25@gmail.com. Mobile No: 9902763106

**UNLEASH YOUR POTENTIAL WITH EFFECTIVE
SKILLS FOR THE FUTURE**

ABSTRACT

The contemporary system of education has been converted into the fresh direction, which requires a great deal of capacity to adapt such progress. "Future Skills" sheds light on data analytics, big data, artificial intelligence and IOT in the modern business environment. This is the elevated moment that educators need to keep up with the robotic world's present need. Only when the learners equipped themselves with contemporary technology will the reality of education be felt. It is very important to know the significance of these abilities in our day-to-day activities without which the educational value is of no use.

Keeping all of these in mind, sharing and disseminating knowledge in and around society is our duty and responsibility. Let us all do our best to achieve the path of success.

In order to inculcate these abilities in our lives, we must dedicate our time so that we can only get a lot of demand for our profile. In the given field, research and innovations must be initiated so that in the long run, much potential can be felt.

Wishing all of you excellent achievement on your path of future abilities.

Dr.M.Sriram

Assistant Professor-Finance

Shri Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Institute for Management Development

(SDMIMD), Mysuru-570012

Email- msriram@sdmimd.ac.in

FINANCES IN INDIA- TRENDS AND CHALLENGES

Abstract

The Indian Corporates have witnessed a paradigm shift in the way finances were raised in the last two decades. Conventionally, corporates have looked upon the banking sector for meeting their financial requirements. The ailing banking sector thanks to bulging Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) have started to show resistance in funding businesses any further as it is focussed on restructuring their financials. The paper investigates other avenues of financing viz., raising funds through OFS (Offer for Sale), status of the current debt market, emergence of private placements and issuance of equity and debt to overseas investors. The paper culminates with a discussion on trends in funding corporates combined with the challenges in raising funds through contemporary avenues.

Keywords- Offer for Sale, Private Placements, NPAs, debt market

Dr HG Joshi

Professor; Manipal Institute of Management
Coordinator ; Centre for Social Entrepreneurship
Manipal Academy of Higher Education
Manipal; India
harish.joshi@manipal.edu

**MULTI-DISCIPLINARY RESEARCH FOR
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT -THE
NEED AND WAYS FORWARD FOR YOUNG
RESEARCHERS.**

Abstract

“Research, teaching or problem solving that integrates several disciplines to create a unified outcome” -James Collins

Research is Increasing of our understanding of how and why we behave the way we do.

The simple theory of research is It Organises Information, helps to explain past events, and predicts new events. Research is based on work of others and past research guides new research but research is not copying the work of others. Repeatability is a sign of credible science as replication guides future research. Research should apply to situations outside of the study setting. It is not done in intellectual isolation and it is based on some logical rationale and it is tied to theory.

When elements of two or more disciplines are used in research process it is called as multi-disciplinary research. Multidisciplinary working is often seen as revolutionary by skill-centered specialists but it is simply a fundamental expression of being guided by holism rather than reductionism.

There are certain constraints for research especially when it comes to multi-disciplinary research as it involves professionals in various fields joining hands to derive answer or new direction to the field of knowledge.

The practical experience of the author in the field of multi-disciplinary work is illustrated to understand the problems of such research and an overview of few research activities are highlighted to explain the pedagogy to achieve the desired goal.

Key words: Innovation, Pedagogy, Multi-disciplinary

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Campus Office: Srinivas Campus, Srinivas Nagar,

Mukka, Surathkal, MANGALURU - 574 146 Karnataka State, INDIA.

E-mail: info@srinivasgroup.com, **Website:** www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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College of Engineering

- B.E - Mechanical (4 years)
- Computer Science (4 years)
- Civil (4 years)
- Electronics & Communication (4 years)
- M.Tech - Structural Engineering (2 years)
- M.Tech - Integrated in Computer Science/
Structural Engineering- 5 Years

College of Business Management & Commerce

- BBA - Logistics & Supply chain /
Aviation Management/
Honours/Port Management
- B.Com - Corporate Auditing with CA
intermediate Syllabus/
International Accounting
with ACCA Syllabus/
Professional with ACCA &
CA Intermediate Syllabus /
Hons. / Aviation Management
- B.Sc. - Interior Design
- MBA - Regular with Dual specialization/
Business Analytics /
Aviation Management
Enterprises Management & Marketing

College of Social Science & Humanities

- M.S.W. - Dual Specialization

College of Allied Health Sciences

- B.Sc. - Cardio Vascular Technology
- Perfusion Technology
- Medical Lab Technology
- Renal Dialysis Technology
- Optometry
- OT & Anesthesia Technology
- Imaging Technology
- Respiratory Care Technology

College of Physiotherapy

- BPT- (USA APTA equivalent curriculum)
- MPT

College of Computer & Information Science

- BCA - Software Application/
Aviation
Management/ Data
Analytics & Cloud
Computing
- MCA - Lateral Entry &
Dual Specialization

College of Hotel Management & Tourism

- BHMCT
- B.Sc. (Hotel Management)

College of Education

- Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.)

For details and enquiries, please contact:

A.O. :G.H.S. Road, Mangalore - 575 001

Phone: 0824 - 2412382, 2423588, 2422381 Fax: (0824) 2442766

E-mail: admission@srinivasuniversity.ac.in, info@srinivasgroup.com